

Toni Morrison's Song of Solomon Delineated Brutality and Genesiology

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Abstract

Song of Solomon examines the complexities of black identity in white America. The prime concern of the novel can be detected in the pattern of violence that envelops the black men in a racially constructed and politically dominated society. The root of this violence can be seen in the strategic silencing of black identity. The Americans conveniently bound and violently silenced black bodies. This very fear of the whites as pointed out by Morrison herself, is violently articulated through various means. In Song of Solomon, it is effected through a recklessly casual misnaming of the characters. The prime focus of the novel is thus the "loss of face" experienced due to such strategies.

Keywords: Complexities, Identity, Violence, Politically, Dominated, Society.

Song of Solomon novel can be observed that often the psychic violence experienced at this draws black men towards a wrong concept of power and dominance, two elements for which men have natural attraction. In the context of the novel it is not difficult to see how too often these are sought through false materialism or self-destructive terrorism. Consequently they repeat the same white power system of dominance and strategy that brings back a new kind of slavery to the world of the blacks. The portrayal of Macon Dead's character, the black capitalist, reveals this reality of the black men in white America. It is not difficult to see how in an urge to retain the lost identity black people gather contempt and disgust by the heap from their people. Thus they are not only rejected in the world of the whites but also alienated from their own people. The inauthenticity marked by this rejection affects a black man's whole social structure, both private and public. Possibly it will not be an overstating of the fact that the novel's men are frustrated to the verge of death, a truth appropriated by many references to suicide, attempts at suicide, attack, counter attack, and such like violence in the black men's world.

This systematically imputed violence that psychologically disables any black in America is delineated through the character of Milkman

Macon Dead, the young protagonist of *Song of Solomon*. In fact the novel is as much about Macon Dead Jr. Milkman's father, as it is about Milkman himself. It is possible to say this because the very cycle of violence in Milkman's life has its root in his own family where in the midst of some inauthentic and thus frustrated people Milkman finds himself entrapped. Being deprived of freedom and identity he too follows in his father's footsteps, and become another money monger like Macon Dead. The insensitive and selfish protagonist the first half of the novel presents is an outcome of the very violence that spring from the question of identity and freedom. Grabbing a wrong concept of freedom he joins Guitar, a member of the terrorist organization Seven Days. Thus Morrison tries to go to the depth of the problem of black existence that is constantly at stake in the racially constructed and politically developed America. The novel completes the cycle of violence by presenting the cob-web like nature of it in the life of the protagonist whose search for an authentic name and identity ends up in his becoming a thief trying to steal his own ancestral treasure. Because, like Macon, at one stage of his life Milkman too considers wealth as the supreme human achievement. Framed in the manner of a quest motif the history and myth of the gold finally leads Milkman to discover the rich American heritage- the geog terms but as the common man. His search for self which gets embroiled in his quest for gold, unfolds the less than heroic nature of both the person and his mission. As summed up by Furman, "Milkman is a contemporary black man lost to his community, family, and most important, lost to himself. His true quest is not for fortune or honor but for his humanity". Milkman is incapable of empathizing with his family or his people. He is a bored young man drawing strength from his father's affluence, and unconcerned about real life problems concerning real people. Till he moves away from the city, he does not even realize that life could be different, that people could have an attachment to the soil or that common human values could be cherished. In that sense his journey down south proves to be enlightening and the experience he gathers brings about a regeneration of sorts in him.

The very opening of the novel helps us to explore the nature of violence in black men's world. It is a kind of rejection identified as visibly different from the one African American women suffer from. White women are rejected chiefly on the basis of physical appearances, men's very entity is killed in the destruction of their pride in their race and culture. This strategy of exclusion that frames the main conflict of the novel is reflected in the white authority's attempt to rename the Not Doctor street is as main avenue. The history that is hidden in the process of Doctor Street turned main avenue turned Not Doctor Street is also the history of the African America. The narrator observes this process when describes the 'naming' of a street in the black locality of the novel.

It is not difficult to see from the narrative how strategically the names are manipulated in blacks' lives in white power system. Replacement of one name by another does not mean establishing power over the other alone. More than anything it is suggestive of denial of one's existence in one's world as we witness in the main crisis of the novel. Though the blacks play equally tricky when they begin to call the street as "Not Doctor Street" both to "Keep their memories alive", the act does not undervalue the underlying implications of black reality in America.

The fact of the Milkman is a victim of the complexities sprung from this very hide and seek played with black solidarity. The childhood and adulthood of Milkman are years of various psychic violence in the house of their inauthentic parent. It is informed in the novel's context how deprivation of ancestral property and position makes Macon a "hard-hearted" man "difficult man to approach". He tries to retain his lost position by creating a new one where money and ownership play supreme. Macon Dead Jr. continues to acquire to see that more property and money heedless of human values. He fails to see that his fellow blacks fear and dislike his power and ruthlessness while whites respect his money not his person. What Milkman learns from his father is the lesson to "own things. And let the things you own, own other things. Then you'll own yourself and other

people too". But it is important to see how far Macon's concept of ownership takes him. He begins to consider his family members as a part of his possessions. He packs his family in his huge car and drives around to complete the display. Even as the family members realize, it the black community is not impressed and calls his ostentatious car 'Macon Dead's hearse'. The novel authenticates the fact that at certain stages of his Milkman begins to count himself among his things. Like his mother Ruth, he too thinks that he was "pressed small... pressed into a small package". It won't be out place to cite here the words of Ruth because Milkman's position is no better than his mother in a house which is more "prison than place". Thus when Ruth says it was important for me to be in his presence, among his things, the things he used, had touched the objectification of human identity becomes prominent.

This same suppressed sense of self Milkman experiences is suggestively delineated through his nickname "Milkman". Names play an important role in Toni Morrison's fiction. Deprived of their name and identity during slavery every African American finds him/herself inauthentic and rootless. Misnaming or nicknaming signals the inauthentic identity of a person. The history of Milkman's name both literally and figuratively points to the violence done to his mind and body. Nursed by his mother beyond infancy, an act for which none is responsible, Milkman earns a name that is like a scar in his life. If name authenticates one's existence and identity then it can be said that Milkman's entity as a man is violently distorted and mutilated in his name. In spite of Milkman's innocent part in the whole play his name denies him that position and pride supposed to be vital in a man's life.

By revealing the inner mind of Macon the narrative clearly shows the impact that any name can have. It opens up possibilities for various interpretations as one can see in case of Milkman's name. It is possible to argue that bear or ask for unwanted interpretations certainly tend to be violent for healthy personality growth. In the light of this view it can be said that Macon's doubt about his son's name, thus his identity, in a sense leads to the questioning of his very existence, coming from his father it becomes suggestive of disinheritance from his birthright, which ensures one's existence, denotes any human being his/her position in this world. The narrative shows Milkman's uncertain existence resulting from his father's inability to make out any definite meaning for his son's name. This disinheritance is emphasized by his father's "disgust and uneasiness" in having to accept Milkman's entity in his life. The novel shows how Milkman is rejected even before his birth by his father's attempt to destroy him in the womb. Thus it can be argued that Milkman is metaphysically disinherited from an authentic ancestral identity through Macon's resistance to his name.

The sense of negation that envelops Milkman at this revelation can be perceived in his self contempt at the implicated meaning of the act so long missing for him. The way Milkman recollects the whole incident after so many years makes his inauthentic position clearly. The narrative also hints at the image of a husband substitute as mentioned above. It is not difficult to image Milkman's position at this stage. It is needless to say that this image is a violation of the essential, independent image necessary for man. In this context one can recollect violet's psychic condition at the violent revelation, that for Joe, her husband, she is a substitute for the young and blonde Dorcas. It is not difficult to remember the consequence of this revelation in Jazz. The same image recurs in Sula when Sula realizes she has misread Ajax's name which was actually A. Jacks., and starts thinking of disassociation and betrayal.

Thus the paradoxical position in which Milkman finds himself increases his sense of inauthenticity. On one hand, his parents seek vicarious meaning through him in their lives which are emptied of meaning; on the other hand, his essential self remains oblivious to them. The psychic violence Milkman undergoes at this stage is reflected in the loneliness he gathers for himself.

The violent realization Milkman comes across at this stage helps to figure out the almost none existence.

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Gender Bias in Vijay Tendulkar's Kamala

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Introduction

Vijay Tendulkar's *Kamala* demands and deserves a special applause from every respect and particularly from the thematic point of view. The play is an ideal proof of Tendulkar's dramatic art in a sense that there is a nice blending and at the same time the balance of all thematic point in it. Point, counter point, all the thematic concerns are juxtaposed and compared. For example : Sarita against Kamala, journalism of Kakasaheb against that of Jaisingh and finally as a journalist against Jaisingh as a man. In *Kamala*, Tendulkar makes use of satire in order to scoff not only at the hypocrisy of the urban upper middle classes but also at the rampant corruption among the journalists and the tenuous relationship that exists between a husband and wife.

In the play *Kamala*, Tendulkar exposes several thematic concerns. At the first glance. 'Degradation of women in India' seems to be the theme of this play. But intense reading brings to the surface some more interpretations. Another viewer may consider 'instant journalism' as the main focus of the play. Here he deals with the current issues and points out the 'drawbacks of investigative journalism'.

The play *Kamala* is the story of an unfortunate woman Kamala, sold away in the flesh market and being a victim of sexual slavery in this male-dominated world. The play deals with the issues of buying and selling of tribal women. Tendulkar uses the play to dwell on the characteristic suffering of the Indian middle class woman made to suffer by selfish, malicious and hypothetical male chauvinists.

The play presents a self- seeking journalist, Jaisingh Jadav who treats the women purchased from the flesh market as an object that can buy him a promotion in his job and reputation in his professional life. by exposing the tribal woman in the press, he desires only publicity. he does not have any sympathy for the woman Kamala. Jadav never thinks what will happen to Kamala after this exposure. Through the exposure of kamala in the press conference Jaisingh wants to prove the degradation of moral values in modern world but he does not know that he himself has become a part of such degradation society. It is proved by the conversation between Kakasaheb and Jaisingh. Kakasaheb says Jiasingh ,“you sold a woman to them to do so. ...

You sold a woman – that poor illiterate woman – by doing so” (31).

Sarita, Jadhav’s wife is also an object in Jadhav’s life, an object that provides physical enjoyment, social companionship and domestic comfort. He talks about freedom and equality of women but at home he does not follow these principles. She performs the duties of an ideal wife as she notes down all his phone calls if he is not present, prepares delicious meals for him, etc. She is so docile that Jaisingh’s friend Jain used to call her.

The play shows that the husband – wife relationship between Jadhav and Sarita has deteriorated to a disgraceful master – slave relationship. In his blind flight towards success, Jaisingh fails as a husband also. In fact Jadhav, the successful journalist turns out to be cruel not only towards Kamala but also towards his own wife Sarita. Kamala to him, is only an object that helps him win instant fame as a journalist.

Sarita is not aware about her own exploitation but the entry of Kamala in the house awakes her conscience. After her arrival she comes to know that she is treated in the house only as a useful object. The entry and the condition of Kamala awakes Sarita, so she says,

I was sleep. I was unconscious even when I was awake. Kamala woke me up. With a shock. Kamala showed me everything. Because of her, I suddenly saw things clearly. I saw that the man I thought my partner was the master of a slave. Slaves don’t have rights, do they, Kakasaheb? They must only slave away. Dance to their master’s whim. Laugh, when he says, laugh. Cry, when he says, cry. When he says pick up the phone, they must pick it up. When he says, come to party, they must go. When he says, lie on the bed – they. ... (46).

This dialogue truly shows Jaisingh’s slave like treatment towards Sarita inside the house. She cannot prevent her husband when he sends Kamala to orphanage. But her likes, dislikes and opinions are never taken into consideration by Jaisingh. So, he sends Kamala to the orphanage. Sarita argues to her husband that Kamala is going to stay here. But Jaisingh says to her, “It is I who takes decisions in this house, and no one else. Do you understand?” (42).

Here Tendulkar exposes the male -dominated society in which man dominates the woman whether she is educated or illiterate. The male dominated society never gives her chance to voice her feelings in the house. She feels that her role remains within the house is as an ideal housewife to cook, to rear the children and to be obedient to her husband. The condition and status of women are like living in a cage like situation at home. We can find it through the character of Sarita who is well -educated, but her husband treats her like a slave within the house.

Through this play, Tendulkar comments on the system of marriage in Indian society. In this play, character of Sarita is purchased legally through transaction under the system of marriage. The institution called marriage has given the authority to Jaisingh to dominate Sarita. The play is an evaluation of the role of an Indian woman within the institution called marriage, which is considered to be the holiest of all ceremonies in our society, definitely provides a completely novel point of view showing that women are still mere slaves to their male owners in Indian society in the later half of the twentieth century.

Tendulkar introduced three female characters in Kamala such as Sarita, Kamala and Kamalabai. These three women characters are in some way or other dominated by the male character Jaisingh Jadhav. Though this three characters Tendulkar reveals the condition of woman in free India.

Conclusion

Tendulkar never tries to reform the society through his drama, but in this play he performs the role of reformer by presenting the exploitation of Kamala and Sarita through the revolt of Sarita. After her awaking she denies to go with Jaisingh in the party which is the first sign of her revolt. She feels that she is purchased like Kamala and that too, legally. Her conversation with Kakasaheb truly reveals that she is awoken against the dominance and hypocrisy of her husband.

In the climax of the play, Jain announces her that Jaisingh has sacked his job and she get shocked and unconscious. At this very moment Sarita changes her mind. She decides to give moral support to her husband Jaisingh. In the end of this play, Tendulkar reveals the common mind-set of Indian women.

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Women's Attainment of Self-Conservation from the Societal Clenches in Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's Novel Sister of My Heart

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Abstract

The position of women in our society lacks the primordial aspect and dictated under the norms of subordination and ignorance. Men are bestowed to the aristocracy and succumb to accept women's interactional ability as they fear of what they might have to lose. Yet the society is unable to observe the fortunes they may receive in the future by allowing women to take equal opportunities. If the society wants to evolve and achieve greater goals, women who occupy half of the humanity should be acknowledged. Thus women are suffering from superiority issues, traditional roles and inadequacy of understanding among themselves. Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni explains the need of autonomy and their rights of selecting their own happiness in her novel Sister of my Heart. Chitra Banerjee published this novel in 1999, which presents the emancipation of two women from their boundaries through their own flow and ebb. It narrates the journey of Anju and Sudha, who have been raised in a matriarchal household and left to the patriarchal society after their marriage. As a result, their deep bonding helps them to prevent stumbling from the disasters and support each other at the verge of falling apart. The author makes the protagonists to realise their needs and evolve them out of their stagnation.

In her book, *A Vindication of the Rights of Woman*, Mary Wollstonecraft says, “let them not be treated like slaves; or, like the brutes who are dependent on the reason of man, when they associate with him; but cultivate their minds, give them the salutary, sublime curb of principle, and let them attain consciousness dignity by feeling themselves only dependent in God” (48). Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's second novel *Sister of my Heart* penetrates Solacement with evident to reciprocal bonding of sisterhood. The author tried to unearth the longing of women to enhance their role as an individual and not as a doldrums. Chitra Banerjee makes her protagonists Anjali and Basudha to dream a world beyond suppression and verdicts by making them as a new woman, who survives as a rebel rather than a victim in the hands detestable tradition and patriarchy. The novel revolves around the two sisters who were born on the same day and meticulously possess different natures and aspirations towards their life. But their love for each other mends all difference of opinions and shoulder each other's burden and errors. Anju states that, “I could never hate Sudha. Because she is my other half. The sister of my heart” (*Sister of My Heart* 11).

The Chatterjee house is managed by three widowed women yet it is bounded by the patriarchal rules. Gouri and Pishi who are Anju's mother and aunt always seek the empowerment of the girls and insist them to get good education. Even after the death of both men Gopal (a distant relative and Nalini's husband) and Bijoy (Gouri's husband) in a ruby hunting, Gouri Ma determined to take care of the household and to bring them up to the standards of Chatterjee girls. But Nalini, (Sudha's mother) is huddled in the belief of typical Indian woman, whose prime duty is to guide and take care of her husband and proposes a woman's highest respect will be earned through marriage. Anju is the one who struggles and questions the inclined society's nature and limitations harboured by a woman whereas Sudha possess a calm nature to flow with the events. Their dreams of future are evident to observe their nature. When Anju expresses her dream as, "I want to run the bookstore. It'll be hard to persuade Mother but I'm sure I can. After all I'm her only child, with no competing brothers. That's why I'm planning to study literature in college" (SMH 74), Sudha wants to have a happy married life and a family.

According to Kate Millet, "Patriarchal ideology exaggerates biological differences between men and women, making certain that men always have the dominant or masculine roles and that women always have the subordinate or feminine ones" (Feminism: A Paradigm Shift, 159). The author represents the prevailing case of women through Pishi, who had been secluded from everything due her widowhood. She says, "But when after three years of being a widow I begged my father to get me a private tutor so I'd at least have my studies to occupy me, he slapped me across the face. I considered suicide, oh yes, many times in those early years" (SMH 248). Anju boldly opposes this suppression and states this has been resulted from keeping them as 'prize cows' (SMH 52).

However, the author exemplifies how the women are preserving each other from all the clutches of society to obtain happiness and individuality. Once Sudha and Anju have visited the theatre secretly and happened to meet Ashok. Sudha's vibrant attitude is exposed after meeting Ashok, a smart and lovely boy at the theatre and falls in love with him. As it is reported by Sarita aunty, who caught them red-handed, Sudha has been punished by her mother by putting a halt to her education. For Nalini, acceptance of society and its opinion is very important than her daughter's concern. Though, Anju is blessed with an understanding mother, her dream of higher education is shattered by the worst health condition of Gouri Ma. Both the girls have been prepared for marriage. Anju says, "Remember how I promised you, the night your mother decided to shut you up at home, that I'd make sure the same things would happen to us both? Well, they have" (SMH 91). It provokes Sudha to make a plan of elopement with Ashok at the same time their alliances have been set up.

But when Sudha realises the hardness and expectations of Manjumdar, the future in-laws of Anju, she puts off her elopement plan for the sake of Anju. Since, Anju falls for Sunil; Sudha sacrifices her desire and love. She wants to preserve the happiness of Anju and from falling into a shame due to her elopement. Sudha explains, "When we reach the garden, the sun is a parched emptiness in the sky because Sunil's father will never let him marry a girl whose cousin eloped with a man she met in a movie house" (SMH 124). So she accepts to marry Ramesh, according to the wish of elders. As planned, their marriage had taken place and the dear sisters met their separation for the first time. Anju settles happily in America, her dream land with her loving husband Sunil and Sudha gets adapted with the Sanyal family at Bardhaman. As days passed, Sudha is criticised and pressured by her mother-in-law for not conceiving a baby. The author expresses the maltreatment of society on women if they fail to bear a child. Raged with Sudha's despair Anju exasperatedly says to Sunil, "You probably don't even see anything wrong in treating a woman that way. You probably agree with all those Indian men who see a woman as nothing more than a baby machine" (SMH 193). In order to avoid criticism, woman has to silently bear all the humiliations.

Even though Sudha gets pregnant, her mother-in-law forces her to abort the womb after knowing that Sudha is conceived with a girl child. In many part of India, people always expect a son to born first. This apparently shows how even the right of woman on her womb has been denied and dictated by someone else. In her book *A Room of One's Own*, Virginia Woolf states, "For if two sexes are quite inadequate, considering the vastness and variety of the world, how should we manage with one only? Ought not education to bring out and fortify the differences rather than the similarities?" (79). When Ramesh fails to protect his wife and daughter, Anju advises Sudha to leave the house and Sudha in order to preserve her daughter's life and her responsibilities as a mother breaks the boundaries of a typical Indian woman. She precisely chooses to be a good mother instead of being a wife to a man, who flunks to protect them. As Sudha expresses, "When the test showed that it was a girl, my mother-in-law said the eldest child of the Sanyal family has to be male- that's how it's been in the last five generations. She said it's not fitting, it'll bring the family shame and ill luck" (SMH 238).

Though the mothers of the house at first gets surprised and tries to console the Sanyals, later they start to preserve the life of both Sudha and her daughter Dayita. They try everything to comfort Sudha and support her choices. They stand as an example for providing solace to their lovable daughter when she needs them the most. But it is not the case with every abandoned woman due to dowry issues, infertility and men's flaws. The author gives the resolution as well as enhances the support of womanhood. Adding to this, Anju wants to provoke the other possibilities for a fresh start at America. When Sunil doesn't show any interest in Sudha's affairs, Anju decides to preserve her cousin's self-respect and prop her up with new opportunities, which cannot be yielded in India as she breaks the boundaries. Anju says, "I will bring Sudha and her daughter to America. Why not! She can sew clothes for all the Indian ladies here and maybe finally-open the boutique she dreamed of" (SMH 254). In her striving for Sudha, Anju's health has been deteriorated and resulted in Anju's miscarriage.

At that time, Ashok shows his willingness to accept Sudha and she is extremely happy to have her love back. But again, she wants to preserve her beloved Anju's health and mental happiness instead of her love. And Sudha realises the need of self-sufficiency and to create a new environment where her Dayita will be free from the classification and doubtful notions of society. As a mother she needs to provide a peaceful and lively surrounding where Dayita can dream more than her mother. Sudha sorely needs a change from the clutches of society which is ready to stamp each woman for their flaws and inadequacy. Finally the sisters reunited at America with new hopes and Solacement. Anju expresses her joy as, "But for now the three of us stand unhurried, feeling the way we fit, skin on skin, into each other's live. A rain- dampened sun struggles from the clouds to frame us in its hesitant, holy light" (SMH 322).

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The Diasporic Perspectiveness of Beast and Man's Fatal Agony in Yann Martel's Life of Pi

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The Canadian novel flourished as a powerful medium of expression for Diaspora or migrated people's world during the middle of the 20th century. The periodical power of regional forces inevitably played a prominent role to relocate people from one place to another in the world. Yann Martel gained full spread attention and acclaimed with the publication of his novel *Life of Pi*. The novel *Life of Pi* starts with the chapter author's note and the protagonist's Limbo-state of unexpected experience, as pi recounts events that occurred when he was 16 years old. The 'Pi' in the title is Piscine Molitor Patel, a middle-aged man who lives in Canada. Pi was the protagonist of *Life of Pi* was the precocious son of a pragmatic zookeeper, an Indian boy fascinated by his nation's many faiths but forced by its many political problems to immigrate to Canada along with his family and their animal charges from Pondicherry. During the voyage of migration, their ship suddenly wrecks, leaving the boy on a lifeboat along with few furry survivors; ultimately only Pi and a Tiger (Richard Parker) remain alive. As the duo drifts through the Pacific Ocean, struggling to survive the elements in voyage of the ocean, Pi most also struggle to escape his shipmate; he relies on his wits and his faith in, intermittently, Christianity, Hinduism, and Islam to do so. We never hear from the tiger again, but we do only hear from Pi. He retells his story as an adult living in Toronto, in a house whose decor- a portrait of our lady of Guadalye rests beside a photo of Kaaba; a brass statue of Shiva stands beneath; a prayer rug lies near a bedside bible. So the protagonist suffers from the dilemma of maniac migration of multi-religious belief.

Canada's dominant cultures were originally British and French, as well as aboriginal. After Prime Minister Trudeau's announcement of the implementation of the policy of multi-culturalism within a bilingual framework in 1971, Canada gradually became home to a more diverse population of readers and writers. The country's literature has been strongly influenced by international immigration, particularly in recent decades. Canada's research, whether written in English or French, often reflects the Canadian perspective on nature, frontier life, and Canada's position in the world. Canada's ethnic and

cultural diversity is reflected in its literature, with many of its most prominent writers focusing on ethnic life.

Margaret Atwood is probably the best known modern Canadian author. Other essential novelists during and after world war II include Morely Callaghan, Gwethalyn Graham, John Buell Hugh MacLennan, Mordecai Richler, Malcolm Lowry, Ethel Wilson, Robertson Davies, Brain Moore, Margaret Laurence, Timothy Findlay, Neil Bissoondath, and M.G.Vassanji. Many of their novels have focused attention on Canadian city life, social problems, and the significant problem of Canadian multi-cultural division.

Canada is divided into many regions – the Maritimes, Ontario, Alberta and Quebec, Saskatchewan, British Columbia, etc. Each region has its peculiarities which permeate the novels of writers living there.

Canada is the land of immigrants from England, France, India, China, Japan, Arab countries, Africa, etc. Hence, it is a land of multiracial and multi-cultural fusion, in which the immigrants assimilate their varied social and cultural values to form a national culture, but their consciousness has hidden sparks of their native culture and social benefits. Thus, Canadian literature has Diasporas' characters.

The mid-twentieth century novels deal with social reality. Mac Lennan's famous novel *Barometer Rising* is a realistic novel which graphically describes the destruction of Halifax, a great Canadian city during World War I. It presents a conflict between the pre-war and posts war Canada. Neil Marcrae, Penelope Wain and Angus Murray represent the war time Halifax, the symbol of the old colonial order. Colonel Wain, on the other hand, represents the new generation, the youth of Canada. Sinclair Ross's first novel *As for My House and Me* is memorable. Collin Mc Dougall's *Execution* is a realistic novel. And also the notable authors Alice Ann Munro and Yann Martel.

Martel then gained international recognition with *Life of Pi*, about the son in a family of Indian zookeepers and his journey to Canada. The resulting acclaim, including the Booker Prize, brought Martel an invitation to teach at the Free University of Berlin, Germany, which he accepted. In 2007, Martel began sending Canadian Prime Minister Stephan Harper a book every two weeks, reportedly out of concern that Harper was not in the habit of reading. By the time he stopped in 2011. Martel had sent Harper a total of 101 books, starting with Leo Tolstoy's *The Death of Ivan Ilyich* (1886) and ending with *In Search of Lost Time* (1996), a six-volume set by Marcel Proust.

Martel has been praised for his investigation of gender roles and the subjective nature of self and Diaspora cultural characters. Martel attained vast comprehension with the publication of his novel, *Life of Pi*. The 'Pi' in the title is Piscine Molitor Patel, a middle-aged man who lives in Canada. The story is mostly told in retrospect, as Pi recounts events that occurred when he was sixteen years old. As a boy, Pi's family decides to emigrate from India to Winnipeg. His father, the keeper of a municipal zoo in India, plans to bring some of the zoo's animals to Canada and sell them when he arrives. There is a shipwreck, and Pi is the only human survivor. He finds himself standing on a lifeboat with some of the animals, including a Zebra, a Hyena, an Orangutan and a Bengal tiger named Richard Parker. Over Pi's 227 days on the lifeboat, the food chain is demonstrated as the Hyena eats first the Zebra and then the Orangutan. The tiger then eats the hyena, and Pi feeds the rat to the tiger, train to keep him from being eaten. Pi realizes that the only way to key the tiger from eating him is to learn to coexist with Richard Parker. He marks his territory on the boat with urine and ultimately comes to love the tiger. Eventually, the ship comes ashore in Mexico, where Richard Parker runs off into the Mexican wilderness. Pi recounts his tale to local officials, who do not believe his story. He retells the story to them allegorically substituting people for the animals. Pi's tale of survival on the boat interspersed with discussions of philosophy and religion and doubt emerge as running themes in work.

The novel *Life of Pi* begins with the chapter Author's note. An anonymous author's figure explains that he traveled from his home in Canada to India because he was feeling restless. There, while sipping coffee in a café in the town of Pondicherry, he met an old man name Francis Adirubasamy who offered to tell him a story fantastic enough to provide him faith in god. This story is that of Pi Patel. The author then changes into the story itself, but not before expressing his reader that the account will come across more naturally if he says it in Pi's voice.

Part one is narrated in the first person by Pi. Pi describes from an advanced age, looking back at his earlier life as a high school and college student in Toronto, then even further back to his boyhood in Pondicherry. He tells that he has suffered intensely and found solace in religion and Zoology. He explains how Francis Adirubasamy, a close business associate of his father's and a competitive swimming champion, taught him to swim and bestowed upon in his unusual name. Pi is described after the Piscine Molitor, a Parisian swimming club with two pools that Adirubasamy used to frequent. We see that pi's father once ran the Pondicherry zoo, teaching Pi and his brother, Ravi, on the dangerous nature of animals by maintaining a live goat to a tiger before their young eyes. Pi, brought up as a Hindu, discovers Christianity, then Islam, choosing to practice all three religious simultaneously.

At the beginning of Part Two, the ship is beginning to sink. Pi clings to a lifeboat moreover encourages a tiger, Richard Parker, to join him. Then, recognizing his mistake in bringing a wild animal abroad, Pi leaps into the ocean. The narrative jumps back in time as Pi explains the explosive noise and chaos of the sinking: crew members throw him into a lifeboat, where he soon finds himself directly with a zebra, an orangutan and a hyena, all seemingly in shock. His family is gone. The storm subsides, and Pi sees his dark situation. The hyena kills the zebra and the orangutan, and then to pi's intense surprise- Richard Parker reveals himself: the tiger has remained in the bottom of the lifeboat all along. Soon the tiger kills the hyena and Pi, and Richard Parker is alone collectively at sea. Pi subsists on canned water, and filtered seawater, emergency rations and freshly caught sea life. He also gives for the tiger, whom he masters and trains.

The days pass slowly, and the life boat's passengers coexist warily. Through a bout of temporary blindness brought on by dehydration, Pi has a run-in with another blind castaway. The two discuss food and their boats to one another. When the blind man attacks Pi, intending to eat him, Richard Parker kills him. Not long after, the ship pulls up to a strange island of trees that grow directly out of vegetation, without any soil. Pi and Richard Parker stay here for a time, sleeping in their boat and exploring the island during the day. Pi discovers a massive colony of Meerkats who sleep in the trees and freshwater ponds. One day, Pi finds human teeth in a tree's fruit and concludes that the island eats people. He and Richard Parker head back to sea, finally washing ashore on a Mexican beach. Richard Parker runs off, and villagers take Pi to a hospital.

In part three two officials of the Japanese Ministry of Transport interview Pi of his time at sea, they are hoping to shed light on the fate of the doomed ship. Pi describes the story as above, but it does not fully satisfy the skeptical men. So he repeats it, this time following the animals with humans: a ravenous cook instead of a hyena, a sailor instead of a zebra and his mother instead of the orangutan. The officials note that the two stories match and the second is far likelier. In their definitive report, they commend Pi for living so long with an adult tiger.

Yann Martel's *Life of Pi* uses meticulously researched details about zoological oddities such as the eating and sleeping habits of sloths and tigers to lull readers into believing that the world Pi inhabits is rational. Pi's survival for 227 days in a lifeboat on the Pacific stretches credulity, but Martel is so detailed about the ordinariness of this ordeal that our disbelief is suspended. We even come to accept that it might just be possible that a 450 pound Royal Bengal tiger could be cowed into submission by the movement of the waves and the need to be fed. Martel tips his hand when

Pi lands on an island of self-sustaining, fresh-water generating algae covered in a veritable carpet of Meerkats. As delightful as this false paradise is, it is impossible, and not so pleasant either as Pi discovers to his horror. With this unsettling revelation about the unreality of Pi's world in mind, readers are then confronted in the final chapters with the overthrow of all that they have understood about the story. The ultimate challenge to readers is to which account they choose to believe. Is truth more than what we can see and measure? *Life of Pi* is an adventurous emigrational novel. It is a novel about religion, philosophy, science, and above all, the relationship between these things and Diasporas characters.

Many critics have regarded the book's resemblance to Yann Martel's novel *Life of Pi* with Ernest Hemingway's novel *The Old Man and the Sea*. Both stories have featured on an immigrant struggle between man and beast against fate. In *The Old Man and the Sea*, a sailor struggles to pull in a mighty marlin, while in *Life of Pi*, Pi and Richard Parker conflict for dominance on the lifeboat. Both the Pi and fisherman learn to respect their animal counterparts; each pair is connected in their mutual suffering, resolve, and strength. Although they are competitors, they are also partners, ally, even double, have the indifferent intention to elude from death.

Besides, both novels emphasize the importance of endurance of fatal migration in an irresistible natural force. Because death and destruction are inevitable, both books present life as a choice between only two options: defeat or endurance until destruction. Whatever the real story, Martel suggests Scliar in his Author's Note, thanking him for "the spark of life."

"Despair was a heavy blackness that let no light in or out. It was a hell beyond expression. I thank God it always passed. A school of fish appeared around the net, or a knot cried out to be reknotted. Or I thought of my family, of how they were spared this terrible agony. The blackness would stir and eventually go away, and God would remain, a shining point of light in my heart. I would go on loving". (209)

According to Pollock and Van, Reken TCK tends to struggle more than others with a "migratory instinct" because "an unrealistic attachment to the past, or a persistent expectation that the next place will finally be home, can lead to inner restlessness that keeps the TCK always moving" (125). Even though Martel's parents were Canadian, his father's position as a diplomat meant that Martel was born in Spain and "grew up in Alaska, British Columbia, Costa Rica, France, Ontario, and Mexico" (Sielke 12). As an adult Martel "spent time in Iran, Turkey, and India (12). In a sense, Martel writes the 'migratory instinct' into Pi's character by forcing Pi into a sense of rootlessness. Martel takes Pi from his home in India to the Pacific, then to Mexico, and finally has him settle in Canada, where he longs for the home that he had with his family. But this home does not exist longer.

Pi's experience illustrates that starvation is a physical sensation with emotional and metaphysical consequences. Initially, Pi is reduced to weeping over the first fish that he kills. Hunger and the desperation that results from starvation quickly alter Pi's attitude. He shifts from a timid vegetarian, respectful of all sentient life, to a vicious pescetarian, a vegetarian, who eats seafood. Two pages after he weeps over the death of his first kill he explains: "you may be astonished that in such a short period I could go from weeping over the muffled killing of a flying fish to gleefully bludgeoning to death a Dorado..." (185). Pi attributes this dramatic shift in his behavior to the simple and brutal truth that a person can get used to anything, even to kill. This moment in Pi's journey is one of the most apparent indicators that Pi's stories are about ethical truth.

Life of Pi is again instructive here. Recall at the outset that in addition to describing Pi as simultaneously a Hindu, Christian, and Muslim, it was also mentioned that he was a trained zoologist. This point of distinction is not incidental to the story and the development of its main character. For one, it provided a connection between Pi's old life in India and his new life in

Canada, giving some continuity to a life story tragically interrupted at sea. While growing up as a young boy, Pi's father owned and operated the city zoo. This intimate knowledge of the life of a zookeeper gave Pi the necessary know-how to survive the long ordeal adrift at sea sharing a lifeboat with his 450-pound tiger companion (or at least so Pi would have us believe). But it was also at least partly the cause of the ordeal in the first place. The reason Pi and his family were traveling by boat across the Pacific was that they were bringing their zoo animals with them to liquidate their family assets by selling off the animals to the highest North American bidders. At this time, God did not provide a haven for the renewal of his creation, but instead, Pi, his family and an entire boatload of animals worthy of a whole zoo were almost entirely lost at sea. And but for the ingenuity of the sixteen year- old Pi all would undoubtedly have been lost.

Pi, during his journey in the Pacific Ocean, had a devastating experience. He lost his family after the shipwreck. Though he survived, he was living with a wild animal which may devour him anytime. He almost lost hope because, in the vast Pacific, he believes that no one can rescue him. There were even times that he questioned God's existence, and he felt that he has abounded. With his experience, Pi almost gave up and almost stopped holding on to his faith.

The attempt by Pi's family to migrate to Canada is presented in a similar way to these zoo animal escapes, emphasizing the involuntary nature of some contemporary migrations. As he describes the family's preparations to leave India, Pi likens himself and his brother to zoo animals: "two animals were being shipped to the Canada Zoo. That's how Ravi and I felt. We did not want to go. We did not want to live in a country of gale-force winds and minus- two- hundred – degree winters (88). This comparison suggests some awareness of captive animal's lack of control (it might also refer to the removal of zoo animals from their natural climates). For Pi's father, the decision to leave has more in common with the discussion of the zoo animal's escapes. Pi says,

People go in the hope of a better life... Any business is a risky business and none more so than small business, the one that risks the shirt on its back... People move because of wear and tear and anxiety... Because of the feeling that nothing will change, that happiness and prosperity are only possible somewhere else. (77-79)

Pi explains that "In February 1976, the Tamil Nadu government was brought down by Delhi... it was to Father the crowning touch in Mrs. Indra Gandhi's dictatorial takeover of the nation." (78). Thus, the possible parallels with escaping zoo animals could be seen to liken the Patel's to animals in their incomplete autonomy. The boys are being moved against their will (initially) as zoo animals are, while their parents are moving only to get away from something, as animals are described as doing.

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Anti-woman Religions and Woman-centric Paganism

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Feminism

Feminists argue that women are not treated on par with what they deserve. Their status in the society is still degraded and minimized within the societal norms of family and its invisible handcuffs. Women are looked upon as inferior to men, indeed. Feminists accuse the age-old dominance of the men-folk of being responsible for female subservience to men; It has been pointed out by most feminists that the masculine world cannot justify it's being regarded as the very type of humanity and that women seen as relative to men.

Language as a tool

In short, the patriarchal world misrules its better half and feminism represents one of the most important, social, economic, aesthetic revolutions of modern times. Female subservience, in my opinion, has its roots in almost all religions and the literary history that followed. As to the English Language, terms like humanity, human resources and chairman do exhibit strong notion of patriarchy, though these terms supposed to denote the entire understanding. Only after a long-fought struggle waged by the western feminists, the common-non-sexist terms 'humanity', 'personnel,' and 'chairperson' came into being. 'Ms' is being used as an equivalent to 'Mr.', instead of 'Mrs.' 'which is to be firmly condemned as a sexist term.

What Religions say

Rig Veda: Women are not faithful.

Manu Dharma: Woman is undeserved to enjoy freedom. She is greedy and treacherous.

Buddha: Women ought to be ashamed to show their face before men.

Christianity: Woman is created for man. She shall abide by the wishes of her husband, revering him a God.

Islam: Women shall practice 'purdah.' They should not go out on their own without the company of their male guardian.

Jain scriptures: Woman with her body cannot attain salvation.

Religions, in short view women as mere tools that have been created for the sole purpose of entertaining and making men happy.

of course, there was a time when women were treated on par with men. Women too were hunters then. Civilization flourished with agriculture, and a land-owning class emerged. Wealth brought out changes in man, and each man wanted to make sure that his biological children alone inherit it. As a consequence, morality as an inherent quality was made mandatory for women.

Role of Great People

Some great people looked upon women in high esteem. According to Swami Vivekananda, “Society is like a bird, and men and women are its wings. If one wing is damaged, the bird cannot fly”. To the tremendous poet-philosopher Khalil Gibran, “Women opened the windows of my eyes and doors of my spirit. Has it not been the woman-mother, the woman-sister, and the woman-friend, I would have been sleeping among those who seek the tranquility of the world with their snoring”. To quote the ex-prime minister of India, Mrs. Indira Gandhi, “Humanity is deprived of half its energy and creativity if the women are neglected.” But these voices sound in vain with the well-settled notions of religions in India.

Mother India

In the Indian context, women are brainwashed for long, to blindly go after many religious customs, never realizing the right intention and core of religions which have always joined hands against them. The women representation in the parliament of independent India is still less than 8%, and it is less than 6% in the Lok Sabha. The women representation in our Supreme, as well as High Courts, is less than 4%. Women working as administrative heads are less than 3%. This great country’s agricultural sector efficiently employs and exploits 80% of the women-folk whose labor is unrecognized and underpaid. Data collected by NGO’s clearly show that equal wage for equal work remains a dream. In other sectors, too, the labor of women is underestimated. The literacy of men in India is 65.5, whereas, in women, it is only 50%. Every 3 minutes, a woman falls victim to sexual violence and degradation; young girls, aged women, and even children are not spared. We listen to people of prominence advising us, women-folk, to behave modestly and take care not to induce our Adams towards evil ideas like the silly-Eve. But yes, our prime minister has, to his credit a thoughtful comment, ‘Parents ought to control boys. Boys are to be taught to behave themselves and to respect women.

Women on Board

In Big Divas connection with women are still not on board, an extensive report by leading law firm Khaitan & coin, international network of learned women titled ‘Women on Boards’: A Process, Policy and Implementation Road map found that, among the 1,470 public classified companies in India, the number of women managers on board were 350, serving only 4% of the total number of independent filmmakers on board. The report found one-fifth of the world’s 200 largest companies have no women directors. The largest economies- the U.S, China, and Japan which have no quotas for women in board rooms, had the lowest growth of women on boards, suggesting that unless pushed, change does not occur, the report said.

Administrative Position

Number Chancellor	-	3
Vice-chancellor	-	12
Pro-Vice-chancellors	-	3
Registrars	-	7
Deans	-	72
Directors	-	11

*Women Administrators in Indian Universities.

Breaking Down Barriers for Gentlewomen in the Workplace

“With economic models straining in every corner of the world, none of us can afford to perpetuate the barriers facing women in the workplace” Secretary of State Hillary Clinton at the new APEC Women’s Summit in San Francisco.

According to researcher Kristen Schilt, men force have the most to say regarding those barriers-in-particular, the men who know how women are treated in the workplace from firsthand expertise.

Schilt’s research investigates the world of work, as seen through the participation of transgender men. Take Thomas, for illustration. When Thomas replaced Susan at trial, a man going at an associated company told Thomas’s boss that it was good to move to fire Susan, due to her inexperience, but that the “new guy”(Thomas) was excellent. What the work associate did not recognize was that Susan has transitioned to enhance Thomas at the industry.

In other word, Susan and the “new guy” was the same person with the same skills and abilities. As Schilt describes it, many Trans men “moderate being treated as not just different from women but better than women” at work.

A case study on gender-related barriers – Questionnaire

Do you feel inferior as a woman?

Do you have decision making power?

Do you balance your role at the workplace and home?

Are you comfortable with your colleague men?

Who do you like your superior to be?

Is your labor recognized at the workplace?

Do you face pressures at the workplace?

Do you receive the same dignity and respect enjoyed by men in society?

What according to you, is the most significant barrier for women at the workplace?

Suggest st overcome these barriers.

100% of women answered that they never feel inferior to women. To all the questions they pointed towards the patriarchy that still prevails in the society. All of them claimed that they work hard in vain. All of them unanimously agreed that they never receive the same dignity and respect enjoyed by men in society. Few felt that women themselves are enemies to the other women.

An Analysis arrived based on a Questionnaire given to 25 women faculty members at Selvam College of Technology, Namakkal is given below.

71.4% of women firmly believe that they are not given the same respect and dignity as that of men.

24% believe that they are respected according to personal reasons like power and wealth.

4.6% of women believe that men are more skilled.

The repressed cry of the women-folk all over the world is in existence. Rajam Krishnan, renowned Tamil writer, and activist once expressed her anguish to a young writer thus. “Reasons which transformed me into a feminist 50 years ago, to fight for the rights of women-folk are still seen around, and now you people are continuing my struggle. I do not know whether this would come to an end.

Paganism

On the contrary to most religions, the age-old ‘Paganism’ of Europe tends to have had certain lofty ideals about the status of women in particular. Paganism dates back to the worship of Mother Goddess that was in practice for many decades and ceased to exist with the advent of organized Christianity. The novel Da-Vinci-code written by Don Brown brings forth the historical conspiracy against women through the clues left by the legend painter Leonardo-da-Vinci, who, the book claims o be a Pagan worshipper.

Paganism is a religion invented in the course of the second to third centuries AD; is a broad group of indigenous and historical polytheistic religious traditions- primarily those of cultures known to the classical world. Pagans generally believe that divinity is found in mind and nature. By the late half of the 4th century in the Greek-speaking East, pagans were-paradoxically –most commonly called Hellenes. ‘Hellenes’ or “gentile” (ethnos) remained the word for “pagan.” Nature generally, and Agrarian, in particular, had been the characteristic of paganism.

As for women, the promiscuity, which is the surest sign of her degradation, never existed as a general or stable characteristic of primitive folk. In ancient Egypt her position was far higher than in late; it was high too among the Teutons. The glimpses we have of ancient matriarchates speak much for the older, honorable position of women; their peculiar festivals (as in Greece, of the Thesmophoria and Arrephoria; in Rome, of the BonaDea) and certain worships, as of the local Korai or Isis. Women priests and women-centered customs were prominent. Paganism revered Motherhood and speaks of love for mother.

Neopaganism

Some currents of Neopaganism, inappropriate, Wicca, have a ditheistic concept of a single goddess and an only god, who in his games represent a united whole. Polytheistic reconstructionists focus on reconstructing polytheistic religions, including the various goddesses and figures associated with indigenous cultures.

The term theology is sometimes used in the context of the Neopagan Goddess movement, a pun on theology and “goddess” intended to intimate a feminist approach to theism.

The Goddess movement is a loose grouping of social and religious phenomena that grew out of second-wave feminism, predominantly in North America, Western Europe, Australia, and New Zealand in the 1970s, and the spiritual center as well. Spurred by the insight that women were not treated equitably in many religions, some women turned to a Female Deity as more in tune with their spiritual needs. Education in the Arts became a vehicle for the study of humanitarian philosophers like David Hume at that time. A unifying theme of this diverse movement is the femaleness of Deity (as opposed and contrasted to a patriarchal God).

It is quite interesting that the male-dominant west had had touches of eastern religions in which ‘Mother Goddess’ has a vital role. ‘Paganism is all in praise of the virtuous feminine. If read completely. Paganism is undoubtedly knowledge with new dimensions to the present-day feminism while challenging all existing religions in this regard.

To conclude, ‘Paganism’ which held a woman in high esteem, revered her as Goddess should take over the patriarchy to ensure that women enjoy their deserving status and of course what the constitutions of men of all nations have guaranteed them for namesake. It is the high time women should realize the conspiracy of all religions against them in double-crossing women’s rights and equality, which are yet to be implemented.

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Position of Women in India- Pre and Post Independence

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Abstract

India is being known for respecting women and even worshiping as Goddess but the fact is that women in India have been ill treated and made to face in human condition at all level of her journey right from her birth. The origin of status of women can be traced to Manu in 200 BC. The women were not allowed to do anything independently even at her home and she could not take any decisions by herself whether its relating to her own self or any other family matters. However, there are many other circumstances which are common i.e. they are restricted at home, with restriction on their mobility and alone in seclusion.

Old and Awful practices are another major cause, which means women is always treated as home maker, house wife and to play the role that of a mother and wife. Though there are changes in such old practices in the rest of the world, such norms dominates in forefront in India and is successful in restricting rights and every other freedoms which are required to be given to the women. They are kept away from public forum and as a result in Indian politics the women's participation is hardly visible.

Keywords: India- respecting women- worshiping- ill treated- condition- journey- birth-status- traced-200 BC- not allowed- independently- home- decisions- relating- own self- family matters- circumstances- common- mobility- seclusion- Old and Awful- major cause- changes- dominates- forefront- successful- freedoms- required- public forum- women's participation.

Introduction

During Vedic period, whether equal rights were existing between men and women or not. But it was understood from the available sources that the attitude towards women were liberal and free policies and practices were prevailing pertaining to women were followed. There were practices whereby women were given the chance to actively participate in the religious and social work. Even the women were allowed to select their own life partner and a widow was permitted to remarry to another partner for better prospect .However, as India started growing and taking steps forward towards the civilization, growth and development, the social discrimination towards women increased in all its spheres.

During late vedic period, Jainism and Buddhism emerged as potent religious reform movements which brought with it many changes religiously. Jainism shared various prejudices caused to the women in its passages of canon and in the form of maxims. According to Buddhism, women's

Spiritual capacities were equivalent to that of men's. Religion of Buddhism began as to treat the women and men equal with respect to personal development by the following path of spiritualism. During early Vedic period the status of women were highly enjoyed and had slowly started diminishing during the late Vedic period. The male child were given more importance because he could be legal heir and legal representative of family property. Since the state saw steep increase in the economic and social status which sons started getting, it witnessed the position of women at a very declining state.

The age of Dharmashtras, the position of women reached an all time low. During this age wherein different codes of conduct, prescribed the various behaviour norms for women which were made and implemented. This period saw the exclusion of women from both economic and religious sphere. During the period of Dharmashastra many rituals started cropping in the Hindusim such as:

- a) Child marriage was encouraged.
- b) Widow marriage was looked down and they were not allowed to remarry.
- c) The birth of girl child was considered as a bad luck and therefore in order get rid of bad luck of the family, people went to the extent of killing the female child. Sati pratha came into existence and the said practice became wide spread. Women thought it was better to be sati then to suffer because of that women started burning themselves with the pier of the husband.

In Medieval India, the Purdah system which was prevalent among royal families, nobles and merchant class of people prior to the Muslims empire, started to spread to other class of people also. During the medieval period, the bad practices increased and they are follows:

- a) polygamy,
- b) sati,
- c) child marriage,
- d) ill treatment of widows.

Status of Women in Different Countries

In Pakistan, woman are deprived of their basic rights and their sufferings starts as soon as she comes to this world and more so even prior to her birth. Girl's fetuses are aborted every year in order to avoid the baby child. They think that girl child she invites problems to the family. There are some baby girls who survive all the odds and they become the one who are unwanted children. Such baby's life is filled with subordination with the male members who dominates them right from the beginning in each and every phase of their life. The most women of Pakistan has no right to make any decision may it be to decide on meal or for deciding her marriage and choosing the life partners. Before women were married they are under strict supervision of their father. Further they are always doubted in character especially when they go to school and communicates with other male students. Women are unable to make their choices about their life partner and therefore, their marriages are being decided and arranged by the family without concurrence of women.

Chinese women does enjoy a very admiring status in legal as well as society. Before 1949, china was a semi feudal and colonial state and therefore, there was lot of pressure of patriarchal system on the women however, the same was changed along with new foundation of China in 1949. Status of women of old china were not very admiring since they have no political rights as well they even had no society freedom. Women were absolutely dependent on their family for their financial needs, further they had no rights of inheritance and no right in the property. Women of china were not working and therefore they had no source of independent income. So they had no status as far as society is concerned. They were lead by father at their home and after marriage, they followed husband and in their last phase of life they were been lead by the son. Founding of New China saw various social movements and various law reforms could be seen.

The United States of America is a federation of fifty sovereign states. Therefore there were different practices being followed by all the States lacking uniformity in the laws and rules. The Constitution of United States has given limited powers to states to make laws concerning only to states. Whereas other laws such as property rights, inheritance, domestic relations concerning women lies separately with centre. Section 1 of the United States Constitution states that Citizens are the people of United States or any states that are born in the particular state or naturalized in the that particular state. Therefore, the state should not enact or implement the laws which are against the privileges granted to the citizens. Further, citizens shall not be deprived of their rights of life and liberty without following due process of law.

Arab women have not seen greater freedom or expanded rights since the beginning of Arabian countries. The survey results found that Egypt is the worst country to be a woman living in the Arab followed closely by the other countries Iraq and Saudi Arabia. There are Nineteen countries which signed the U.N. Convention to Eliminate All Forms of Discrimination against Women. In the survey the questions which were put to all the nations, were based on the said convention.

UK was no different from other countries with regard to oppression of women's rights. Women at the ancient cultures also were subordinated to men socially and legally. Women were treated inferior right from the human came into existence. All mention in documents, scriptures and some cases do justify inferiority of women to man.

In Ancient Greece, Athenian women were not allowed to avail the education further they were married at puberty to a grown up men without her consent. Women were considered and treated as the property of their family/fathers. Her family used to take all the decisions for them like marriage, divorce. Further also get them married to another person. In making all the decisions regarding women, women's choice are not taken into consideration at any stage.

Women at Canada has all the rights and protection available for the right development and protection for safeguarding their rights. Canada is a leader country which promotes and protects the women's rights and issues arising out of gender inequalities. In Canada, Central Government takes the responsibilities of making policies on all these issues. Canada is a nation which clearly understands as well as believes that equal rights to all is not only required for better human rights in the nation but also required for the sustainable development, social justice, peace, and security for all the human beings / citizens. Sustainable development in terms of security, peace and other can be achieved, only when women are given equal right to take part in development as well as decision making i.e. in politics. Various rights are enshrined and recognized in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW). Canada is a member of United Nations General Assembly. Further, 1981 CEDAW was ratified by Canada. After signing the said convention, it took lot of measures to make/ amend the laws and put in place various mechanism for implementing the laws and policies. After becoming the confirming party to CEDAW, it was governments responsibility to take the steps as per the standards set in CEDAW. Further strong mechanism is required for implementation. UN made lot of emphasis on promoting and safeguarding the women's rights and therefore, lot of progress could be seen in gender equality. After all these steps also, the struggle was yet to get over and go long way before achieving the ideal situation.

Modern India

When the arrival of British in India, the position of women saw many changes. The East India Company was mainly a trading company involved in trade in India. To expand their business, they started acquiring many territories and states in India. Since they started facing lot of issues while doing their own business of trading, the question of law and order in the acquired territories, posed

a great challenges before the East India Company. In order to handle the law and order situation, the company acquired the rights to make laws related to the crimes. Women were denied basic rights as well which included:

- a) equal matrimonial rights to property,
- b) rights to widows to remarriage,
- c) adoption and divorce rights,

Therefore, the 19th century is often termed as the century of social reform. The criticism by colonial authorities triggered anger among the people of India which had caused a serious threat to the ruling of colonial rule in India. Thereafter, it was declared by the queen that they will not be interfering in religious matters of the people of India. Status of women changed in all these years due to many reasons amongst environmental and institutional factors. Technological changes due to developing science created new roles which in turn have created new demands for the women labour.

Conclusion

Status of women changed in all these years due to many reasons amongst environmental and institutional factors. Technological changes due to developing science created new roles which in turn have created new demands for the women labor.

After independence though, the Indian constitution was drafted and many rights and freedoms were granted but the status of women had not improved. It only during 1954 and 1956 that, our parliament drafted many laws relating to Hindu marriage and divorce Act, succession Act, laws relating to Adoption, minority and guardianship Act were enacted and thereafter the women got equal rights as men and the status of women started developing. Old and Awful practices are another major cause, which means women is always treated as home maker, house wife and to play the role that of a mother and wife. Though there are changes in such old practices in the rest of the world, such norms dominates in forefront in India and is successful in restricting rights and every other freedoms which are required to be given to the women. They are kept away from public forum and as a result in Indian politics the women's participation is hardly visible.

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Feminism Conflicts with Migrant Students and Workers

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Abstract

Feminism the word its not only a word it's came from the inter-feelings of feminine. The word of Migration and feminine it's the same thing, the bird also followed the migration. Is the regular seasonal Movement, often East and west , along a flyaway between breeding and wintering grounds But. Women leaving their country for studies and work, Because, they want uncertain money for some personal issues and family issues, so, they are migrant give up own emotions, desires, aim, habitual, which kind of conflicts they will meet the migration studies and works this is the major theme of the presentation.

Keywords: Discrimination, equilibrium introvert, Excretion, forerunner, interdisciplinary, Discription, conflicts, Contribution, Barriers, Waged, smear.

Introduction

To move our understanding of issues forward in-depth analysis using best impacts how to provide the fact of effects.

Classification of Conflicts

- Poverty – Economical status
- Gender Stereotype
- Hierarchies for Female
- Mental Agonies
- Discrimination of native people and migrants
- Working Priority
- Emancipation
- Tolerate another cruel activities
- Applications
- Sacrifice

It's the little bit of classification wore the female migrant students and workers which kind of phenomenon making in that migrant Place, they are hot react the feelings and emotions, just muted presents in that place. They are like a dwarf

Poverty

Studies reviewed are consistent in showing the negative impact of remittances of poverty somebody's hope only the scholarship it's the main navigation in their life

Societies of Destination

In the societies of destination gender relations and hierarchies as well as policies practices leading to gender inequalities condition the effects of migration students and workers.

Obstacles

They are confused – how to handle family issues between work issues

1. Insufficient Maternity Leave (private sector)
2. Business Plan change
3. Health issue
4. Unequal pay
5. Mental Physical harassment
6. family duties
7. Mother responsibility

Discrimination

Some Scholar Responded only the gender discrimination. The Feminist Movement has effected the discrimination. Like that woman's suffrage, hot equal pay they are not making a decision authority. Native workers or the students responding to others but, the Migrant workers and the students seats also little bit of percentage in that place migrant workers not allowed to join or form unions. Just they are always cohesion the conditional life. But, Enhanced the discrimination classifications, not reduced the traditional country, But, the great remedy in that orthodox country-just revealed their opinion-always warm-up the migrant workers.

Marital-Status also anther kind of problem, that particular women .She is the migrant women means – main controversy topic about the emotions of women.

Mental Agonies

When impoverished women decide to leave their Countries to work abroad, They often deceived or abused. The Smugglers and the organ hackers also used them, and the major cruelty – is. They are included the prostitute sector-unpaid prostitution. So, they are pushed the Gutter place. They are live only like style-corpse.

Supple Persons

Migrant women observed lots of things, But, they are not proposed to anyone , unrevealed dumps in that place. Those guys are forgotten their aim, too flexibility makes on that place, if any work, they'll done it, that is the major concept of others, because they are migrant women.

Mother Responsibility

Mother's responsibility is the main theme of women life. But, that migration women give up their child in native Land-it's the main cause of mental agonies to the migrant women. They are always thinking about the children's. It's the dead feel, It's not tolerate thinking to anyone person. They are give up the maternal feelings. Because, They are migrants –that 's Only blink in that time. They are just think this is the destiny of our life. Just lidden the emotions, feelings.

Labour Migration Vs Student Migration

It's may be same as one. Labor they are working for some commitment in personal issues-Compulsory making a job, after got money. The Students also no one find out the way of liberty from the Co-Students, Some body Studied for Scholarship amount, It's the fate – defiantly They'll Complete the studies. Both guys students and workers also making flexibility in their migrant places. Because Native place people not waged thoughts on the migrant women.

Conclusion

Migrant Women has interdisciplinary activities, and archetypal work also. But, which time they will get equilibrium in the society lots of contributions they was given the migrant places. Many kind of barriers also they had, some times the journal and the books only revealed the conflicts. That is the tiny size of reflection, but , we'll not Know about the full of form of introvert feelings of migrant woman, Some Developed Country also just smear interviews for their popularity .But, Which time the migrant woman rip the obstacles, which one is build the archive the migrant woman, Who is the fore-runner of good and equal activities making for migrant woman. But, Which time the migrant woman-they will show the door of heavens.

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Family and Social Relationship in Arthur Miller's Play "The Price"

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Abstract

For family relationships, the present paper takes into account Miller's one of the significant plays The Price (1968). Post World War II America faced new challenges. The common questions which became prominent were the growing disintegration in the marital life of Americans and the fear of another world war. The responsibility in marriage was the critical issue to be dealt with by the dramatists of the time. The revival of the family ethos was the cry of the day. Arthur Miller, the family healer, presented this question in The Price (1968) and the plays published in 1968.

Family is the basic unit of the social system which guarantees security and well being of an individual. In fact, "it [family] is the key social unit within where we learn to love, come to terms with our aggressions, develop a conscience, and acquire values". Miller, throughout his life, remained influenced by the Greek tradition of Social Drama. He felt that the relationship between man and society is the primary concern of man as far as human life in general and family life, in particular, is concerned.

Keywords: Family relationship, Marriage, Society, Human life.

For family relationships, the present paper takes into account Miller's one of the significant plays The Price (1968). Post World War II America faced new challenges. The common questions which became prominent were the growing disintegration in the marital life of Americans and the fear of another world war. The responsibility in marriage was the key issue to be dealt with by the dramatists of the time. The revival of the family ethos was the cry of the day. Arthur Miller, the family healer, presented this question in The Price (1968) and the plays published in 1968.

Family is the basic unit of the social system which guarantees security and well being of an individual. In fact, "it [family] is the key social unit within where we learn to love, come to terms with our aggressions, develop a conscience, and acquire values". Miller, during his life, remained influenced by the Greek tradition of Social Drama. He felt that the relationship between man and society is the primary concern of man as far as human life in general and family life, in particular, is concerned.

Miller's plays highlight the pathetic condition of the contemporary family life of the American middle class. Miller was "a preacher who sermonizes on the pathetic martyrdom of an oppressed middle class." Due to Miller's emphasis on family and society, it is generally assumed that he is a social critic and thinker who tries to unearth the multiple threads of social and adheres to any 'line,' whether political or ideological. Nevertheless, he bears a quasi-Marxist stamp, and most of his plays tend to become partisan social critique". Miller was concerned with the welfare of the individual. He delivers the message that relations between individual, family, society, and state should be cordial and harmonious. He explores and investigates the causes which vitiate the cordiality and harmony in human relations.

Major concern of Miller's plays is industrial and commercial society on the one hand, and family on the other. His endeavor in his plays is to reconcile public and private postures of modern man. In *All My Sons*, *Death of a Salesman* and *The Price* one of the characters is shown as committed to the family – Joe Keller, Willy Loman, and Victor respectively. However, the drive for success and material prosperity in a competitive society causes disintegration of family set-up, and family relations suffer severe jolt and shock. From the perusal of the plays, it becomes crystal clear that only genuine love, loyalty, compassion and piety, and moral responsibility in human relations can stop the erosion of cordial family relationships and damage caused by industrial-commercial pressures of society. Material success is achieved for the welfare of the family. But this material success takes place at the cost of moral responsibility towards society. The magical spell of the capitalist system which nurtures false illusions of success is akin to the cobweb which strangulates the head of the family. Miller does attack the capitalist system, but his tone is diplomatic. He attacks the capitalist system in the guise of "liberal parable hidden under social responsibility." Miller imparts excellent importance to the concept of family, and rightly so because family is the basic and primary unit of human society.

The existence of an individual is based on family and society. Family and society provide safety and security to the individual. The individual should treat both family and community as his home. One must be amenable to change in oneself and society. Man has a subjective as well as objective existence which stretches from individual to family, and family to the community. The individual is an integral part of society.

Further, society plays a dominant and decisive role in the life of the individual. Culture is inside of man and man is inside of the community, and you cannot even create a truthfully drawn psychological entity on the stage until you understand his social relations and their power to make him what he is and prevent him from being what he is not. The fish is in the water, and the water is in the fish.

The Price is the play which centers around the familial conflict which disintegrates familial values. It shows that the father's money-minded attitude brings disaster in the family, which is the leading cause of discord between the two sons, Victor and Walter. The play depicts the Depression only as a vehicle to unravel the father's materialistic attitude. The father in this play hovers like a ghost in the memories of his two sons. As the play opens, we find two brothers – Victor and Walter – meeting after a gap of sixteen years to settle the family affairs and to dispose of their parental furniture. Their meeting takes the shape of a dispute, and the meeting which was to decide the price of the parental furniture includes the issues of several other costs – the price for filial loyalty, successful career, happy marriage, and breaking family ties.

In the materialistic society, the feelings and emotions of love, loyalty, and sacrifice have lost their fragrance. Even the smallest unit of society, that is, the family is also corrupted by money, which makes man treacherous, self-centered, and disloyal to those who have done a lot for his well being. *The Price* is the continuation of *All My Sons* and *Death of a Salesman*, but in this play, we

find a change in Miller's attitude towards family relationships. In this play, we see the progress in Miller's views in the sense that for the discord in familial ties only society is not to blame, rather human nature and human imperfections also play a significant role.

The Price tries to dramatize the theme that man is responsible for his actions and their outcome. A man should take responsibility for his decisions rather than merely cursing society. The arguments between the brother's point out their differences on the issues like responsibility, love, and loyalty within the family relationship: "Responsibility is a kind of love. It's the only thing that prevents total slaughter, violence, and nihilism".

In the play, Victor is the only character who has a sense of responsibility for his family. When his family is in the grip of Economic Depression, he comes forward to help it. He sacrifices his studies and joins the police force to support his family financially. However, it is the fact that later in life, he feels that his sacrifice has gone waste. This desperation finds an outlet when he talks to his wife Esther, and says, "I'll be frank with you, kid – I look at my life, and the whole thing is incomprehensible to me. I know all the reasons and all the reasons and all the reasons, and it ends up – nothing". Walter, on the other hand, does not take any responsibility and has a materialistic bent of mind. He is self-centered and refuses to sacrifice his aim in life for the sake of his family, which is facing a tough time because of Depression. Walter establishes himself as a well-known surgeon and earns millions of dollars. The ghost of failure makes him ill, and as he recovers from his illness, he finds that in the pursuit of materialistic success, he estranged himself from the familial bonds. He finds himself alone and isolated. He realizes that without the cordial family ties, life is barren and dry like the wasteland. Thus, the blind race for material gain ends in the disharmony of family relationships – father-mother, father-son, brother-brother, and husband-wife.

In the discussion about their past life, Walter reveals that their father had 4000 dollars with him at the time of Economic Depression. Thus, he tries to shatter the illusion of Victor's sacrifice for the sake of the family. Walter tries to dismantle the illusion and pressurize Victor to face the reality that there was no feeling of love in the family, and Victor's attitude of sacrifice was merely his illusion to run away from reality. As far as family relations between Victor's father and mother are concerned, there was lack of warmth of love and loyalty. Walter says, "There was no love in this house. There was no loyalty. There was nothing here but a straight financial arrangement".

The Price has been paid by Victor and Walter for their deeds. Victor has paid the price for his sense of loyalty and duty towards his father; while Walter has paid the price for his materialistic attitude. He is lonely and isolated from familial ties. He is also under mental depression due to his broken marriage. He has lost his peace of mind. In this play, two main approaches to life have been discussed in detail – moral and material. It is true that Walter has achieved success in the materialistic sense, but he lacks Victor's moral responsibility towards family. Too much stress on personal gains makes Walter selfish and self-centred. He does not bother about the welfare of his parents and brother. The basic question is "to find an interpretation of existence which depends neither on a naive endorsement of human perfectibility or a cynical pose of alienation. The real problem lies in acknowledging the imperfection of man and the inadequacy of society and yet continuing to place faith in the human potential".

Family relations are based on material considerations. Victor's father betrays him by concealing the information that he had 4000 dollars with him. But Victor is a loyal son who tries to defend his father when he says, "I just didn't want him to end up on the grass. And he didn't. That's all it was, and I don't need anything more" (Miller, *The Price* 92). In the play, the attitude of the wives is also materialistic. Victor and Walter's mother and Victor's wife are a case in point. As Walter says, "There was nothing here but a straight financial arrangement. . . . She [mother] said a hundred times that her marriage destroyed her musical career. They [parents] were never lovers".

The emphasis in *The Price*, father-son relationship has been discussed in a new perspective. The play shows that in the father-son relationship, the father's role is not always laudable. Franz betrays his son Victor by concealing the information of money that was with him during the Depression. Franz's money-minded attitude plays havoc with the career of his son, Victor. He could not pursue his university education.

In *The Price*, Victor is left with no option. He is on the verge of his retirement. The revelation from Walter's mouth that there was no need of Victor's sacrifice for the sake of family because their father had enough money to run the family at the time of Depression has no value for Victor as he has spent the best part of his life in the job of a policeman. Miller's earlier conception that family is a sustaining force for society seems to be shattered as all the members of the family except Victor are motivated by materialistic ends. There is no feeling of genuine love for the family. Even parents are themselves indulged in betrayal. As far as family relations between Victor's mother and father are concerned, they lacked the warmth of love and loyalty. As Walter tells Victor: ". . . There was no love in this house. There was no loyalty. There was nothing here but a straight financial arrangement. . . . She [mother] said a hundred times that her marriage destroyed her musical career. They [parents] were never lovers".

As regards the relationship between brothers in *The Price*, Victor recognizes and epitomizes the value of filial and human relations, the value of love and loyalty, but Walter is a foil to Victor who represents the value of money and dream of success at the cost of duties and responsibilities towards the welfare of the family. Victor is the icon of moral and ideal responsibility towards family, whereas Walter shirks the same, and stands for money and prosperity and material gains for one's success and benefit only. Victor stands for idealistic attitude towards family, but Walter represents a pragmatic attitude which stands for self-centered and selfish and individualistic approach caring little for love and loyalty towards the family. Victor embodies moral responsibility towards family and society, which may be treated as the main trait of "the whole man". Victor is quite aware of the fact that as a police officer, he has performed his job towards society in a responsible and manner.

In *The Price* seem to be tied by a similar thread, which is the extension of Miller's approach towards fraternal relationship. The family undergoes the same trauma due to the economic depression of 1929. In the play, we have brothers –one who is loyal to family and the other who is prone to self-interest. Victor (*The Price*) sacrifices his interests in favour of the family by leaving the college studies to help the family during Depression. Walter (*The Price*) represents the category of selfish and self-centered sons who leave their home in search of better opportunities without caring for the interest of the family. Here the moral responsibility is abandoned in favor of selfish ends. In this play economic disaster tells upon the financial and spiritual health of the head of the family, that is, father; and the mother in this play instead of showing sympathy towards the husband, criticizes her husband's failure in business. In *The Price*, the wife's reaction to husband's failure in business in Victor's words is of a very unpleasant nature:

While comparing Victor and Walter, it may be said that from a material point of view, Victor is loser and Walter is the victor. But as far as a moral obligation toward father and family is concerned, Victor is victor and Walter is loser. In brief, we come across the theme of guilt and betrayal in *The Price*. Drive for success in the thematic concerns affects the relations among the members of the family, and we can safely conclude that family and societal concerns are intertwined to the extent that they cannot be treated as isolated from each other. Family relations affect societal relations and vice versa.

Welland rightly remarks that "the frictions of family life" are related "to those of the macrocosm outside: his [Miller's] families live in a recognizably real world" (2-3). Miller has used the analogy of interrelationship between fish and water to describe the interrelationship between individual

and society. This analogy means “serious treatment of a human being must encompass the society that surrounds him or her as the force that has conditioned thoughts, culture, attitudes, and values” .Relationship between individual and society is the same as we notice between fish and water. Fish cannot exist and survive without water; similarly, individuals cannot exist and survive without society.

Further, fish is surrounded by water, and the individual is surrounded by the socio-economic and political phenomenon of society. Modern tragedy emanates from the conflicts and clash of values between individuals and their socio-economic environment. Man’s situation is either threatening the survival of the individual or promising him security.

Social surroundings, when threatening, generate conflict in family relationships as we notice in *The Price*. Family is the smallest fundamental unit of society which reflects broader concerns of nation: “. . . The larger society is reflected by the little society of the family. That little society, that microcosm, Miller knew intimately and revealingly documented”. As far as the concept of “whole man” is concerned, the protagonist has to be judged both about family and society.

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Gender Based Marginality: Suppression and Oppression in Arthur Miller's Broken Glass

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This paper focuses on Miller's impact on the suppression of female character in Broken Glass. The play was written in the decade of nineties and forms a kind of continuum- the common theme of dysfunctional marriage and family is at the core of the play. The woman character is again represented in a negative way, in the play. Miller is concerned here with the paralysis of a nation or an individual conscience in face of increasing anti- Semitism in Europe and America. Broken Glass, set in Brooklyn in November 1938, is a two act play that explores the themes of sexual awakening, the result of denial and effect of social injustice on an individual.

According to Murray Biggs, Broken Glass (1994) is a study of both those psychologies: the impulse to ignore what is happening and the refusal to admit that it did happen. The play's whole thrust is in fact psychological at least as much as political. Philip and Sylvia Gellberg are joined by race and marriage; yet divided by both. He seeks to suppress his Jewishness, she to embrace it. He is sexually dysfunctional, she sexually unsatisfied what Hymen diagnoses as her hysterical paralysis with its source in her unconscious, is an effect of both these divisions.

The three important characters are Philip Gellburg, his wife and Doctor Hyman. The play shows the institution of marriage. Philip Gillberg is an executive and the only Jew working in a wall street Bank. His wife is obsessed with Nazi Germany. When she sees a photograph of old Jewish men scrubbing the sidewalk with toothbrushes, she becomes suddenly paralyzed in the legs. Dr. Hyman is perhaps the only person who sympathetically understands the plight of this long suffering homemaker, her fears and longings. Dr. Hyman is shown as highly passionate person, whose counterfoil becomes Philip who is very repressed by the system. The usual issues of denial and social injustice are linked with sexual awakening in the refined and well aware Sylvia who has been a timid and quiet woman for more than thirty years of her married life. In fact, the system does not allow her private space and makes her conform to the traditional role of a dutiful and obedient wife. A feminist reading of the play reveals the plight of woman like Sylvia trapped in a loveless cold marriage.

Sylvia represents the repressed female sexuality that is dreaded by the male centered, conservative money driven society. As usual, the focus of the play is largely upon the two male characters. Sylvia just happens to be a secondary prop to them.

The Broken Glass has two types of Women, Sylvia and Margaret. Sylvia is meek and dominated by her abusive and controlling husband. She does not find any fulfillment in her married life. She has been forced to suppress her real feelings and sexual desires in order to save her marriage of convenience. She does this sacrifice for the larger good of her parental family that is dependent on Philip. Margaret is the opposite: vivacious, active and perceptive, keeping an eye on the extra-marital relationship of a philandering husband.

In the play, the paralyzed Sylvia comes to discover her suppressed sexuality and other desires, in fact, her identity as a woman through the sympathetic doctor Hyman who praises her and her body in very flattering terms. This praise makes her aware of her own body, her desires and dreams. She has been long suppressed and neglected in her marital home. Doctor Hyman offers her sympathy, understanding and love. In the end Sylvia is taunted by her suspicious husband and made to stand up, which she does finally gets the courage and overcomes her initial guilt. Even Margaret and Doctor Hyman are pleasantly shocked to see this sudden change in an otherwise quiet and silently enduring Sylvia. For twenty years, as suggested in the play, Sylvia could not get intimate pleasure from her husband, thus forcing herself to a life of a nun in her own house. But Doctor Hyman changes all that. She is no longer in denial about her body and her suppressed sexuality. She finds her release before her collapsed husband and feels liberated by that sight of her fallen tormentor.

The Holocaust and its terrible images of persecution of the Jews leaves her paralyzed but in the end, her will to live and find meaning in life makes her come out of her hysterical paralysis. The collapsed Philip and an encouraging Hyman trigger her recovery. Seen this way, from a feminist angle, Sylvia becomes a symbol of recovery from oppression. She finds her freedom and reclaims her sexuality in those final moments of confrontation with her husband. The Play Broken Glass, on a feminist reading reveals the role of sexuality in the release and liberation of an oppressed woman. Glass is to be broken by somebody and Sylvia does it in this play. As usual, the playwright focuses more on the male characters than the female ones. His sympathies are with the male viewpoint only. Women although on marginality forms common emotional lexicon of disillusionment, pain, humiliation and rejection that enables them to arrive at a better understanding of themselves and their psyches.

Thus, Women are the other in Arthur Miller's theatrical world. They are powerless, suppressed and subordinated by the patriarchal system that has got precedence over the class structure in the advanced capitalist model called America, the very citadel of democratic rights. Women, however are the second sex, despite the political rhetoric. Women and marginality go together in the artistic world of Arthur Miller.

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The Dramatic Technique - Symbolism in Girish Karnad's Tughlaq

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Abstract

This paper is an attempt to study Girish Karnad's Tughlaq as a history play. Tughlaq is a play of many wonderful facts. A countless evidence of Karnad's dramatic achievement in Tughlaq is its immediate success and its secret lies in the techniques employed by playwright. It is immensely serious and also entertaining. It is the result of a magnificent effort of both intellectual energy and poetic imagination. It is full of pathos and sympathy. In order to produce such effects in the theatre Karnad, very skillfully employed various devices like spectacle, quick shift of scenes, quick shift of scenes, blackout, poetic elements, disguise, irony and symbolism.

Keywords: Tughlaq, Sympathy, Imagination, Techniques, Pathos, Symbolism.

Karnad has designed special costumes for Muhammad Tughlaq and other characters, keeping in view that they belong to the 14th century India and Muhammad was the Sultan, and also a great scholar. The 'visual aspects of production' on the stage are remarkably effective, and natural. He has used another technique of poetic sensibility. He endows the protagonist with rich poetic imagination. Muhammad, so often, becomes lyrical in his speeches in order to be convincing, fair, just and thereby he tries to win sympathy and support of his people so that they should 'understand' his visionary plans. Muhammad at times uses his poetic quality to move the audience emotionally, to exploit their sentiments. When he is deeply anguished and frustrated to think of his failures that he couldn't translate his dreams and ideals into reality Muhammad displays his poetic sensibility. His pathetic words:

I wanted to make for myself an image of Sadi's poems. I wanted every rose in it to be a poem.

Karnad's use of various symbols in Tughlaq is a part of dramatic technique through which he tries to explore the "inner landscape of the dramatic persona." In this context, Aziz and Aazam, Chess, Python and The prayer are striking symbols. These two characters symbolize those who are opportunists and men without any principle. Under disguise they cheat and deceive the eyes of others including the Sultan and

take undue advantages of the liberal, democratic and secular policies of Muhammad. Interestingly enough, the playwright achieves his satiric purpose through them. Through Aziz Karnad aims at justifying the statement that politics is the last refuge of scoundrels. Aziz takes delight in harming others and misappropriating huge public funds for his selfish ends. He symbolizes the class of such rogues and scoundrels even in present day politics.

The game of chess symbolizes the game of politics going on in the entire kingdom. Muhammad uses his brain in check-mating others in dealing with revolts and enemies as he does on the chess-board. He plays chess to solve intricate political problems and moves. 'Through chess, Karnad has highlighted Muhammad's manipulative skills in dealing with his adversaries.

He plays them as political pawns to gain his ends". The word python is used by the Old Man in Scene Eight for a long passage within the Daultabad fort. When he is asked about it by the young man the old man says, "yes, it's a long passage, a big passage, coiled like an enormous hollow python inside the belly of the fort. And we shall be far, far happier when that python breaks out and swallows everything in sight- every man, woman, child, and beast". The old man uses the python symbol to suggest that the fort is no longer a safe place on account of the cruel, savage and tyrannical behavior of the Sultan. The atmosphere within and without the fort had become hellish and chaotic where people had to die for no fault of their own, but due to starvation, want of medical aid. The economy of the country had gone to dogs due to bad policies of Sultan. Food riots had shaken the foundation of the fort as it is reported towards the end of the play. The old man also symbolically suggests destructive attitude of the Sultan who had become a savage, a tyrant and hence there was a danger for every man, woman, and child of being swallowed by the python. What a degeneration of Muhammad's personality!

Prayer is used as a symbol to reveal the 'real' Muhammad, altogether different from the 'ideal' one. The playwright deliberately creates an ironical situation at the time of prayer when Muhammad Tughlaq faces violent attack of his rebellions. Although he could avoid the aim, he must have been reminded of what he himself had done at the time of prayer killed his father and brother, as it was the talk of the town. Prayer is the time when one is always unarmed. It's a holy time. It must not be vitiated. If one does it he is a sinner. Muhammad forbids prayer in his kingdom when he realizes, though too late, that "prayers too are ridden with disease and must be exiled." This again is symbolic of hastening of Tughlaq's degeneration. With the 'exile' of prayer, something 'holy' within Tughlaq also is exiled. He is divorced from idealism, virtue and humanism. He becomes callous, cruel, revengeful and tyrant. He doesn't hesitate in getting his set-mother stoned to death as she had owned up to have Killed Nijib.

Vultures are the birds of prey symbolized by Tughlaq government officers, Amirs and the trusted ones who had turned hostile. His kingdom is now "honeycomb of diseases" and Muhammad can't leave "the patient in wilderness" unattended. His misery is that the birds are very close to him and every moment he expects a beak to dig into him and tear a muscle out. All his dreams, ideals and aspiration have ended in smoke and now he resembles a disillusioned romantic. The vultures thus symbolize his spiritual agony and anguish.

Thus Karnad has used symbols to make the play dramatic and forceful. His symbols have great emotional value. With symbols, the playwright has adorned his language and made his expression rich and effective. It is also one of the techniques employed in Tughlaq. In the light of the above, it can be said confidently that Karnad, with his dramatic skill and imagination, has made Tughlaq wonderful, fascinating and rich both in theme and technique.

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Toni Morrison's Song of Solomon Delineated Brutality and Genesiology

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Abstract

Song of Solomon examines the complexities of black identity in white America. The prime concern of the novel can be detected in the pattern of violence that envelops the black men in a racially constructed and politically dominated society. The root of this violence can be seen in the strategic silencing of black identity. The Americans conveniently bound and violently silenced black bodies. This very fear of the whites as pointed out by Morrison herself, is violently articulated through various means. In Song of Solomon, it is effected through a recklessly casual misnaming of the characters. The prime focus of the novel is thus the "loss of face" experienced due to such strategies.

Keywords: Complexities, Identity, Violence, Politically, Dominated, Society.

Song of Solomon novel can be observed that often the psychic violence experienced at this draws black men towards a wrong concept of power and dominance, two elements for which men have natural attraction. In the context of the novel it is not difficult to see how too often these are sought through false materialism or self-destructive terrorism. Consequently they repeat the same white power system of dominance and strategy that brings back a new kind of slavery to the world of the blacks. The portrayal of Macon Dead's character, the black capitalist, reveals this reality of the black men in white America. It is not difficult to see how in an urge to retain the lost identity black people gather contempt and disgust by the heap from their people. Thus they are not only rejected in the world of the whites but also alienated from their own people. The inauthenticity marked by this rejection affects a black man's whole social structure, both private and public. Possibly it will not be an overstating of the fact that the novel's men are frustrated to the verge of death, a truth appropriated by many references to suicide, attempts at suicide, attack, counter attack, and such like violence in the black men's world.

This systematically imputed violence that psychologically disables any black in America is delineated through the character of Milkman

Macon Dead, the young protagonist of *Song of Solomon*. In fact the novel is as much about Macon Dead Jr. Milkman's father, as it is about Milkman himself. It is possible to say this because the very cycle of violence in Milkman's life has its root in his own family where in the midst of some inauthentic and thus frustrated people Milkman finds himself entrapped. Being deprived of freedom and identity he too follows in his father's footsteps, and become another money monger like Macon Dead. The insensitive and selfish protagonist the first half of the novel presents is an outcome of the very violence that spring from the question of identity and freedom. Grabbing a wrong concept of freedom he joins Guitar, a member of the terrorist organization Seven Days. Thus Morrison tries to go to the depth of the problem of black existence that is constantly at stake in the racially constructed and politically developed America. The novel completes the cycle of violence by presenting the cob-web like nature of it in the life of the protagonist whose search for an authentic name and identity ends up in his becoming a thief trying to steal his own ancestral treasure. Because, like Macon, at one stage of his life Milkman too considers wealth as the supreme human achievement. Framed in the manner of a quest motif the history and myth of the gold finally leads Milkman to discover the rich American heritage- the geog terms but as the common man. His search for self which gets embroiled in his quest for gold, unfolds the less than heroic nature of both the person and his mission. As summed up by Furman, "Milkman is a contemporary black man lost to his community, family, and most important, lost to himself. His true quest is not for fortune or honor but for his humanity". Milkman is incapable of empathizing with his family or his people. He is a bored young man drawing strength from his father's affluence, and unconcerned about real life problems concerning real people. Till he moves away from the city, he does not even realize that life could be different, that people could have an attachment to the soil or that common human values could be cherished. In that sense his journey down south proves to be enlightening and the experience he gathers brings about a regeneration of sorts in him.

The very opening of the novel helps us to explore the nature of violence in black men's world. It is a kind of rejection identified as visibly different from the one African American women suffer from. White women are rejected chiefly on the basis of physical appearances, men's very entity is killed in the destruction of their pride in their race and culture. This strategy of exclusion that frames the main conflict of the novel is reflected in the white authority's attempt to rename the Not Doctor street is as main avenue. The history that is hidden in the process of Doctor Street turned main avenue turned Not Doctor Street is also the history of the African America. The narrator observes this process when describes the 'naming' of a street in the black locality of the novel.

It is not difficult to see from the narrative how strategically the names are manipulated in blacks' lives in white power system. Replacement of one name by another does not mean establishing power over the other alone. More than anything it is suggestive of denial of one's existence in one's world as we witness in the main crisis of the novel. Though the blacks play equally tricky when they begin to call the street as "Not Doctor Street" both to "Keep their memories alive", the act does not undervalue the underlying implications of black reality in America.

The fact of the Milkman is a victim of the complexities sprung from this very hide and seek played with black solidarity. The childhood and adulthood of Milkman are years of various psychic violence in the house of their inauthentic parent. It is informed in the novel's context how deprivation of ancestral property and position makes Macon a "hard-hearted" man "difficult man to approach". He tries to retain his lost position by creating a new one where money and ownership play supreme. Macon Dead Jr. continues to acquire to see that more property and money heedless of human values. He fails to see that his fellow blacks fear and dislike his power and ruthlessness while whites respect his money not his person. What Milkman learns from his father is the lesson to "own things. And let the things you own, own other things. Then you'll own yourself and other

people too". But it is important to see how far Macon's concept of ownership takes him. He begins to consider his family members as a part of his possessions. He packs his family in his huge car and drives around to complete the display. Even as the family members realize, it the black community is not impressed and calls his ostentatious car 'Macon Dead's hearse'. The novel authenticates the fact that at certain stages of his Milkman begins to count himself among his things. Like his mother Ruth, he too thinks that he was "pressed small... pressed into a small package". It won't be out place to cite here the words of Ruth because Milkman's position is no better than his mother in a house which is more "prison than place". Thus when Ruth says it was important for me to be in his presence, among his things, the things he used, had touched the objectification of human identity becomes prominent.

This same suppressed sense of self Milkman experiences is suggestively delineated through his nickname "Milkman". Names play an important role in Toni Morrison's fiction. Deprived of their name and identity during slavery every African American finds him/herself inauthentic and rootless. Misnaming or nicknaming signals the inauthentic identity of a person. The history of Milkman's name both literally and figuratively points to the violence done to his mind and body. Nursed by his mother beyond infancy, an act for which none is responsible, Milkman earns a name that is like a scar in his life. If name authenticates one's existence and identity then it can be said that Milkman's entity as a man is violently distorted and mutilated in his name. In spite of Milkman's innocent part in the whole play his name denies him that position and pride supposed to be vital in a man's life.

By revealing the inner mind of Macon the narrative clearly shows the impact that any name can have. It opens up possibilities for various interpretations as one can see in case of Milkman's name. It is possible to argue that bear or ask for unwanted interpretations certainly tend to be violent for healthy personality growth. In the light of this view it can be said that Macon's doubt about his son's name, thus his identity, in a sense leads to the questioning of his very existence, coming from his father it becomes suggestive of disinheritance from his birthright, which ensures one's existence, denotes any human being his/her position in this world. The narrative shows Milkman's uncertain existence resulting from his father's inability to make out any definite meaning for his son's name. This disinheritance is emphasized by his father's "disgust and uneasiness" in having to accept Milkman's entity in his life. The novel shows how Milkman is rejected even before his birth by his father's attempt to destroy him in the womb. Thus it can be argued that Milkman is metaphysically disinherited from an authentic ancestral identity through Macon's resistance to his name.

The sense of negation that envelops Milkman at this revelation can be perceived in his self contempt at the implicated meaning of the act so long missing for him. The way Milkman recollects the whole incident after so many years makes his inauthentic position clearly. The narrative also hints at the image of a husband substitute as mentioned above. It is not difficult to image Milkman's position at this stage. It is needless to say that this image is a violation of the essential, independent image necessary for man. In this context one can recollect violet's psychic condition at the violent revelation, that for Joe, her husband, she is a substitute for the young and blonde Dorcas. It is not difficult to remember the consequence of this revelation in Jazz. The same image recurs in Sula when Sula realizes she has misread Ajax's name which was actually A. Jacks., and starts thinking of disassociation and betrayal.

Thus the paradoxical position in which Milkman finds himself increases his sense of inauthenticity. On one hand, his parents seek vicarious meaning through him in their lives which are emptied of meaning; on the other hand, his essential self remains oblivious to them. The psychic violence Milkman undergoes at this stage is reflected in the loneliness he gathers for himself.

The violent realization Milkman comes across at this stage helps to figure out the almost none existence.

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Gender-Based Marginality in Toni Morrison's Beloved

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Abstract

The focus of this paper is to separate gender issues in literature. It deals with how writers build female characters in their works. Before Shakespeare's period, women characters are notable personalities in literature. This paper mainly focuses on Toni Morrison's female characters through her novel Beloved. Gender defines the behaviour of the individual, how he or she walks, talks, eats and socializes and nearly all other features of everyday life. Gender signifies in the definition of the self. Beloved expresses a black woman who explores the specific ways in how black women suffer. Gender will be examined with a particular allusion to feminism. Feminism as a social philosophy, it shares equal opportunities for career building and self-growth. Feminism is a broad area dealing with the matters of women. Feminism is not only spoken about male domination but also developments of women community. This study is significant for its exclusive focus on the work written by a black woman, her cultural background, her presentation of female characters and their relationships with one another and with male characters. Inequality comes from the rebuttal of equal rights. The main obstacle to equality is sexism. It also examines significant for adopting a female framework for the interpretation of literature written by woman, rather than adopting a male perspective.

Keywords: Gender, Feminism, Refutation, Sexism, Marginality.

The focus of this paper is to analyse gender issues in literature. It deals with how writers build female characters in their works. Before Shakespeare's period, women characters are notable personalities in literature. This paper mainly focuses on Toni Morrison's female characters through her novel Beloved. Gender defines the behaviour of the individual, how he or she walks, talks, eats and socialises and nearly all other features of everyday life. Gender signifies in the definition of the self. Beloved expresses a black woman who explores the specific ways in how black women suffer. Gender will be examined with extraordinary citation to feminism. Feminism as a social philosophy, it shares equal opportunities for career building and self-growth. Feminism is a broad area dispensing with the concerns of women. Feminism is not only spoken about male domination but also developments of women community. This study is significant for its particular focus on the work written by a black

woman, her cultural background, her presentation of female characters and their relationships with one another and with male characters. Inequality comes from the refusal of equal rights. The main obstacle to equality is sexism. It also examines significant for adopting a female framework for the interpretation of literature written by woman, rather than adopting a male perspective.

The relationship between men and women varies in the literature. However, women are generally represented as the marginalized section of society in one way or the other. The role of the man as a dominating figure over woman might be traced back to the ancient pre-historic period. In the Elizabethan period, particularly in the romantic comedies of Shakespeare, female protagonists have been represented as charming and glistening beauty meant exclusively for man's sensual gratification. All the hazardous undertaking is conducted by male characters either for possessing any beautiful and helpless lady or for power and prestige that are not supposed to be in a lot of women. In the nineteenth century, problematic issues of women's marginalization in the patriarchal society were getting the high water mark among a myriad of problems. The Victorian literature, particularly the novels, highlights the emerging image of women. The preoccupation with the place of women was also a recurring theme in the works of the late nineteenth century.

In American literature, particularly in black literature, feminism and racism have played crucial roles. The writers of African American literature would be the base of the events that were taking place in the world around them and consolidate them into their novels. This is the stable and dominant voice in their literature. They have suffered from the attempts of white slave owners to try and erase not only the history of African American but their culture as well.

They had to work; and confer to the aesthetics of this country, they were not beautiful. But neither were they, men. Any intelligence or aggressiveness on their part, qualities necessary for participation in the work world, were constructed as and uninspired (Barbara 72).

The birth of women writers, the growth of female education, the extension of teaching as a female profession and the intensification of a women's literary market are consequently the entire consistent lexis of feminism in a capitalizing global economy. Women writers became an integral part of the literary backdrop, other than until the end of time as representatives of their gender rather than as individuals.

Beloved is Toni Morrison's fifth novel, which published in 1987 as Morrison was taking pleasure in growing popularity and accomplishment. Morrison raises many unanswered topics to think over these pressing issues. What it means to be a mother regularly and what it means to be a mother in slavery. Think about Sethe's relationship with her biological mother, Nan and Baby's relationship with her children and so on.

In Toni Morrison's *Beloved*, she clearly explains gender differences between men and women slaves. Although sometimes the roles overlap, they differ to some extent. As earlier mentioned, Morrison's *Beloved* is a heart-rending story of Sethe, a women slave who escapes the brutality of slave masters at Kentucky to freedom at Cincinnati. Through the eyes of the heroine, her mother and mother-in-law, Babby Suggs, the roles of female slaves are illustrious from those of female slaves such as her husband. Halle and his colleagues like Paul D, Sixo and others. The dehumanizing roles that slaves play cause a deep sense of alienation-estrangement from the self or rather internal fragmentation. Hira Ali observes that *Beloved*'s "fragmented structure" (1442) gives a hint of the characters' sense of alienation that is a consequence of the dehumanizing nature of slavery. Morrison uses some flashbacks that disrupt the chronological order of events.

Beloved represents inter-relatedness among the individual identity and the communal identity of blacks. Stories of two freed slaves, they were Suggs, and Paul D are paralleled to analyze the relations among slaves and master-slave. Resultantly, declaring the need of an individual to retrieve an identity for them before having the bond with the community. In this connection, Morrison

condemns the traditional values associated with white male suppression. She proposes a gender model for blacks based on the mutual suffering of an imprisoned past and struggle for the future of freedom and equality. The battle of black women for the realization of self is eminent in both novels under discussion. It challenges the cultural construction of gender roles by the narrative of two women who are employed in a struggle for the realization of self. In the lives of black woman, brutality makes motherhood a two folded burden. Firstly, they have to view their children who were sold off and experiencing the traumas of slavery. Secondly, most of their children are conceived by rape rather than marital relations. For example, *Beloved* is not a product of hatred, and she wants to want to restrain her from slavery. As Morrison puts, “whites may make her filthy all right, but not her best thing, her beautiful, magical best thing – the part of her that was clean” (*Beloved* 296). Sethe Suggs tries to keep away her children from the impacts of slavery.

The emotional hunger of the child constitutes the essential psychological drama of the novel. An injured, enraged baby is the central figure of the book. It is present in the title character of *Beloved*, and symbolically it is in the unconscious of all the roles of the novel. The viciousness of the baby’s unsatisfied needs, colours, the mother-daughter relationship in *Beloved*. A baby’s unmet needs not only refer to physical needs but also psychic and emotional ones. In *Beloved*, the worst atrocity of slavery and the grimmest dilemma of the novel present not only physical death but also the psychic death. The children have been denied to their basic need and their birthright, which is the lap of the mother that is essential for the psychic growth of the child. This unfulfilled desire leaves such holes in the sub-conscious as are not filled throughout life. Sethe, unable to have the love and care of her mother develops into an overprotective mother whose selfish love takes away the life of her daughter. The predicament, of the novel, is Seth’s murder of her baby daughter, *Beloved*. Seth, having passed the growth of slavery and then able to run away from the cruel master, is on the threshold of being captured again. Her experience of slavery is so worse that she prefers to kill her daughter instead of leaving her to the cruel institution of slavery. So she decides physical death for her daughter instead of psychic death: “if I hadn’t killed her she would have died, and that is something I could not bear to happen to her” (Morrison 1988).

Thus concluding the discussion, it could be said that gender plays a significant role in the construction of self. Due to gender politics, women are doubly oppressed and to combat this oppression first, they have to locate the cause of this oppression and then employ a strategy to deal with it. They have to suffer double persecution, one of patriarchal society and constraints of tradition and the other of the cruel institution of slavery that strips them of every right of motherhood as well as womanhood. Women do exist, and they have played their role in sharing the responsibilities of family and society where men have often shrunk their responsibilities. Especially under the institution of slavery, women have struggled hard to realise their slaves entirely where either their roles as mother or some internal agency catalyse their journey towards the construction of self. Black women, to come to terms with themselves, are fighting for their rights as human beings and as cherished members of the Black society.

Beloved also presents an authoritative account of the foundation of black America in the light of feminism. The ficti, on to some extent recounts the formation of a new people and culture, displaced and forced to forge a unique identity in the face of dehumanization and brutality. It reflects on the subtle balance between individual and community, between self and other. To conclude, feminism is a tool to develop women community, but nowadays, women are thought that feminism is only about male domination. Feminism speaks about women needs, rights, and how they are suppressed in society. The suppression of women is not exclusively male domination but also marginalized culture and religion.

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Bama's Karukku Portrayed an Achievement to be an Identity of Vitality, Virtuous Venture of Voice and a Cheerful Cleverness of Confidence

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Abstract

Karukku is both fiction and autobiography in a duel of ways. In Bama's life Karukku is to find out her own identity. In her life she had lost everything. She felt, she was a stranger to society. In her village she was a stranger to society. In her village she was spent more happy life. Karukku explains recollection of her past life in the village. Karukku explains to the crisis of the Dalit, of the untouchable, how class treat in the rural setting serves to calm voice.

Bama shows in this novel about how the difficult of the Dalit is one of the bad outrages. Dalits have been told again and again of their loss of dignity, they have come to believe they are disrespect they have reached a stage where they themselves, willingly, hold on to themselves apart. The result of all this is that there is no way for Dalits to realize freedom or retrieval. Had Bama naturally written a work that only useful to herself in the structure of her own story, she might not have been able to expanse as numerous people? Bama desires to deliver voice to as class structure in a nation that has openly said that there is no class structure. In this novel shows Bama's personal critical point and separated in her life which moves to make intention of her life which moves to make intention of her life as woman, Christian, Dalit.

Keywords: Untouchable, Outrage, Dignity, Dalit.

Meaning of Karukku is Palmyra leaves which with their jagged sharpness on both sides, are like double-barreled weapon. By a delicious pun, the Tamil word Karukku, encase the word seed, also means span-new. In her prelude, Bama to make attention to the emblem and refers to the words in Hebrews (New Testament). In Karukku, Bama concentrates the unsecured condition of Dalit people how they are loss of destiny due to their poor economic background. The abide country less farming laborers who are economically helpless.

She gives importance to other main issue such as unreliability, intolerance in the modern church, Christianity. She harmfully to notice that their wealthy civilization is despoiled and they are left

with no civilization. She shows in this novel about the Dalit Christians have been oppression. So the Dalit people have oppressed in every caste such as Hindu, Christian, and Muslim. They live separately because normal people not treat Dalit people as their equals.

Bama concentrates the inequalities that history and heritage frequent upon Dalit women. On the one hand there is the black perspective of liberation and, on the other clear perspective of fate. They, however, purpose for cultural sociable, profitable and political reform and they do not look back. They continue to be oppressive people, who are undeniable. The Dalit woman who wants to need job in an urban is making a symbolic message. She gets more suffering for job. She is travel more for job that gets shameless in their society. They did not give equal rights to them. They do only small jobs such as sweeps, making clean into drains and the toilets. From her birth to death, she has to follow all the rules of the society and also the men folk at home. In many Dalit families have no freedom for anything. Similarly like caged birds. Without feathers birds cannot fly. Likewise Dalit families have not got their rights.

Below these bad conditions, the Dalit woman would discover a social equality as well as economic free equality. They were faced three types of bad conditions: Dalit people have affected with caste and other people treated them to untouchability and inequality. These things affected both male and female oppressed by the form of the Hindu religious system. Get more sufferings from their society. They only get pain, sad, domination and inequality.

Bama gives more importance for education. Education gives us knowledge and it helps to people how to behavior in outside. She says Education is self-serving Government. Education helps to Dalit people for decrease poverty. Education gives values of Dalit people especially for their rights. Through the education they break all the rules and conditions in their society. Without education Dalits gets only upper caste domination and untouchability. Education improves their social status, economic and political power. No one understands their values. But Bama shows through this novel everyone needs self-discipline, self-esteem, self-reliance, self-concept and self-perception especially for Dalits.

No one understands value of human life, especially Dalits life. Upper caste people showered no sympathy on Dalits when they bad condition. Dalit people not only suffered caste problem. They suffered more in different ways especially black women, injustice and that is not free from racism. Dalit have more miseries in their life. Bama focused all the things and explains through this novel. Bama's life arranges in different order, as with most autobiographies.

It shows different themes, especially work, games, recreation and etc. Bama gives in this novel about more aspects of Christianity, equality, justice and all kind of people need love. She explains her own life and experience share with reader. It is actively engaging in alienated the sufferings of bad conditions. Finally, Bama makes the only chance possible for developing awareness for Dalit people. Her own life and experience is a major part of Dalits. Bama's life is a model of other people.

She leaves her religious order and moved to her native place, she feels her life is insecure, but she does not feel complicated. She mainly focused in this novel of identity. She suffered identity, but she change which means at the end that get identity in their society. She uses a Dalit style of writing, especially she follow separate rules of grammar and spelling. But the reader can understand easily of her writing. She shares everything directly.

Reader read this novel and take resolution of how to behaviour and how to treat others equally. Karukku explains simply of life and the values of life. Every people need identity in this society.

But some people not realize that. Karukku tells these are all the things to the people. Bama's Karukku is good example of others. This work speaks wants to live hopefully and shows what the matter of life is. She shows in this novel reality of life.

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The Representation of Existentialism in the Select Novel of Saul Bellow

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Abstract

Existentialism is one of the most important themes of Saul Bellow's novels. The Adventures of Augie March is not only regarding the quest for survival but the survival of meaningful life. The whole novel deals with the life of the protagonist, Augie March. The novel is portrayed from the first person's point of view. The novel expresses the importance of existence in spite of any struggle and suffering. The novel seems to be different from those of others, but it clearly depicts the vision of the author, Saul Bellow.

Keywords: Adventures, Vision, Society, Existence, Struggle.

The Adventures of Augie March is an apt vehicle of Bellowian vision and establishes it in clear terms. Augie March, the protagonist, tells the story from his boyhood in Chicago to his wanderings in Michigan, Mexico and the African sea. In first person narrative, he keeps on telling the story of his attainment of maturity and his experiences as an import businessman in Paris. It is a picaresque novel and reflects high intellectual ideas. In this fiction, Bellow scrutinizes the working of human mind and tries to answer where the problem lies. His scrutiny establishes him as a radical thinker, who has affinity with existentialism and in some distance concerns with Buddhism.

This novel is a little different from Bellow's other novels; but it aptly demonstrates his vision. Bellow envisages human freedom from every kind of false pretensions, whether it is morality or ideality. It establishes Bellow as a writer who holds a mirror to the human beings, advocating the acceptance of their true self. In the veil of fiction, his only endeavour is to write what the truth is. Bellow's faculty to observe human nature disinterestedly makes him a free thinker. He is far from being a serious moralist. As a meticulous craftsman, he has interwoven his deep thoughts into the structure of

Augie's life. On the surface, it is in conformity with the Dickensian story of an illegitimate child; though it is a true manifesto of human predicament at a deeper level.

Bellow has stuffed the novel with several philosophical concerns. Like his other novels, in *The Adventures of Augie March*, Bellow has reflected existentialist theme. Bellow creates an aura of speculation around Augie, who is truly engaged in a struggle to choose among fantastically complicated metaphysical alternatives. The fiction also exemplifies naturalistic mode of writing. Naturalistic prose renders a human being as a product of his heredity and environment. In a naturalistic fiction, the actions of a person are determined by the compulsive instincts that he inherits together with the social and the economic forces of the family and the society, in which he is born. In this novel, Bellow shows a deep sense of environmental intrusion and of life as competitive struggle chaotically releasing and suppressing energy. Bellow portrays an urban mechanical world in which the individuality is influenced by dominant processes and the laws of social places. The character of Augie is also influenced by his unhealthy family atmosphere. His lack of moral earnestness is a counter reaction to his illegitimate birth, docile mother and despotic grandma Lausch. On a wider level the materialism induces to behave immorally instead of being sincere. Bellow has followed the tradition of picaresque novel. He has used a great number of characters and detailed action that covers the period of several years.

Bellow's other protagonists struggle in acceptance of their true self but the case is different with Augie. He has no aversion to evil or immoral behaviour as long as it is true to his instincts. In view of modern devaluation of human spirit, Augie's plea to have free existence reminds one of the Satan, the protagonist of *Paradise Lost*, book first and second. Moreover, it proves the superiority of truth over morality. Though at the same time, one cannot blame that Bellow is an immoral writer, advocating inhuman conduct. On the other hand, it is also true that Bellow has never given any sermon through his novels. It is never his motto to instruct his readers as to become good but true to oneself. And the truth of human condition is that human beings are not perfect. If one accepts one's true self, it is the most moral work that one may perform. In fact, the morality which insists one to act against one's real self can be easily discarded. Throughout his life, Bellow tried to adhere to his truth. Bellow's crusade against established morality again confirms him as an existentialist.

Morality is temporal and related to particular society. The application of moral laws differs from situation to situation. For example, to tell a lie is morally unacceptable, but if it saves someone's life, it can be accepted easily. Thus, morality is context-related and flexible. In the novel, *The Adventures of Augie March*, Augie never endeavours to be morally good. Augie, in truest sense, is a Bellowian hero, who experiments in the realm of morality. He acts according to his instincts. Through Augie's conduct Bellow tries to deconstruct the established hierarchy, which posits good at a higher level than the bad. Bellow tries to destroy all those hierarchies in the society which restrict individuals to progress further. All his heroes are victims of this internal conflict with no exception of Augie. Augie steals money, plunders store, and defies authorities without any remarkable feeling of remorse afterwards. His adventures in the realm of evil are counterbalanced by his sympathy towards George, optimistic quest for a better fate, enthusiasm for life and his craving for being loved. In this way, the character of Augie is a superb example of masterly craftsmanship of Bellow.

Bellow has made Augie a real genius. Augie shows one the art of living as if he knows what troubles most to a human mind. He is a rebel, a rough, a criminal yet a hero because he has the quality of contentment, which is rare even to a so-called good person. Augie is not polluted by ideologies of society. He does not act to be good but to be true. Augie does not believe in the wisdom of elders because he can easily perceive loopholes in those theories. Therefore, he follows his own discretion.

To be loved and to be admired by others are two basic cravings of human beings. Augie sacrifices these two for his third craving of being free. It is the character of Augie which establishes Bellow as an existentialist in the true sense. Augie is conscious of his status as a free man. That is why he is never a victim of bad faith and remains calm in every situation. Augie is not a winner in any field of life, yet he does not have a burdened conscience. He has nothing to prove. He knows his reality and is content to get rewards accordingly. The story develops Bellow's own views regarding true self and its acceptance. Bellow was himself a rebel whenever it was a question to follow the accepted morality. The conventional morality could never prune Bellow's instinctual drives. Bellow himself could never follow the patterns of behaviour; he should have been followed according to the prescribed codes of conduct.

Bellow is a supporter of truth of human nature. In the true sense, Augie's thoughts present Bellow's own psyche. Augie always supports his instincts and never transfers his guilt to any other person. This is the key to Augie's contentment and Bellow's optimism. Like his creator, Augie is detached; he does not want something particular from his life. If he wants true love, he does not personalize this love within a single person. Rather, he is able to move on knowing the truth that he can get it somewhere else too. In this way he does not attach with any person or object. He is ready to leave and move forward in his quest for another suitable destination, though he never reaches at the same. Even after a chain of disappointment he never loses his hope.

Bellow's novels are a salute to human wish to survive. It is not easy to suffer and similarly one can't avoid suffering. Suffering is universal and perennial. On this earth there are countless human beings who struggle daily. Their minds are thwarted by several kinds of problems—social, familial, individual, psychological etc. Still everybody does not commit suicide. Human beings fight for their existence. Though one's life is unquestionably stuffed with inhuman sufferings, one never loses one's hope to survive. Bellow has always written in appreciation of this hope. This admiration of Bellow is clear when we read the last page of *The Adventures of Augie March*, in which Augie appreciates Jacqueline's wish to lead a hopeful life even after getting assaulted by several intolerable misfortunes.

Bellow's *Augie March* is also peculiar because unlike his other protagonists, Augie does not undergo a change of heart in the end. Augie is not shown to be a prisoner of his own device. He constantly unfolds his future and accepts it as being of his own. Again, Bellow's purpose is fulfilled by Augie's light-hearted acceptance of his struggles and failures. Augie is not tired of his life, instead of that, Jacqueline's hopeful attitude recharges Augie further to live his life with a hope and not as a burden. To say Bellow's vision of human life as sub-angelic may be a little misleading, but Bellow absolutely respects human life for its potential to survive.

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A Cosmodern Reading of Language in David Mitchell's Novel Cloud Atlas

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Abstract

A cosmodern reading of David Mitchell's Cloud Atlas creates a positive vision of the longer term for readers through varied techniques of fragmentation together with fragmentation of voice, language, and time. By fragmentation, I actually have in mind the consistent interruption of the novel's voice, language, and time that needs a vigorous and aware audience. The reader's interaction with the text makes the novel re-constructive. In fact, the worldwide nature of Mitchell's novel, its hopeful ending, and its exploration of the results of globalisation will be thought of as a way of exploring the dynamic relationships between the characters, the reader, and Mitchell's auctorial voice. Instead of falling back on acquainted postmodern truisms like the despair of real communication or the impossibility of truth, Mitchell creates a hopeful vision of the longer term of the planet, one that champions the life, agency, and private narrative of the individual.

Keywords: David Mitchell, fragmentation of language, historical, intractability of power, Cloud Atlas, Cosmodernism.

Rather than putting forward a only optimistic reading of language in Cloud Atlas, this chapter can explore the positive potentialities created for language within the novel, however additionally acknowledge the negative outcomes of fragmented language that are apparent within the novel. Fragmented language is a smaller amount consistent than voice or time within the novel, happening in some narratives at the extent of speech whereas in others it operates as a mental awareness solely. In an exceedingly novel that explores acquainted narratives of the thirst for power (colonialism, slavery, capitalism), Mitchell uses language that is the building block for alternate management, and one centered on community and personalised narratives. Mitchell explores the house between the desire for power and management through fragmentation of language – a mixture of the language of power and individual speech creates a private belief that reframes reality. What's a lot of, instead of that specialize in the impossibility of communication, Mitchell explores

language in an exceedingly means that enables for a philosophical theory of metanarratives, followed by a lot of optimistic reconstruction. Mitchell, in fact, sets up a multiplicity of potentialities for language in order that optimistic and demoralized views of language operate on a wage schedule instead of as absolutes. To boot, to differentiate between the ideas of language and voice, my analysis of language focuses on understanding, or lack thereof, whereas my analysis of voice within the 1st chapter centered on expression. whereas voice in *Cloud Atlas* is closely tied to narration, I read language and understanding as ideas that operate at the communal level of society, and community, like expression, exists unambiguously for every of the novel's main characters. As a result, *Cloud Atlas* outlines the chance for understanding of the self, or self-actualization, yet because the understanding of the self's place inside community and time.

Similarly to fragmentation of voice, fragmentation of language is nuanced, therefore it's no surprise that vital interpretations of the language in *Cloud Atlas* have varied wide, starting from an ending of history and a dying language to freed language, and numerous places in between. Language is, as Martin Heidegger posited, the mode by that authors, readers, and characters become attentive to their own reality, outline themselves and also the world around them, and verify their own agency and place inside the dominant narrative of history. Trendy British authors struggled with the thought that language couldn't properly categorize their own thoughts and concepts, so that they turned to fragmentations of kind so as to account for his or her postwar reality and envision a brand new world. However, this method was conjointly involved by heart. That is, the new world was unable to seem thanks to remembered trauma, and language didn't have the words or content, the expression, broken or unbroken, that might enable it to talk a brand new world into being. Mitchell's exploration of language in *Cloud Atlas* is actually attentive to this ineffability, however it's conjointly fragmented within the positive sense of that term, specifically the making of agency. We would say that the language of the novel is torn between cosmopolitan risk and predatory extinction. As a result of cosmopolitan interpretation of language is international in its impulses, it frees language from the requirement of showing in any correct kind. It encourages multilingualism (in the sense of each spoken and cultural languages) and sees language as one thing borrowed from society, one thing owed for the requirement of communication, instead of owned, and happiness to the self. However, the novel's capitalist concepts lead the reader towards a spotlight on the novel's narratives of predation, and this has junction rectified students to focus nearly solely on the language of 2 stories: "An prayer of Sonmi-451" and "Sloosha's Crossin' an' Ev'rythinonce." however these stories, necessary as they are, supply an incomplete read of the means Mitchell uses language. This can be a result of, instead of strictly a battle for community and shared language (in a cosmopolitan sense), the conflict of language in *Cloud Atlas* is primarily for understanding. Mitchell leaves the reader to explore linguistic themes that area unit personal and international. The linear narrative of language within the novel charts its destruction and reconstruction, following the theme of predation. Conversely, fragmented language within the novel queries whether or not the characters will perceive themselves, their places in their communities, and their places in time, all of that Mitchell sees as necessary so as to survive and build a permanent impact upon their own world. Moraru writes that language provides "a sense of happiness," which, in *Cloud Atlas*, unites characters that might possibly well be separated from each other, connecting them by crossing time and language barriers (78). In Cosmopolitanism, he posits,

The hope for self-expression and communication...does not lie in a one-language but in our ability to speak each other's language and give it the intonations and connotations likely to reinscribe it into the multivocality it comes from...the self articulates itself in the strongest sense of the word, that is, it enunciates itself as it ascertains its link, its articulation unto another. (81)

This interpretation of self-understanding is essentially tied to the self's need to unite language to the

communal voices it's originated from whereas at the same time attending to outline what's distinctive and totally different in its own expression. This understanding comes from recognizing that language is shared, instead of separately in hand. Mitchell's characters expertise this affiliation overtly within the text by the expertise of their shared soul. They sense an affiliation to one thing outside of themselves, one thing that they bear in mind or collaborating in. As an example, once Luisa hears Robert's *Cloud Atlas Sextet* for the primary time, she tells the clerk, "I have to be compelled to own this music too. I actually have to... But I do know it. I'm telling you I do know it" (408-9). Luisa is a component of a shared community through time, and she or he acknowledges her own, or a component of her own, language once she hears Robert's music. In a very connected moment with a distinct outcome, Robert's expertise of shared language causes him to ponder suicide. He senses the joined soul and believes that point follows Nietzsche's theory of eternal repetition which he is born and live once more, that each one history and time can still repeat themselves, unchanging. He believes, supported his musical interpretation of the shared soul that it's his time to die, so his music can stay because the embodiment of his person. As a musician, he experiences a duality of language - music and language. He feels these come back to him across time and area, and their interconnected relationship leads him to grasp his own role within the communal language, that is to unite them in his *Cloud Atlas Sextet*. (This is why his life ceases to possess purpose when he has finished his composition.) As an example, he writes of his brother's letters from the nice War as being "hauntingly aural" and observes, "One will shut one's eyes however not one's ears... European music is stormily savage, broken by long silences" (442). He describes music in terms of the sound of warfare, and his descriptions double for the content of his brother's letters and knowledge. He conjointly discusses the means that later understanding, formed by speech communication, adds in additional violent, larger sounds.

In the latter 1/2 his narration, Henry Martyn Robert items along the six separate voices of the novel in terms of his sextet. He writes that he's "reworking my year's fragments into a 'sextet for overlapping soloists': piano, clarinet, 'cello, flute, oboe, and violin, every in its own language of key, scale, and color. Within the 1st set, every solo is interrupted by its successor: within the second, every interruption is sustained in order" (445). This is often an apt description of how language functions in *Cloud Atlas*: though fragmented across time, it's fashioned by the expertise of the voices coming back along. The form they create and notes they play overlap to become a shared narrative. Their overall expression would be hampered were they every speaking alone. The anxiety of reception that follows Robert's description of his work mirrors what may well be taken as Mitchell's own anxiety during a Meta fictive moment.

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Cultural Effects of Individual Versus Society in Aravid Adiga's Select Novels

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Abstract

This paper aims to analyze the cultural effects of individual versus society in Aravid Adiga's select novels. The Last Man in Tower and The White Tiger. These novels examine Indian's sacrifices for the next generation, and sometimes they behave crude and cruel manner towards the people they love. In these novels, through the major characters, the culture differs according to their class. So this paper going to argues how the culture differs between individual and society through Aravid Adiga's novels.

Introduction

Aravid Adiga was born on 23rd October 1974. His first book, *The White Tiger* won the Booker Prize in the year 2008, the year of its publication. As far as his professional experience is concerned, he was the former correspondent of the Times magazine. His articles developed in various financial dailies like *The Sunday Times*, *The Financial Times*, and *The Independent*. This shows that he had enough background in the domain of writing. As his family went to Australia, he had some education there. Following on, he went to New York. His journey worldwide and his interaction with many people enriched his writing skills. It also informed Adiga with the reading habits of the people.

Arvind Adiga won the Booker Prize for the novel *The White Tiger* on 14th October 2008 which was published by HarperCollins. *The White Tiger* described the two parts of India, one was dark, and another was light. The reader has sympathy for Balram, who is not a villain in the real sense. *Last Man in Tower* is a novel by Indian writer Aravid Adiga. It was the second novel by Adiga Published by HarperCollins in India in 2011. It tells the story of a struggle of a discharged school teacher named Yogesh A. Murthy, who is affectionately known as Masterji.

Cultural Effects in Individual Versus Society

Indians sacrifice for the next generation, and sometimes they behave in a crude and cruel manner towards the people they love. Characters tend to make decisions based on their life's conditions as time goes by. As Indians are God-fearing people, image-breaking and iconoclasm are not there in classic Indian literature. For example, nobody is discussing extra-marital relationships proudly. Ashok is the landlord's son. He is a product of the western culture in spite of his roots in Indian culture. He finds it hard to bridge the gap between the two cultures. He has western values implanted in him and struggles to obtain feet in the political set up in India. Ashok considers that he is a misfit in Indian circumstances.

Ashok had been married to ultra-modern Pinky Madam. She was disappointed with her husband's interest in political and commercial activities in India. She was interested in western countries and the modern culture there. Husband and wife struggled incessantly. Pinky Madam was angry with him for his false intentions of visiting back in India. She had a lot of western values. When she moves the country, she helps Balram by giving over some money to him. She was not carrying her husband during crises. Ashok's wife means people who have left their origin in traditional society and are being in a modern one. She determined to carve out a niche for herself by adapting herself to the new mindset.

Balram selected advantage of the bickering within Pinky Madam and Ashok. He set his eyes not only on Ashok's money without more on Pinky's person. Lascivious information that Balram makes of Pinky's breasts and bums reflects on his sexual desire for Pinky. Balram brings Ashok everywhere. Since he was a car driver, Balram recognized the many places and people Ashok visited. He could eavesdrop the business discussion in the car. He could espionage Ashok's illegal actions. He studied Ashok carefully. We come across a pathetic character, Mohammad. Mohammad is a poor, hard-working Muslim who needs a job desperately. The landlord he proposed was known for his antipathy for Muslim. The poor boy took a new name, Ram Persad to hide his Muslim identity.

In the old days, there were thousand castes and destinies in India. These days, there are just two castes: Men with Big small Bellies and Men with Big Bellies. And only two destinies: eat or get eaten up (The White Tiger 179).

Munro begins his life as a starving, half-naked child of a remote village in a hilly area and dies in a related state. Balaram, on the other hand, develops from a cringing employee to a multimillionaire employer. This approach to characterization says a lot about the new Indian novel. Characters in the past books did not change so dramatically. Fate ruled their destiny. Balaram changed his future.

Aravind Adiga's Last Man in Tower". The impulse to become rich performs people act less compassionate and humane in the age of globalization. The Man Booker Prize-winning writer Aravind Adiga's debut novel The White Tiger throws light on the dark India which resides untouched by the rapid economic transformations of the 21st century. His second novel Last Man in Tower discovers the crimes connected with real estate, which is one of the booming industries in the age of globalization. It explores how greed to become rich makes people more self-centered and provokes them to do dirty, unimaginable things to other fellow-beings.

In recent decades, the booming real estate industry, which is one of the extension engines of the national economy becomes out to be the richest and highest agency in reordering social life of the middle class. It would be essential to know the concept of the middle class in the Indian context as the novel centers around the Indian middle class. Pavan K. Varma defines the middle class in the Indian context as,

Anybody who has a home to live in and can provide three meals a day, and has way to primary public transport, schooling, and health care, with some disposable income to buy such basics as

watch or a fan or cycle, has already climbed on to the middle-class bandwagon (The Last Man in Tower 138).

The development of the new middle class involves two parallel processes such as “the politics of exclusion” and “the politics of aspiration.” In countries like India, Nepal, and China, the new middle classes are seen as inspirational as they believe “the privileged lifestyles” and “distinctive images” portrayed by the advertising industry and mass media are attainable. As a result, the aspiring middle classes are victimized by exploitative property developers who make a profit out of such famous dreaming.

Conclusion

In *The White Tiger* and *The Last Man in Tower* expresses the culture differs between individual and society through the major characters of these novels. In *The White Tiger* Ashok is the landlord’s son. He is a outcome of the western culture in spite of his roots in Indian culture. He finds the bridge gap between the two cultures. Because Ashok has been married with ultra-modern pinky, madam. She was disappointed with her husband’s interest in political and commercial activities in India. In *The Last Man in Tower* explores how the greed to become rich makes people more self-centered and provokes them to do dirty. As a result, the desire for wealth drives the middle class and underprivileged to do criminal activities. Finally, this paper finds the culture differs between individual and society. Because society readily accepts the new religion. But an individual unable to adopt the new lifestyle but slowly they try to take a new culture. These things are clearly explained in Aravind Adiga’s novels.

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Perception of New Indian Women in the Novels of Nayantara Sahgal

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Abstract

Nayantara Sahgal was born on May 10, 1927, to Ranjit Sitaram Pandit and Vijayalakshmi Pandit as the second of their three daughters. She has issued eight novels, two autobiographies and a political reading of Indira Gandhi's years in authority along with a significant number of journalistic writings mostly on contemporary political events and a lot of women, giving a clarion call to women to appear as a 'new women' journeying towards freedom. This article focuses on the idea of New Indian Women in her novels. The notion of 'New Women' with a "new morality" based on reason and justice is of current origin, struggling to cultivate into any reasonable form. This article gives a complete appraisal of the highlights of the problems, especially of women.

Keywords: chastity, morality, freedom, marriage, chauvinism.

Nayantara Sahgal is one of the eminent Indo English writers who inscribe in the tributary & national consciousness. She is a prolific writer and her literary norm of nine novels, two autobiographies and some non-fictional works. Nayantara Sahgal has introduced a large number of autobiographical elements in her books. For a query, she asserts that 'all art is autobiographical' (Women's Space the Mosaic World of Margaret Drabble and Nayantara Sahgal, 27). Her work ranges from honest and emotional autobiography to fictionalized autobiography.

Nayantara believes that it is not a severe, moral offense in a woman to break away from the 'sacred' marriage bond if she finds the shackles too harsh to the enlargement of her inner self. She finds that a women's responsibility to be genuine to her inner self is far superior and critical than to be for family and society. Nayantara portrays the unchallengeable right of freedom in women in many of the characters in her novels, such as Simrit, Saroj, and Rashmi. This piece of writing focuses on the perception of New Indian Woman in India through the ages so that it might throw brightness on the approach and action of those problems by Nayantara Sahgal.

Through centuries the perception of perfect womanhood has been based on mythological personages like Sita, Nalayani. A woman was supposed to be under the concern of a male throughout her life. One part made a great crash is that which disallows any autonomy for women, is as follows:

Pitaarakshatikaumaree, bhartharakshatiyauvane

Putroorakshativardhakyee, nastri

Swathantharyamarhati (ix,3) (Women and her family, 2)

(‘The father protects the woman during childhood, the husband during her youth and the son during her old age. A woman does not deserve freedom’).

A woman is therefore inculcated with the ideals of martyrdom, of satisfaction intolerance, of the need to believe a lower status through the mythological models of Sita, Savithri, Gandhari, etc.

The dialogue between Rose and Ram in the novel ‘The Rich Like Us’ is introduced to carry to light the circumstance of women usually prevailing in Society. Another vice perpetrated in society is the male privilege over female issues. Women are considered as commodities, more significant the convenience. Men do not worry about the poignant constraints, which they require upon women. Women have to put up with such inconveniences on financial considerations. When Ram represents Draupdi was gambled away by her five husbands, Rose is accurately shocked.

Sahgal approaches the trouble of women with liability, ripeness, and understanding. She is conscious of the fact that women’s problems are not confined to women only. Society consists of men and women, and the pleasure of one or the other depends upon a co-operative endeavor. Women cannot be aggressive towards men as they cannot be so without danger. The accountability of bringing about a joyful society rests uniformly on men and women in society. Sahgal understands the requirements for strength of co-operation on the piece of men. It is the responsibility of the educated, dependable men in society to assist in the liberation of women. Sahgal brings out this point obviously when she makes her heroines in the novels needy on the trustworthy men in society. Simrit is maintained and guided by Raj in every way. It is Raj who tries to fracture the strength of submissiveness in Simrit and construct her to obtain some positive action. Under his power, inconsistently she says that she feels entirely free.

It is Dubey who directs and supports Saroj to create her imagine liberally, to break away from the shackles, particularly if they establish worthless or indefensible. Rashmi is directed by Kalidas. It seems that Sahgal makes her heroines intentionally submissive or reliant so that responsible men should come advance to assist them discover their way in the mire. It is the society’s dependability, Sahgal believes, to get steps to progress the excellence of existence for women, to create them full-fledged human beings, to understand their self-governing ‘personhood.’

Society consists of men and women. She cautions woman not to squander away their rigid on freedom in fighting for impartiality in costume or performance. They should attain something substantial to show their advantage. A self-fulfilled woman will be a benefit to the family. She also finds responsibility with the society, which observes a dual standard with perceive to virtue or morality. While culture imposes sturdy sanctions against even slight indiscretions on the element of women, it shows significant compassion towards such aberrations in men. She also castigated the undue importance given to moderation. The perception of morality, according to Sahgal, is much more related to intelligence than to corpse. Most of the times the penalty falls heavy on the aggrieved party that is related to woman. For her, Sex is not an operator of the body or for the movement, but it permeates mind and power and all activities of husband and wife. It is a perform of the finale of love, understanding of kindness. But it does not mean she is for promiscuity. She condemns the perkiness and excesses in sex in women as exemplified in her novels.

This critique was undertaken a critical study of the novels of Nayantara Sahgal in an endeavor to appear at some suitable conclusions regarding her attitude towards women's problems and how she envisages "the perception of new women in India."

In Sahgal's *Storm in Chandigarh* Inder, the husband, who himself is hankering following another woman Mara, frequently rebukes and harasses his wife Saroj because of her past sexual pleasure with her college mate once; Ram in *Rich Like Us* has previously two wives at home, but he continues to expand adoring love activities with Marcela. Sahgal feels, "if chastity is so important and so well worth preserving. It would be easier to safeguard it by keeping men seclusion, not women." (*Chandigarh* 191)

Marriage is sincere as well as the difficulty of all human relations. Religion considers marriage as a sacred union of two souls. But the similar religion imposes stiff code of behavior for women. Wounded butterflies who stretched to live to emerge out of chrysalis and find an opening in doing social service as in the case of Maya in *A Time to be Morning*; Rashmi terminations her marriage and stands unaccompanied in *This Time of Morning*; Simrit, a freelancer, marries Raj starts a fresh life in the *Day in shadow*: Saroj an innocent and caring mother bravely comes and discover consolation in Vishal in *Storm in Chandigarh*; and Devi, a woman cabinet minister, survives without help in politics in *A Situation in New Delhi*.

There are female characters that, in the name of freedom, irritated the limits of family and marriage. In Sahgal's *A Time to be Happy*, Lalitha Chatterjee, a very significant person, drinks and has an affair with an additional man: Uma Mitra, the young wife of Arjun Mitra, smokes, flirts, drinks, and ruins herself: and Leela, as student, conceives out of marriage commits suicide when she sees of it in *This Time of Morning*, Gauri, freely has sex with Vishal in the lack of her husband, Nikhil: Leela, the disloyal wife of Vishal, dies, when her pregnancy is medically finished: and Mara has a special affair with Inder outwardly the facts of *Jit in Storm in Chandigarh*. This breach of ethics in their existence does not permit them to become new women. Sahgal looks to have a clear message to convey when women resort to dissolution their life becomes either worthless or end up in an abnormal death. Sahgal's marital ethics, as revealed in her works, is based on sincerity, mutual faith, considerations, understanding, and liberty; she attacks egotism, pretense, which result consequently in marital breakdown.

Instinctively, her major women characters stay agreeable, student, quiet and suffering, but when faced with discrimination Maya, Saroj, Rashmi or Simrit, they explain the sight of awaking, discard the stereotype and speak out the fact. Earlier they have been only humans' obedient and conforming persons, but later on, they are sovereign and whole beings.

Men like Inder in *Storm in Chandigarh*, Som in *The Day in Shadow* are the personification of Chauvinism. They have the code of behavior as far as they are worried and an additional where women are concerned. As a consequence, Saroj and Simrit suffer embarrassment and pain. But they administer to live on once they come out of their marriages, from 'the subdued sex, creatures not yet emerged from the chrysalis.' (*Chandigarh* 189) they were 'filled with the sheer rightness of beings alive and healthy.' (*Shadow* 236)

The regular communication Sahgal gives is men and women are equals, and nonviolent survival depends on common respect and understanding, women should have the ethical bravery to maintain the rights and 'men..were born to lead and sometimes educate to triumph'. (*Shadow* 236).

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Ecological Discourses in Indian English Fiction

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Abstract

This research paper aims to learn the ecocritical aspects in the fiction of Indian authors like Bhabani Bhattacharya, Kamala Markandaya, Amitav Ghosh, Raja Rao, R.K.Narayan, Ruskin Bond, and Anita Desai. Since ages literature is well known for sparkly society, current issues and human activities. There is a profusion of research which uses nature and scenery as its background. Man and nature interrelate on different levels, helpful or equally destructive. At the same time, the permanent intrusion of man in natural activities has posed a hazard both to himself and to the atmosphere. If this is not attended to, it will guide to irreversible damage.

Keywords: Ecocriticism, contemporary issues, society, Indian fiction.

Literature and environment are always entangled in a strong association, as is evident in the works of writers throughout the ages. The realization of writers has brought the two disciplines, ecology and literature, collectively again and again. Their aim has been respecting nature as a guide, protector, and mother (Wordsworth), as a supernatural force (Coleridge), or in more modern texts to accumulate the earth's environment which is being damaged due to man's mishandling.

Work has been completed on ecocriticism or 'green studies' in the USA and UK. For ecocritics, the nineteenth-century developments in literature are essential. American and British Romantic writers took a fastidious concentration in nature as a theme. Henry David Thoreau's *Walden* (1854) and Ralph Waldo Emerson's *Nature* (1836) are the defining works in the meadow of ecocriticism. Don DeLillo, a modern American author, has in his *Underworld* (1988) highlighted the subject of managing to dump of waste which is leading to the descent of the environment. If we glance into the history of Indian literature, we discover many well-known writers contributing to this track.

The word 'ecocriticism' was first used by William Rueckert in his essay "Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocriticism" in

1978. He defines ecocriticism as “the application of ecology and ecological concepts to the study of literature because ecology (as a science, as a discipline, as the basis for human vision) has the greatest relevance to the present and future of the world” (1996:107). Peter Barry added a chapter titled “Ecocriticism” to the second edition of his *Beginning Theory: An Introduction to Literary and Cultural Theory* (1995). Thomas K. Dean considers Eco-criticism as “a study of culture and cultural products (artworks, writings, scientific theories, etc.)... in some way is connected with the human relationship to the natural world.” He extends his explanation of ecocriticism as “a response to needs, problems, or crisis, depending on one’s perception of urgency” (Dean 1994 p.1). Ecocriticism is a field that bridges the gap between literature and science.

This research is an effort to investigate the symbol of nature, as landscape as well as metaphor. It will effort to seem into the different ways in which life has combined in and has been anticipated by diverse writers in India. At the start of the 21st century, nature forces us to carry it to the center period. We must try to tackle the subject of life in this extraordinarily scientific and profitable world, through an investigation and scrutiny of modern Indian literature.

We discover impressions of nature study in the fiction of some post-World War-II, Bengali writers such as Manik Bandopadhyay, Advaita Mallabarman and Samaresh Basu in *A Boatman of Padma* (1936), *A River Called Titash* (1950) and *Ganga* (1957), respectively. All these novels are about rivers which equally maintain life and at times become destroyers of fishermen and boatmen. These tradesmen, through their effort and fight for livelihoods, redesign the daydream environment into a lively arena of social life. All the three novels portray the day to day resist for endurance and how this process of interdependence and collaboration between the fishermen, boatmen, small farmers, and their river centric environment influence each other’s survival. However, as Raymond Williams aptly points out, “when nature is separated out from the activities of men, it even ceases to be nature in any full and effective sense” (16).

Bhabani Bhattacharya’s *So Many Hungers* (1947), is a genuinely moving work of art. We discover in it an ingredient of eager inspection of men and life. It is about ache, fright, sadness, starvation, pain, and sacrifice, mainly due to man-made scarcity leading to the death of millions. He talks about the most sickening actual incident in the history of India, i.e., the Bengal famine of 1943. It is a heart-rending demonstration of the starvation for food, malnourishment, and ultimate death, the other face of nature. It is a lacerating description of the naked dreadfulness through cumulative details and absorbing story. It is about the difficulty of the two families living in the village of Baruni and Calcutta due to the starvation. The characters trust that they have been punished for their sins dedicated in the past. He deals with a parallel theme in *He Who Rides a Tiger*.

We also discover impressions of ecocriticism in Kamala Markandaya’s *Nectar in the Sieve*. But here the perception is contradictory, being the other face of nature. This novel deals with ‘The Flood,’ i.e., life trying to manage humans, it is in the ruined state. This leads to the pitiable and wretched conditions of the victims of the flood. When it became a danger to human lives, it is then that it became a substance of worldwide concern.

The Hungry Tide is a review on an endangered ecosystem- the Sundarbans in the Bay of Bengal. It is written by a flexible modern writer, Amitav Ghosh. The Sundarbans in the Bay of Bengal are some islands which people split with animals. The situation of their living is much lower for animals. The dilemma the inhabitants undergo due to unwanted, unexpected tidal surges and tiger attacks demonstrate a severe ecological disaster on earth. The reason is to generate alertness to assist organize action plans for the safety of the settlers.

Ghosh states that the environmental decline in the Sundarbans in his lifetime has been very noticeable and very shocking (Ferdous & Rutsch 51). Birdlife, crabs and fish, and individual trees and plants have incredibly uncommon, and their absence is felt. The loss of marine mammal

populations is part of this “catastrophe” (51). He feels there is “incredible urgency” to these ecological issues, and this comes out very evidently in the novel, contributing considerably to its ecological tone (51). One of his characters, Nirmal, watching his favorite landscape, is in no doubt that it is in dreadful decline:

Age teaches you to recognize the signs of death....

Now it was as if I could see those signs everywhere,
not just in myself, but in this place that I had lived in for
almost thirty years. The birds were vanishing,
the fish were dwindling, and from day to day,
the land was being reclaimed by the sea. (215)

Amitav Ghosh discusses the unstable life of people living in the Sundarbans. Christopher Rollason defines the novel as:

[an] exploration of the huge field of human communication,

testing both its opportunities and its limits as the characters seek to cross multiple barriers – the barriers of language, social class, and religion, and those between human beings and nature, between traditional and cosmopolitan India, between urban and rural, between India and the wider world. (2)

Thus, Amitav Ghosh’s novel is an idyllic illustration of a modern author grappling with literature’s perspective to address ecological issues.

Similarly, Raja Rao, one of the essential writers, has used the environmental setting in *Kanthapura* depicting the connection between man and nature. He uses rivers and mountains to highlight the significance of nature in man’s life. The temple, The river, and ‘Malgudi’ have an essential place in R.K.Narayan’s fiction. Moreover, Malgudi has been a backdrop to about ten novels by Narayan, becoming the ‘Hero’ in the words of Prof. Iyengar (Saxena 26).

We also discover glimpses of nature in the novel of Ruskin Bond, who lived in the flourishing green scenic surroundings of Dehradun and Mussoorie. His short stories reproduce his passionate belief in the nurturing feature of the environment. In the accounts for children like, ‘No Room for Leopard’, ‘Copperfield in the Jungle’, ‘An Island of Trees’, ‘The Tree Lover’, ‘The Cherry Tree’, and ‘All Creatures Great and Small’, which genuinely pursue their titles, explores themes like deforestation and its after-effects, saying no hunting, and the correlation of man and nature. He is compassionate towards nature, be it living or non-living.

Another significant writer of this age, writing about nature is Anita Desai. We find a sturdy existence of animals, plants, birds, and outside images of landscape in her psychological novels. It is attractive to a reminder that in her *Cry, the Peacock*, we are taken into the intellect of the character through the exterior landscape. This novel is a narrative of a lady Maya, who is not joyful after her marriage. She distinguishes herself with a peacock, which fights by its male partner before mating. Sadly this novel ends with Maya stirring her husband off the roof, finishing in his death. In *Clear Light of Day*, Monisha, the female protagonist, feels herself to be encaged like a wretched bird. Lastly, to increase liberty, she has to assign suicide. Anita Desai has also considered the problem of heartlessness towards animals and has used the landscape, particularly the mountains of Kanchenjunga, to tell the changing conditions or the mood in *The Inheritance of Loss*. The gloomy atmosphere of a child is reflected through Kanchenjunga, which is believed to have rewarded for the cruelty of human beings by losing its attractiveness. Her novel is apt for ecocritical study.

Thus, writers like Bhabani Bhattacharya, Ruskin Bond, Kamala Markandya, Amitav Ghosh, Raja Rao, R.K.Narayan, and Anita Desai, through their literature, have drawn concentration towards the representation of natural beauty as well as nature’s catastrophic face in the form of natural calamities like flood, famines, etc. These writers are longing to speak for the natural world

in literature. Many of them tried to portray what man has to damage nature, but few come up with suggestions as to how we can defeat or overturn the harm that has been done. Are a man and the writer a mute spectator, or just a responsive observer, or can he suggest what to do now? In our race towards modernity, are we competent in saving our natural landscape, or is it doomed for destruction? Lastly, it is, to a considerable extent, to be decided by a man who faces of nature he wants to see. Wordsworth could never have seen this countenance of life which the Indian writer sketches in these texts.

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Gender Inequality in Arundathi Roy's The God of Small Things

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Abstract

Women are not born but they are made. Women are framed by our society, mainly by men who think they are more powerful than women in all aspects. In the orthodox and conservative Indian Society, women are always underestimated because of patriarchal assumption. The society says that women's greatness lies in sacrificing and serving for the goodness of the family. There is no value for her personal thoughts and emotions. It is always ignored and unseen. Through this paper, I would like to picturise the gender inequality shown in Arundathi Roy's The God of Small Things. How the society gives every opportunity to man and declines even a single opportunity for a women.

Keywords: Inequality, Orthodox, Underestimated, Patriarchal etc .

Suzanna Arundathi Roy was born on 24 November 1961 at Shillong in Assam. She is a great writer, essayist, social activist that is political activist who showed her interest and involvement in human rights and environmental causes. Her mother Mary Roy, a Malayali Syrian Christian women's right activist. She did her schooling at Corpus Christi, Kottayam followed by the Lawrence School, Lovedale, in Nilgiris. Then she got graduated from School of Planning and Architecture, Delhi where she met Gerard de Cunha, an architect. But later they got separated. After that Roy obtained a position in a National Institute of Urban Affairs. She then made her debut in an award winning film *Massey Sahib*, a film by Pradip Krishen who was an independent filmmaker. After that, they got married and collaborated on a television series that was based on independence movement and also they joined on two films namely *Annie* and *Electric Moon*. Later they got separated because of some misunderstandings.

She became more successful after the publication of her novel *The God of Small Things* 1997. She wrote screenplays for *In Which Anne Gives It Those Ones* (1989) she also appeared in *Electric Moon* (1992). Arundathi Roy won National Film Award for Best Screenplay for *In Which Annie Gives It Those Ones* in 1988. Roy's *The God of Small Things* is semi- auto biographical and captures a major part of her childhood in Aymanam. The book received many appreciations and awards. the Los Angeles

reviewed the novel as “a novel of poignancy and considerable sweep.” Roy was awarded the Sydney Peace Prize in May 2004 for her work which dealt with her advocacy for non- violence. In January 2006, she was awarded the Sahitya Akademi Award from India’s Academy of Letters for her collection of essays on *The Algebre of Infinite Justice* but she refused it.

K.M.Pandey Describes the Accomplishment of the Novel

The God of Small Things is a polysemic novel which can be interpreted at several levelsa family saga narrating the story of four generations of a christian family... a novel having a religious overtone...a love story with a tragic end.

Gender Inequality is another repeated problem in the novel. In *The God of Small Things* characters such as Mammachi, Ammu and Baby Kochamma are treated unfairly because they are female. In the book, the male character possess more power. For example, Pappachi got a high ranking post in the government, while Mammachi is in charge of household chores. When Mammachi starts up a pickle business and becomes more successful and powerful, Pappachi develops an envy on her and started abusing her. In the novel ,the female characters appear to be more resourceful and smart, yet they are not ready to develop into a strong matriarchs due to the strict social structure.

Even though higher class female characters like Rahel, Ammu and Mammachi are physically healthy but they don’t have any right to make decisions in the society or in a family.

“The fact that something so fragile, so unbearably tender had survived, had been allowed to exist, was a miracle.”

In addition, people speak very low of women who do not marrying society. This is so evident when Roy talks about Baby Kochamma, accepted her regrettable fate of not having any husband, feeling bitter for Ammu because she saw her fighting against the same fate. When Baby Kochamma actually could not find any spouse, her father sent her off to college. This shows that families view on marriage is more important than basic education that should be provided for a women.

“Mammachi’s own marital experience has not enabled her to emphasize with her daughter’s brutalized married life .Rather , she sees Ammu’s failed marriage as just retribution for her daughter who dared to marry outside her community. Her firm emotional investment in the hierarchies of class ,caste and gender is illustrated at several points in the novel. (Caste, Colonialism and Counter-Modernity)

“Like a young bride who couldn’t believe her good fortune.”(p.22)

In the modern India ,gender-based difference continues to be an issue. In India ,people tend to believe that male are more valuable and so they prefer sons. Male are seen as bread-winners, while females are seen as a burdens for family because at the time of a marriage the brides family must offer some gold and dowry to the bridegrooms family which the parents of a girl cant afford. This eventually results in uneven female to male ratios. People they are ready to take illegal gender tests so that if the fetus is a female, then it will be aborted.

“Pointed in the wrong direction , trapped outside their own history unable to retrace their steps because their footprints had been swept away.”

A 2011 study in the British medical journal *Lancet* found that 12 millions Indian girls have been aborted in the womb itself in the last three decades. Asides from higher abortion rates of females, girls are cared less when compared with the male siblings. They may not

receive less healthcare and hence die from preventable diseases like diarrhea and pneumonia. According to a U.N. Gender Inequality Index, India's gender differentials in child mortality is the worsts in the world with a rank of 132 out of 148.

In some parts of India, laws that prohibit that daughters and widows to inherit land also exist. Addition to this, laws such as the Goa Polygamy law allow a husband to marry again if he does not get a son from his first marriage.

A lack of sanitary facilities and privacy also discourages Indian girls stepping into school. According to a study by AC Nielson and NGO Plan India, approximately 23% of girls discontinue their education once they hit puberty. Girls in school that lack the sanitary facilities for females have higher absent records, missing on average 50 days mainly because of menstruation.

Along with laws that discriminate against females, violence that are held against females is also relatively common. Two years ago, a college student was forced a sexual assault and murdered. Last year, a 5-year-old girl was plundered. These are only two out of the many extreme gender that female are faced with. The Indian National Crime Bureau states the number of rape cases to be 24,206 in 2011 in one every 21 minutes. Shockingly, only 26% of these cases resulted in offender judged guilty.

In the conclusion, we find that Arundathi Roy has a very deep concerns for small things. The small things means the victims of socio-political and the cultural practices. She confirms small things such as women, dalits and children who get the position of second sex. Women are always considered as the private property and always taken them for granted. Therefore in *The God of Small Things* Arundathi Roy has raised the voice for the voiceless and showed the gender inequality that is shown by the society.

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Rabindranath Tagore's Chandalika as a Cognitive Play

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Rabindranath Tagore is a renowned poet, musician and an artist. He was a Bengalian and English writer. In 1913 he won Nobel Prize for this notable work Gitanjali. His compositions were selected as National Anthem for two nations, India and Bangladesh. He also wrote many other short stories and novels. Chandalika is the play by Tagore which brings out ideas of upliftment of lower class people without degrading high class people.

Chandalika means the forbidden girl. Tagore always raised his voice against the maliciousness done by man to fellow men through the segmentation of caste and community. He always pleaded for the the perception that it is the Supreme Power who is Sporting in the world in so many forms like elegant and hideous. That it is our immunity his children to participate and adore that sport.

Tagore has deliberately given the heroine the name of Prakriti. The term means native, nature with all its elevated possibilities and the rigid actuality. Prakriti is convicted by the society Atul live a creep because of the the background of her birth. She has not known any e affection except that of her mother. When Buddhist monk Ananda asks the chandalika girl Prakriti to pour drinking water into his cupped hands. Prakriti who is basically pure readily accept the connotation of this small art. Her awareness suddenly blooms like the lotus in the rising Sun and she became profoundly awake of the honor to which she is characterized as a human being. Thus Prakriti and Ananda stand at the two Extreme levels of a psychological ratio. The two are brought together near the well of life.

A sense of her personality expanding into egoism and self conceit in Prakriti's mind started working. She wants the Buddhist Bhikshu in her arms and she is insisting her mother to use her eerie skills to bring the Bhikshu to her. The Bhikshu's words of advice to her had given her a sense of het own existence as a human being. Later she has began to think herself an significant person having the right to fall in love and having the right to await for an encouraging acknowledgment to her love. In this belief Prakriti is going too far in the direction of egoism and self conceit. Herself gas become more essential in her eyes.

The situation is aggravated when one day Ananda again happens to pass the same well, yet this time he is in an association of a group of other Buddhist monks, he does not even look in the direction of the well where a chandal girl quashed his thirstiness. Noticing Ananda's complete negligence to her and to the well. She thought that Ananda had forgotten her existence. She now strengthens her intentions to conquer Ananda and fore sin through the power of her mother. The mother who is helpless to bare her daughters adversity agrees to workout her magic spells.

After fifteen days of continuous chanting the magic spell started working. Prakriti can see the passion for sensual desire, which the Buddhist monk is fighting hard against his own sensual pleasure for the Chandal girl who had given him water to quench his thirst. In response to the spells, Ananda has already being travelling through the forest over The Hills in direction to Prakriti's house. Prakriti asks her mother to drive the Buddhist monk come to her and ask for water once again. This time she would give him water from the ocean of a heart.

She finds that the Buddhist monk has come very close to her house and feels happy to see him. She also sees the Buddhist monk's struggle to overcome his allurements towards the chandal girl. By seeing the struggle of her beloved she she asks her mother to stop the chanting. The Bhikshu against of his own misery pardons and blesses Prakriti at the end. She also realizes the fact that love for a person cannot be forced by anyone. She apologized for her guilt and changed her perception.

Thus play emphasizes Tagore's ideas that the helpless and the distressed have to be given a helping hand to come up in the communal and ethical scope. This cannot be attained by bringing the high class to the base level.

The Portrayal of Women as a Matriarch in Henry Ibsen's *A Doll's House*

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Abstract

*Henrik Johan Ibsen was born in 1828 in the town of Skien on the Southeast coast of Norway. At the age of fifteen Ibsen decided to become a professional artist and in 1884 he was apprenticed to an apothecary in Grimstad. Ibsen, the father of modern drama, began his career by writing romantic history plays. In 1870s he turned to social and ethical concerns. This was the play made Ibsen internationally famous. Ibsen was the first major dramatist to write tragedy about ordinary people in ordinary situations, using colloquial prose for dialogues. *A Doll's House* is a realistic play. It is an anti-romantic play both in its theme and setting. The play deals with the problem of man – women relationship through the mirror of marriage. The theme of the play is the assertion of wife's rights. Nora Helmer, remains the puppet and doll wife of her husband. She remains passive and self-effacing for eight years. At the end, she asserts herself and becomes an individual in her own right.*

Keywords: apothecary, ethical, puppet, doll.

A Doll's House the most famous and best known of Ibsen's plays was published in 1879. The play was a crushing indictment of contemporary middle-class marriage. It created immediate sensation. It was this play that made Ibsen internationally famous. Ibsen was the first major dramatist to write tragedy about ordinary people in ordinary situations, using colloquial prose for dialogues. *A Doll's House* is a realistic play. It is an anti-romantic play both in its theme and setting. The play deals with the problem of man-woman relationship through the mirror of marriage. The theme of the play is the assertion of wife's rights. Nora Helmer, remains passive and self-effacing for eight years. At the end, she asserts herself and becomes an individual in her own right.

Nora and Torvald Helmer seem to lead a happy life with three beautiful children. Torvald is fond of his pretty young wife. But he treats her as his pet and possession. He wants her to play the role of a beautiful, careless, happy wife. He controls everything in the house including the eating habits of Nora. He gives her money for buying fine clothes and let her dress and dance at the fancy dress ball in the apartment of the Stenborgs the night after Christmas. He does all these to stimulate his sexual desires. Nora is her husband's doll and the children are her doll.

Torvald is dead against borrowing and sees to it that the home is run within his income. He falls seriously ill, in order to save his life Nora takes him to a warm country in Italy by borrowing money from Krogstad, by forging her father's signature in the bond, without her husband's knowledge. When Torvald decides to dismiss Krogstad from the Bank, Krogstad threatens Nora that he will expose her forgery if her husband does not retain him in the Bank. But Torvald dismisses Krogstad, who writes a letter to him exposing Nora's forgery. Nora thinks that her husband would take all the blame on himself, when he comes to know the truth. In order to prevent that she even thinks of committing suicide. But all her hopes are shattered when her husband revealed his true colour. Then she realises that she has so long lived with a stranger and decides to break all marital ties with him. So she walks out of his house, slamming the door and goes out in quest of her identity.

Nora recalls her past when she was with her father at their home, she could not have any personal opinion on anything. Her father never allowed her to differ from him. Her father called her his "doll child" even when she had become old enough to marry, and played with her just as she played with her dolls when she was young. Nora was confined in her father's home and did what he wanted. She had never left home. After that she was simply transferred from her father's hands to that of Torvald's. Then it was Torvald who arranged everything to his taste.

In Torvald's home she is treated as a child. She is protected, petted, patted, dressed up, given pocket money but is not allowed to be herself. She has not been allowed to be her true self either by her father or by Torvald, her husband. As both have treated her like a doll, she has to play the "doll" throughout. She plays the doll with her husband and pleases him and helps him to keep his image as the head of the house.

The doll-world set up makes Nora nurture romantic notions about her husband's love for her. She hopes that when her husband comes to know about the forgery committed by her, through Krogstad's letter, he would perform a miracle and would take up all the blame on him and let Krogstad publish his letter. Torvald shatters all her hopes by showing out his true colour and Nora understands that all her romantic notions are illusions of her doll-world. Nora, the heroine of the play, is modern in the sense that she readily gives up her traditional role of the doll wife and doll-mother in order to get self-liberation individuality and independence. In its middle-class setting, its plot and its medium, the play tends to be modern.

The Pictorial Representation of Social Milieu in Kamala Markandaya's Nectar in a Sieve

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Kamala Markandaya is a well-known and renowned writer of the twentieth century. She is a Revolutionary writer especially by focusing on the real-life of rural India. The grass-root analysis of Markandaya's work shows that she has an excellent knowledge of Indian rural life. The novel Nectar in a Sieve is her first novel in which a sincere attempt was made to project a pragmatic survey of rural India in all its shades and details – early marriage, dowry system, illiteracy, lacking in family planning, famine, drought, excessive rain, and struggle for survival, eviction, And superstition. There is a realistic description of a village which is symbolic of rural India.

It Depicts with vivid clarity and keen observation of social conditions of rural India. Individually, the terrible disgrace that human life brings is depicted with courageous realism. Markandaya spotlights the depression of the farmers realistically. They are desperate because of the vagaries of heartless men, the ruthless machines, the rampant hunger, and natural calamities. When an Indian village is on the threshold of industrialization, the peasant community suffers.

Both physically and mentally. Nathan and Rukmani are representatives of tenant growers in India and their life is an example of the mess caused by industrialization. Rukmani is the protagonist of the novel Nectar in a Sieve, has undergone many. Obscurities as a responsible Indian wife. She has been continuously entrapped and messed by The social setup which was followed by the ancestors of Rukmani. Being an educated daughter of the headman of the village, her family faced the hard times on her marriage which leads her to marry.

A tenant farmer, Nathan at her too young age. Though her husband Nathan is elder to her, his patience proves to be a loving person. Rukmani gives birth to the first child, a beautiful daughter named Irrawaddy, but for six Long years she fails to bear another child. Rukmani's husband wait for boy child so she secretly meets with western doctor Kenny who discharges his duties diligently and offers

her Treatment for infertility. Rukmani gives birth to five sons. Although, Rukmani and Nathan both Delight in their many children. Rukmani's family becomes a large one, so they search for a better salary job which must meet out the needs of the family.

Very soon, when a leather tannery opens in their village, things begin to change. People Are happy about the establishment of tannery unit which brings work and good pay. But the nearby villagers also influx to the area for doing a job which paves the way to hike the food prices. It makes the situation more difficult for Rukmani's family to feed her daughter and sons. In this The situation, Rukmani arranges the marriage for her daughter Irrawaddy. The suitor of Irrawaddy is Found by old Granny. They are delighted in finding a "good match" with a man financially Secure enough to care for her. At that time, they have had a good harvest, so both decide to Conduct the wedding. Unfortunately, that the same year the monsoon arrives earlier and destroys their crops which forced them to depend on their saved supplies, many of that were used at the wedding celebration.

The two eldest sons of Rukmani, namely Arjun and Thumbi now, in their early teen, work At tannery. Irrawaddy's husband returns their daughter to them because she cannot bear a child. In the secret, Rukamani pleads the western doctor to give her fertility treatment, but it is too late. Irrawaddy husband marries another woman. The boy's income at the tannery help to keep the Family afloat for a few years. To get rid of the trouble-making labors they organize a labor the strike which leads their family into more trouble, so they emigrate to Ceylon forever to work on a Tea estate. They do not have communication with the family. All these were happened because of Rukmani and Nathan's unawareness of family planning. The whole family continued to struggle. almost their family members are scattered. For the following year, the farmers encounter drought and the crops all wither and die.

The landlords also demand the tenant farmers to pay half of the rent for the land. Rukmani sells Even the cattle's to buy grains, but it is not enough. Starvation forces their family to forage Garbage and grass to eat. Due to poverty, Rukmani's third son Raja steals calfskin, he was Killed by tannery guards. Selvam, their fourth son, is the most educated person in the family who Works as an apprentice to the doctor Kenny. Rukmani's youngest son Kuti is suffered from poverty and so he was in dying state which forces Irrawaddy into prostitution.

One evening in a rage, Rukmani attacks Irrawaddy while she comes late to home. The family has no choice but to accept her new occupation. Kuti slowly recovers and soon his health Dies and deteriorates. Irrawaddy gives birth to an illegitimate child of Sacrabani. Though illiteracy prevail everywhere, Rukmani somehow succeeded in her life because of her rudimentary education and also her family members support.

The novel Nectar in Sieve highlights and unfolds many social issues which cause Rukmani's family to spread to various places and which makes all aware of social incapability and economic inadequacy and also kindle the inner heart of mankind.

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Deracination in the poem **House and Land** by **Allen Munro Curnow**

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Allen Curnow was a leading poet of New Zealand. His works are well known for the theme of displacement. It gives a firsthand experience of the issues that bothered the English settlers in New Zealand. *House and Land* is one of his famous works and is based on the same theme.

Allen Curnow’s *House and Land* investigates the sentiment of alienation experienced by the European immigrants. Even though they have used two generations in the selected land, they still felt displaced. Curnow indicates the theme of displacement, though the settlers dismissed from England to New Zealand. They failed to identify New Zealand as their inability to adapt to the place. Miss Wilson, the child of one of the immigrants, obtains herself charged with avoid. A Historian visits her home for research on the immigrants. He learns that the lady lives a luxurious life. She has grown old.

She cherishes the everlasting memories of her girlhood days spent in England. She is filled with pride at the photograph of a baronet uncle. It shows her pride in her ancestral heritage. A picture that portrays the big hall of her ancestral house also revealed her rich past. Her expansive building was equipped with all the necessary amenities of life. In spite of a stay for such a long time, she felt detached. Miss. Wilson represents the settlers who managed to adopt but failed to adapt.

The Cowman, a resident of the house, tells the historian about his long association with the family. He has been working for them from Miss. Wilson’s father’s days. Upon enquiring about the family background., he has no answer. His statement, he merely “lives,” shows his detachment. He has already made up his capacity to shift his working place next winter. He says that he is leaving the house because it is “bloody quiet”. The house lacks joy or merriment. It is haunted by utter hopelessness.

The historian then takes up the case of the tie-up dog within the compound. The dog was lying tied up “under the bluegums.” The phrase underscores the feeling of depression. The dog seems to be brooding and consuming itself. It just lazily rambles from privy to fowl house to a restroom. It senses the innate stagnation and a state of decay.

Miss. Wilson, her servants, and even the dog experience a sense of hollowness. The idea that the house might fall illustrates how fragile their spiritual situation was. The spirit of exile, concludes the historian, “Is strong in the people still. Miss. Wilson is obsessed with the past. The Historian senses that it is going to rain. Rain is some fertility and redemption. Though it rains, it does not bring contentment. The dog retires to its vessel, where it remains “lost and lame.” The word ‘lame’ suggests the advantage of the settlers as they missed their motherland. The settlers always felt themselves to be unfinished.

The poet voices his opinion through the Historian. The message is loud and clear. The settlers must move on and not cling to their past. Having adopted the country, they should adapt themselves accordingly. Things cannot change drastically, but the hope is there to be pursued.

In House and Land Allen Curnow emphasises the theme of displacement. Though the settlers removed from England to New Zealand, they failed to identify New Zealand as their homeland. Though they live in the selected land, they have not yet adapted to the circumstances. Unless they change their attitude, their life will remain miserable. The poet believes that the next generation will change. He presents it symbolically through the rain that occurs in the last stanza. Ole Miss. Wilson does not have anybody to carry on her legacy. With her end, the old connections too will end.

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A Brief Study about Transgender

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Abstract

This paper provides a general sense of transgender studies in society. This review primarily focuses on knowledge that will benefit the transgender people and communities. It also focuses on cultural presentations, political movements, social organizations. The transgender studies also provide an interdisciplinary approach to gender studies. It includes transgender history, transgender literature, transgender psychology, and their health.

Keywords: Movements, Interdisciplinary, History.

A subfield of LGBT studies, transgender studies gives an interdisciplinary approach to gender studies, gay and lesbian studies, and sexology by studying the intersections of sex and gender as related to cultural representations, lived experience, and political movements. The transgender studies provide replies to negative aspects of beliefs about transgender people. Those negatives mistakes could be the narrow and inaccurate transgender state in psychology medicine and psychology. The final goal of transgender studies is to provide knowledge that will benefit the transgender people and communities.

In response to analyses of how transgender issues were represented in gender, gay and lesbian studies, the late 1990s saw an increase in transgender scholarship and the emergence of a specific discipline of academic research. Transgender history begins with transgender people in early cultures in every developed region and remains to the instant. Sumerian and Akkadian writings from 4500 years ago document transgender reverends, and Assyrian texts document trans prostitutes. The evidence suggests these gender roles to back to prehistoric times and may have a common origin with third gender roles were accepted in America before European colonization Some of which survived colonizers hostility.

Graves of transgender people in Europe and America have been identified from 4500 years ago, and likely depictions occur in art around the Mediterranean from 9000 to 3700 years ago. In those days in Greece, Phrygia and Rome, there were trans-female Galli priests and records of women dressing as men to vote, fight, study.

In the middle ages, accounts about Europe document trans men, while Kalonymu's lament for being born a man instead of a woman has been seen as an early account of gender diaspora. A male-bodied Briton captured in 1394 while living and acting sex work as a woman,

has been recognized as a trans woman. Transgender people are facing inequality and discrimination even before the 1880s. Some native American tribes had third-gender roles, including transgender people. When Europeans came over, they deemed them “berdaches” a derogatory term for a man trying to pass as a woman’s pejorative term for women who wanted to assume masculine roles. The name ‘transitive’ originated in 1910 from the German sexologist Magnus Hirschfeld. At that time, it was used similarly to transsexual, a word that was not coined until the late 1940s. The term transgender was first used in 1971.

Transgender people face inequality even when they try to begin their school education. A transgender person applied to school, and college was rejected because their home state identified as transgender. They gave first preference to ordinary human people and not transgender students. Mental and physical strain through varying forms of assault by their peers is an unfortunate effect on transgender students.

For instance, they have to face the embarrassing situation in the public restroom and whether they can use the male or female bathroom is choosing what restroom to use. While they enter into the lady’s toilet, women screamed in horror, and they will look like “you are not supposed to enter here/this is not a place for you” referring their gender though they did not confront them. They try to say that they are trans woman, and have every rights to use the toilet.

Media shows transgender as a sex worker and begging people in so many movies. The reality presented about transgender as sex workers are the view of entertainment. Transgender usually represented as roaming alone or group with brighter make-up, wigs glittering costumes and as calling the heroes and comedians for sexual relationships in media and showing innocents suffered by transgender, their social in certainty does not represent in any film and transgender people usually represented in songs, particularly songs which humiliate them in some movie.

While the transgender people traveling by bus or train they alienated by the other passengers. In case the transgender people sit along with them, they gave respect through Untouchability. Even if they are the standard genders like men and women are mistreating them with their misrepresentation names.

These things reflect the sick mentality of people. We have to respect them like other human beings. There is nothing to discriminate them. As a human being a part of society, we have the responsibility to produce them and respect them.

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Topsy – Turvy condition of the illegal immigrants in Kiran Desai’s “The Inheritance of Loss”

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Abstract

Kiran Desai, one of the talented writers of our generation published her novel “The Inheritance of Loss” in 2006 and fetched the “2006 Man Booker Prize” for it. She highlighted the sufferings of the illegal immigrants in this novel. Some people build air castles and go abroad thinking they can spin money there. But things become topsy – turvy for them. They are kicked by people from one place to the other and they finally decide to fly back to their mother land. These aspects are highlighted by Kiran Desai in her novel “The Inheritance of Loss”

Twentieth century women’s writing was considered as a powerful medium of modernism and feminist statements. The last two decades have witnessed overflowing success in portraying the theme of immigration and consequent alienation of the self. This was the metric pre-occupation of Indo-Anglian novelists like Jumpha Lahiri, Chitra Banerjee, Amitav Gosh and Kiran Desai. They are chiefly concerned with cross- cultural and racist encounters between the characters on socio-cultural plane.

Kiran Desai who was born of 3rd September 1971 at Delhi, is one of the talented writers of our generation. She is the daughter of Anita Desai. She wrote her first novel *Hullabaloo* in the *Guava – Orchard* in 1998. She was highly exalted for this work and she received a 1998 Betty Trask Prize from the British society of Authors. Eight years later, her second novel *The Inheritance of Loss* was published in early 2006 and won the 2006 Man Booker Award, the National Book critics Circle Fiction Award in 2007 and the 2006 vodafone crossword Book Award. Rajni Singh passed the following comments on the novel *The Inheritance of Loss*:

Desai tries to depict the subjugation and exploitation of immigrants from centuries by America, the economic super power of world. Post modern global economy has created drastic situation in the life of third world immigrants specially the predicaments of illegal immigrants are nerve shattering (198).

The Inheritance of Loss. follows the journey of Biju, an illegal immigrant in the U.S. who is trying to make a new life. This novel is set partly in India and partly in the U.S.A. Desai tries to capture what

it means to live between East and West and what it means to be an immigrant and she highlights how an illegal immigrant is fretting and fuming in a foreign land.

Jemubhai Patel, a retired judge lived with his chatty cook Nandu and with his granddaughter Sai. Nandu's only son worked as an illegal immigrant in various restaurants in New York. He moved from one place to another and sadly remembered his father and childhood days in a village in India.

The novel concentrated on the down scale immigrants who were leading a miserable and disrespectful life in America, with a staunch hope of a better future for his son. The cook, with his very meagre savings, planned to send his son to America. Biju too dreamt of establishing himself in an alien soil. In America, Biju leaped from one low paid restaurant job to another. The insensitive restaurant owners, not only exploited Biju, but also took every opportunity to degrade him which was the part of their power game.

At the Gandhi Café, Biju had close association with rats. They said "Halloo" and chewed his hair. He was having power of tolerance and he was able to bear with it. Kiran Desai vividly portrays how the rats played on him casually:

The rats of his earlier jobs had not forsaken Biju. They were here too, exulting in the garbage, clawing through wood, making holes... One chewed Biju's hair at night (147)

S. Nusrath Sulthana, in her "The Theme of Alienation and Identity Crisis in Kiran Desai's *The Inheritance of Loss* observes:

In New York, Biju finds himself cast in a strange world, a world where sympathy, fellow feeling and peaceful Co-existence does not seem to exist. He spends his time changing jobs, enduring deplorable conditions and trying to dodge the immigration authorities of the United States. As he is an illegal immigrant, he is forced to work for very few wages and experience extreme servitude to his employers.

At Pignocchio's Italian Restaurant, Biju had a tough time, in pleasing the owner's wife. The lady complained that Biju smelt Indian and that she was allergic to his hair oil. The lady's persistent grumbling and disgust for Biju, compelled him to seek a new job for himself. "He smells," said the owner's wife, "I think I am allergic to his hair oil" (48)

Kiran Desai had portrayed the impact of the politics of globalization and post colonialism on the economic structure of the once colonized nation. When an advertisement appeared in the local paper for drudge staff in America, Biju applied and attended the interview in Kathmandu, Nepal and finally got selected. Biju took some of the cook's fake recommendations with him to the interview to prove that he had come from an honest family and a letter from Father Pooty. When the Americans enquired, Biju had shown a fake bank statement procured by a cook from a corrupt State Bank Clerk in exchange of two bottles of Black Label. Desai presented this character "Biju" who got trapped in the vicious desire of becoming a 'big shot'. Saeed from Zanzibar, kavafya from kaza, Omar from Malaysia and Harish Harry from India endured the pain of exile with a smile. The illegal immigrants spent their time dodging the authorities and stood benumbed to the questions asked by them.

In New York, Biju worked in different restaurants as an illegal immigrant and thus encountered unhappy social as well as cultural experiences in the West:

Biju joined the shifting population of men camping out near the fuse box, behind the boiler in the cubby holes, and in old shaped corners that once were pantries, maid's room, laundry rooms and storage rooms (51).

Racial situations and reactions have come up at many places in the narrative. Biju had inherited feelings of 'Nationality' and hatred for subjugating "white world". In New York, Biju felt tormented by the thoughtless commercialism, rampant racism and rapacious ruin perpetuated by the neo-colonial exploitation. He eventually came back to India. His life in 'America was full of hardships.

Tired of hopping from one job to another, he decided either to go back to India or to get all elusive green cards. In the USA, the illegal immigrants lost their identities. Regarding this Dr. Rajni Singh opines:

Migration is a realistic pain and a deplorable situation of illegal immigrants in the USA... Every character of novel persuades, but in reality he has not received anything, nevertheless he loses whatever he gets in his life (200)

Biju was walking on the thorny and ticklish path in New York. He thought over the happy days, he had spent with his father in Kalimpong. Biju felt the past days in India were jubilant and he thought that he walked on bed of roses during those days. Biju pondered:

How powerful our village is. How good the roti tastes there! It is because the atta is ground by hand, not by machine ... and because it is made on a choobash, better than anything cooked on a gas or on kerosene stove (103)

At Gandhi Café in New York, Harish Harry, the owner of the café told him how he could not afford money to him for his medical expenses. He pointed an accusing finger at Biju and told him that he was responsible for breaking his leg. He blamed him of not being careful and said:

You should have to pay me for not cleaning living like a pig. Am I telling you to live like a pig? You can help cutting the vegetables while lying down and if you are not better, go home. Doctors are very cheap and good in India (188-189)

Kiran Desai brought out Biju's pitiable condition by the image of the dead insect. It was ironical to see that the restaurant workers in America could at least relish daintly dishes, no matter even if it was at the cost of their own country. Biju was sick of the fork and knife, the everyday difficulties, the green card desire and the daily assaults of the restaurant owners. Biju decided to go back to India with his little savings. But misfortune was waiting for him in Kalimpong. He was robbed off his belongings. But misfortune was waiting for Biju in Kalimpong. He was robbed off his belongings, money and even his American dress.

Kiran Desai used "irony" as one of the devices to highlight the theme of the novel. Biju and his father made all attempts right and wrong to get American Visa for Biju. The cook obtained a fake passport with the hope of bright future. He was proud to announce he was the father of a boy in America. He even recommended some boys for jobs in America. Kiran Desai used the symbol of idle insect to explain the condition of Biju in America, because his hopes were devastated.

Whether India or America, human beings cannot fulfill their dreams and that is what the novel tried to say. Cook's dream was to see his only son become an American. Sai's dream rested on her lover Gyan. Biju's only dream was to earn wealth. But nobody's dream was fulfilled till the end. That is the reason why Kiran Desai titled this novel as *The Inheritance of Loss*

Of late people have craze for visiting and working in abroad. They enter into a new nation, dreaming that it will be raining gold there. But when they meet with plenty of problems there, they start feeling that, "it is raining rats". This aspect is focused by Kiran Desai in this novel, through the character Biju.

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Feministic Perspective of Shashi Deshpande in a Matter of Time

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Abstract

The present paper entitled FEMINISTIC PERSPECTIVE OF SHASHI DESHPANDE IN A MATTER OF TIME speaks about feministic views of the novelist. Her chief concern is to expose the sufferings of women in the hands of their members of the family, including their husbands. This novel also depicts the picture of a lady, namely, Sumi, who is not exploited by her husband directly, but she suffers due to sudden and selfish abscond of her husband, Gopal, leaving all responsibilities of the family upon her shoulders. This novel portrays the pathetic condition of Sumi and other women characters in a patriarchal set-up. Shashi Deshpande gives a sensitive portrayal of female protagonists attempt to be liberal and independent in thinking, making decisions, taking actions, working, and creating on the same terms as men. They try to move towards self-realization, self-investigation, and self-assertion. They fight against age-old man-made rules with the help of their inner strength. Her novel A Matter of Time explores the many facts of feminine sufferings in India, like gender differences and passive experiences, familial relationships. Sumi in A Matter of Time is an emancipated lady who undertakes her journey to liberation after she is deserted by her husband Gopal after twenty-three years of married life. The novel puts forth Shashi Deshpande's views on women's liberation.

Keywords: feminist, aspiration, submissive, marriage, family empowerment, patriarchy.

Shashi Deshpande's novels are always dealt with woman, her anguish and deprivation, tensions and irritations, grief and sorrow. Unable to disobey social conventions or traditional morality, the middle-class women themselves are entangled by desires and despairs, fears and hopes loves and hates, withdrawal and alienation, suppression and oppression, marital discord and male chauvinism. Indeed, Shashi Deshpande's central theme is a woman's struggle, in the context of contemporary Indian society, her effort to find and maintain her identity as a wife.

Her writings are a sincere effort to examine the hidden psyche and consciousness of women caught in the trap of patriarchal society. She has a thorough understanding of the fundamental reality of the tragic life of women, victimized creatures. She deplores that they have always been socially, emotionally, psychologically, sexually, and biologically suppressed and exploited in a male-dominated society.

This novel describes the picture of a lady, namely Sumi, suffers due to sudden and selfish escape of Gopal, her husband leaving all

responsibilities of the family upon her shoulders. One evening Sumi's world is collapsed as her husband Gopal walks out from home, leaving her with three daughters Aru, Charu and Seema. The pain of the breakdown of the family upsets Aru who considers herself responsible for her father's death and sets out to undo it. Sumi along with her daughters go back to their ancestral house where her mother Kalyani had been living in a depressive and strange silence, striving to make sense of her relation with her husband who hasn't talked to her for years. Sumi finds comfort in taking up her dream career; Aru understands her mother's indifference and her father's desertion.

The novel revolves around an urban middle-class family consisting of Gopal and Sumi and their three daughters. Sumi maintains long silence in her adverse circumstances without complaining against anyone and accepts it in a mute way. Gopal has a cordial relationship with his wife and daughters so long as he lives with them, but he deserts them suddenly for a reason not known to others. Among the daughters, Aru is the eldest one who proves herself more intelligent, wise, and respectful towards her whole family, including her grand-father and grand-mother. Sumi, an educated lady, matured enough to know the reality of life and truth of the world. She is ready to face any hard situation in her life, so she does not stop Gopal leaving the family.

A Matter of Time is a story of female emancipation as it describes the journey of Sumi to her liberation. She has much concern about her career. So that she does not see herself lonely for her grief. With full of courage and boldness, she astonishes everyone. She works hard because she wishes to pay her daughters fee and their other demands not expecting from anybody.

Deshpande wants her women not to remain passive and submissive but to emerge as a firm, self-assured and ambitious characters in their ways, attempting to and succeeding in striking a delicate balance between traditional beliefs and individual needs. She portrays her married women not to be mere shadows of their husbands. They refuse to accept them as sheltering trees. They never follow their husbands blindly and mechanically. She makes them realize that true liberty lies in having the courage to do what one accepts is the right thing to do and the resolution to stick to it. She makes them be new and modern in the true sense of the term.

In A Matter of Time, education is the only way through which the women's knowledge can be expanded, and her place can be assured in the society to which she belongs. She regards women individuals equal to men, as competent to them with a lot of abilities and potentials. Her female protagonists undergo a psychological journey of self-realization to trace themselves as free and independent individuals. They can discover and assert their self-identity and self-realization. They have an appetite to make themselves bold and confident, to detect space for themselves to grow and develop on their own. Though, many of her female characters are emotionally and sexually frustrated; they struggle against conventions and traditions within the framework of a family.

Gopal lodges a few miles away from his wife and daughters in the house of Shankar, one of his old students. Gopal's desertion disturbs the very peace, happiness, and balance of the family. Sumi's return to the Big House after Gopal's abandonment is a matter of shame both for Aru, her eldest daughter, and Kalyani, her mother. Kalyani, Devaki, Premi, and others feel sorry for the failure of her marital life. The family renders to take her into confidence and even to comfort her. Sumi never wishes to unlock her heart to anybody.

After Gopal's desertion, though, Sumi seems to be calm and undisturbed, her grief, fury, and humiliation are so deep and severe that she becomes anxious and restless. Her silence turns into a cry of despair. She feels alone and emotionally disturbed. She comforts herself when she says: "It takes time to get used to sharing your life with another person, now I have to get used to being alone" (23).

She determines to adjust herself with changing circumstances and to accept her tragic life. She is bothered about her daughters. She asks herself: "Am I the enemy? Do my daughters blame me for

what Gopal has done? Do they think it is my fault? Why can't I talk to them, tell them what I feel, how it was? Why can't I open my heart to them?" (23).

Aru proves herself strong and bold in adverse circumstances. She gives her full support to her mother at her level best. She behaves to be a responsible member of the family. Sumi does not wish to be a parasite in the family. She, therefore, seeks a temporary job of a teacher to support herself and her daughters. It is hard to Sumi to handle her daughters. On the surface, they appear to live a normal course of their lives, but Sumi notices some change in them. They have withdrawn into themselves. Aru's reserve has changed into secretiveness. Charu turns into a single-minded book worm. She appears to be interested in her college, with her evening classes and books. Seema keeps distance both from her mother and her sisters. Uneasily, she thinks: "I don't want my daughters to live with a hand clasped over their mouths like Premi and I had to" (59).

She does not like her daughters to be silent sufferers. Sumi has no hatred for her husband. Aru is not ready to forget and forgive her father's action. She wishes even her mother not to forget it. She asks her mother to consult the lawyer and to do something against him. Sumi does not go with her. She just laughs and says:

Gopal has outsmarted the law. He's given us all that he had. And he has nothing now, not even a proper job... So what can the law make him do? ... Do you want to punish him, Aru? I don't. I'm not interested. I just want to get on with my life... Let him go, Aru, just let him go. This is not good for you(61).

Gopal's abandonment creates a vacuum in Sumi's life. She traces out the clues in the past acts and utterances of Gopal. During her search for the house, she happens to meet her husband for the first time since the day he left home. They cannot speak freely, and they feel the burden of unsaid things. They become speechless when they look at each other. She realizes:

We can never be together again. All these days I have thought of him as if he has been suspended in space, in nothingness, since he left us. But he has gone on living; his life has moved on, it will go on without me. So has mine. Our lives have diverged; they now move separately, two different streams. (85)

Sumi proves herself to be a woman of daring, self-possessed, dignity, self-sufficiency and self-fulfillment by taking care of her daughters without the help of her husband. She manages her family in her adversity. Though she has full of grief and humiliation, she makes herself calm and controlled.

Gopal's departure makes the whole family into collapse. This unexpected crisis in her life gives her a chance to prove her inner strength and potentiality. She patiently accepts the role of a deserted wife. She does not encourage any discussion over it and prefers to be silent. Her self-respecting nature and self-trust do not allow her to accept any monetary help from her close relatives. She is ready to face the challenges of her life. She never expects pity or concern from her family members. Sumi's decision to learn to ride the scooter indicates that she is confident enough to live her life all by herself.

A Matter of Time is not about only Sumi or Gopal; it portrays the life of four generations of women. Manorama belongs to the first generation is dead, but her presence is always felt, Kalyani is of the second generation, Sumi is of the third generation, and Aru is of the fourth generation. Manorama was the daughter of a poor man and was married in a very wealthy family. Kalyani, Sumi, and Aru are the direct victims of patriarchal society. Sumi, after Gopal's desertion, gets a new identity. She changes herself into an independent woman. Aru, the fourth generation, is constantly trying hard to come to terms with reality.

She has to overcome this shock and establish her life in society. Sumi bears everything with silence. She does not ask the reasons for her husband's desertion. Sumi longs to be independent.

She transforms her emptiness into meaningful to redefine her identity. She began a new phase of her life and dedicated herself to her job and her children. In Indian society, A woman has a happy life when she has got the dependent marital life. But Sumi revolts against this tradition. She starts writing and her first play, *The Gardener's Son*, becomes successful.

Sumi gets a job and decides to go to Devgiri. Aru is shocked when she knows about it, but Sumi says, "Be happy for me, Aru. This is the first thing in my life. I think that I've got for myself" (220). Only when Sumi attains economic freedom and immerses herself in creative writing, she becomes more dynamic. Sumi meets with an accident while riding a scooter with her father, Shripati. Both Sumi's and Shripati's bodies are found heavily injured. Sumi dies just before she is going to start a new life. But she has proved her identity and found a meaningful existence before her death.

Traditionally, marriage is the "only means of support and the sole justification" of a woman's existence. But Deshpande has revealed that a woman can also find meaningful existence even outside marriage. Sumi's daughters also establish their identity. Aru is going to be a lawyer, and Charu is on her way to becoming a doctor. They are loved by two capable young men -Rohit and Hrishikesh. When Sumi is ready for a fuller life, it is an irony of fate that her life cut off in the prime. It is a pity that Sumi dies when she gets a job to support herself and her daughters. She would have become an economically independent woman with a modern and matured outlook towards life; and at the same time, a loving and responsible mother.

The novel illustrates how women are being treated in India. Though Deshpande brings out the submissiveness of her women characters, she enables them to move in a positive direction to maximize their potential.

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An Atlas of Impossible Longing: A Study from the Green Perspectives

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Abstract

This article seeks to examine the relationship between man and his environment. Anuradha Roy portrays man as a part of an ecosystem. The characters in the novel are a part of an intricate system. Anuradha Roy shows that if man is to be complete and content, he should view himself as a part of the natural world. This article illustrates the eco-critical consciousness of the novelist and how the nature is treated in this novel. The novelist portrays characters as searching for comfort in the nature and characters grew with nature. The novelist presents nature as one of the characters in the novel.

Keywords: Intricate system, Natural world, Ecosystem, Nature.

Anuradha Roy, one of the well-known Indian women writers. She gained fame as a novelist. The novel *An Atlas Of Impossible Longing* sets in the outskirts of Bengal, Amulya and his family lives in their big new home. Kamal and Nirmal are the two sons of Amulya and Kananbala. Nirmala's wife died during the childbirth and gave birth to Bakul. Mukunda, orphan boy is adopted, who helps Amulya.

Anuradha Roy in her novel, *An Atlas of Impossible longing* describes about the relationship between the human beings and the nature through the portrayal of its characters. The novel begins with the life of Amulya in Songarh. Amulya is a family man with a young wife and two children. His family abandons the Calcutta life and lives in Songarh town where he can co-exist peacefully with nature. This decision to settle in Songarh was taken by Amulya himself because while Amulya came to visit the fort and the town, it gave energy to him and when Amulya walked over the little town he felt a connection with the town. The idea of living in the town came to him as a benediction. He was not stopped from thinking about Songarh and felt that his life would be completed if he would live in Songarh. He liked and wished to enjoy the silence in nature.

Anuradha Roy throughout her novel uses ruined fort and wilderness into the characters to show that how nature is interconnected with characters. The ruined fort and the forest in Songarh gave spirit to Amulya. As years passed the nature also grew with Amulya's family. The ruined fort was in broken condition and even in its ruined condition; fort gave a fresh and peaceful feel to him. A few walls and one domed watchtower, which were in the fort was enough to feed Amulya's fantasies.

Amulya has a very deep and strong relationship with nature and forest. He woke up early in the morning and enjoyed the cool air and purple sky and felt that the forest was his only solace. When he came to Songarh the place was filled with weeds and bathua. Now the place is grown with “soft carpet of droop grass” (67). Amulya has a garden too. There is also a kitchen garden, which is dark with trees. Tall jackfruit trees and green coconut trees, like the green patches of his cultivation, have left their despairing signs in the abundant lush greenery when the saplings were planted the twigs were with four or five leaves. After twenty years those saplings are thirty feet tall and the branches seek place in the sky which is not visible under their garden and the afternoon stillness is broken by the falling of fruits from the trees. He speaks to the plants and nature is the only true companion for him. He walks all around the garden and sits in the garden swing. Every day he inspects them tenderly and pats those making strokes and he sees the plants as if it were pet animals.

Amulya converts the wilderness into garden by clearing the weeds and planting fruit trees, flowering plants and creepers. He selects plants to grow in his garden, and disregard the pink Kachnar and orange become plants. He planted his garden with flowers that bloom in darkness which gleamed white in darkness and scent the night time air. He allowed only one coloured flowering plant, that is yesterday – today – tomorrow colour plant, in which the flower turns from purple to white over during days and spreads fragrance. The rest of the garden was filled with pure white flower, *Magnolia grandiflora*, a plant which spreads its creamy petals against the shining green leaves. He also grows *Jasminum pubescens*, *Jasminum sambac*, *Nyctanthe sarbortrists*, and *Cestrum nocturnum*. The earth, Anuradha Roy presents, is one where little things matter.

Amulya finds solace in nature. At times when he was filled with thought he failed to notice the changes in nature. He also found solace in the ruined fort, the fort comforted him and gave him spirit and the nature calmed his mind. Amulya was on his way to the ruined fort. It comforted him to sit soundless among the fallen stones, thinking of nothing in particular waiting for his sense of calm to return. The fort was his ivory tower; he went to it whenever he needed to think anything through in solitude. Perhaps it was the suggestion of evanescent empires, the gaittiness of centuries. Old stone or perhaps the memory of people who, in those ruined rooms and dark passage, had lived lives as real as his own. It might have been the twisted grey-brown bark of tree with its suggestion of the Buddha's face.

Amulya reached the rim of the fort and sat on a block of fallen stone, a tall, greying, angular figure watching the blue shallow pool at the edge, which at that time of year had some water still. The folds of his dhoti spilled wave like on this stone, lifting a little at times in the breeze, picking up the dust which he did not notice. When the sun began to set the birds would know and began to call out each other. He willed himself to listen to the birds and think of nothing else. After the death of Amulya the garden was left unnoticed and it went back to wilderness, the garden was tended for a time but by an itinerant garden who had to be sacked after it was found he who nurturing a flourishing failed of cannabin in a sunny corner. Soon the grass was knee-high again and wild bushes of berries at the edges were attracting birds and noisy monkeys.

Anuradha Roy gives the relation between humans and the natural world in literature and how characters behave when they are in harmony with wilderness. Nature is represented as a comfort to the characters in the novel. Kananbala wife of Amulya also has relationship with nature. Kananbala is a house wife, who had to be in her house all alone, there was no neighborhood and there is no one to talk to her. So Kananbala wanted to disappear into the trees. She looked out through the window the moonlit trees. Once Kananbala and Larissa Barnum, the neighbourhood white lady went to the ruins of the fort. Kananbala though she is mentally ill she walked fastly to the old stone walls, touched the stone and saw the enormous banyan tree with hundreds of aerial roots. Barnum liked nature and said “Thus tree is supposed to bring people peace. It certainly does me” (81).

Kananbala was filled with happiness and her smile was filled with radiance. When she saw a shallow pool of water she ran towards the water like a child. She sat dipping her toes and let the feet slide in the water. In the ruined fort Mrs. Barnum tells the background of her life. But Kananbala was unable to understand anything.

Anuradha Roy represents characters as a peace gives. The physical and geographical settings in the novel also intermingled with nature and characters. Nirmal, son of Amulya and Kananbala also interested in garden who also went to Songarh ruins. Excitement and happiness filled Nirmal when he walked into the ruins. While Nirmal was in the ruins he also accepted the birds as part of the nature. Nirmal went to Rajasthan as a part of his job. He liked the desert sky in Rajasthan.

Anuradha Roy portrays pet animals and birds in the novel. The pet animals and birds also play a part as a character in the novel. It is to discover the roles have been played by literature in the ecology. Nirmal grew a pet dog, and he did not want to leave his dog alone. His wife is Shanti, who is also interested in growing plants. She named her daughter "Bakul". She was named by the tree which was found near her room. Bakul was also interested in gardening from her childhood. Mukunta another character in this novel named his son as "Gowtam", he named his son after the Banyan tree in Songarh ruins. Meera, a widow who was in Songarh to look after Bakul, was interested in feeding animals. She walked all the way to the ruins to feed the stray dogs, she felt bothered about the dog's foe those days when she did not come to feed the dog. When Meera decided to leave Songarh and go to new place she came to take a last look at the ruined fort and also to see the dog and its pups for the last time. Nirmal and Meera thought that the dog's family would be waiting for her every day. Meera also liked walking to the beautiful places in Darjeeling there were beautiful places to walk and had hills, beautiful orchids.

Suleiman Chacha, was the history teacher and house owner. Mukunda stayed in his house. Suleiman Chacha grew a parrot called Noorie. It looked as all parrots do, bright green, with a scarlet-purple band around the neck which seemed to be able to swivel a full circle as it watched people from its cage. Every night, Suleiman Chacha would cover the cage with a cloth, all the while muttering to the bird in a coaxing tone he used only with it. During the day, Chacha and Chachi would take turns to tempt the bird with curly green chillies and grain. The cage was large with a swing in it, which was kept in the wide upstairs verandah overlooking the trees, so that "Noorie could envy her free compatriots at leisure" (189).

Suleiman Chacha loved the parrot so much that the bird was let fly free in the house. He after completing his morning prayers goes to the cage and left cloth "with a flourish, making chucking noises at the bird" (189). The bird too loved the family and it responded to the family with a series of clicks of its beak and a soft word or two. Suleiman Chacha had taught the bird to say his name and half a dozen of other words. "As parents do with young children, he would coax the bird into speech for his visitors" (189). Suleiman and Noorie had been together every morning. Mukunda and Noorie had a good relationship. Noorie talked to Mukunda and he felt that Noorie was his constant companion: "It was only to her that I could confide how my success made me" (205). It would be on the door or on Chacha's shoulder or in Mukunda's shoulder.

Suleiman Chacha and Chachi decided to leave Calcutta. Chachi brought crisp green chillies and half a kilo of the grain which the bird liked to eat. Chachi said to Mukunda, "You know the sound Noorie makes when she wants a Chilli don't you?" (191). Suleiman Chacha asked Mukunda to keep the cage clean and talk to Noorie every morning: "Talk to her every morning, before you leave for work. She will be lonely with nobody in the house. She's not used to it" (98). After Suleiman Chacha and Chachi left the house parrot did not come out of the cage.

Barababu, Shanti's father and Mukunda's father-in-law, once he came to Suleiman Chacha's house. Barababu looked at the garden and as soon as they entered the house Barababu jumped to the corner and climbed up in the mango tree. He said that you don't know how much my soul longs for this. He said in rapture, looking down through a fringe of leaves on a high branch. "The village, our trees, the fruits I plucked as a boy" (195). Through these it is evident that Barababu, a minor character in the novel also portrayed as a lover of nature.

In another one incident Anuradha Roy made her character found comfort in nature. Mukunda went to Nirmal house. His heart beats uncomfortably and he wanted to slow down his breathing and calm him. So he looked back into garden, and saw "A madhabilata was in full flower on one of the walls. It had not been there before – a pink flowering intrude in the garden of whites. The mango trees had grown and small green fruit were visible even at a distance" (222). Mukunda walked into the garden and wandered towards the well. The white jasmine next to it was still there, still scattering the water with its flowers. He felt that it was a beautiful garden filled with old fruit trees, fragrant bushes and creepers. The incidents in this novel illustrate the ecocritical consciousness of the novelist and how nature is treated in this novel.

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An Outlook of Ecoregionalism in Amitav Ghosh's *The Hungry Tide*

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Abstract

*The purview of this article is to promote the voices of Amitav Ghosh regarding the environmental issues. In *The Hungry Tide*, Ghosh examines the landscape, the flora, the fauna and the tide people who settled in the Sunderbans, a reserved forest area. Except Lucibari and Garjontola, the other places such as Canning, Gosaba, Satjelia, Morichijihapi, Emilybari... etc are real one where a wide variety of rare species from the microscopic fish to the endangered man eating tiger live. The biotic life of the Sunderban is shaken by the invaded human beings. That leads to reduce the growth of the species. This height of ecological insanity creates a conflict between men and animals. Fear conquers the mind of the sunderbans. To survive in their allotted place, the animals struggle from the inhabitants. Tiger encounters, crocodile attacks, natural disasters... etc become common in that place. Nature as well as man function both as a preserver and destroyer. Ghosh creates an awareness among the readers about the ecology through Piyali Roy, the cetologist, who studies the dwindling breed of Irrawadoly dolphin. Unlike other naturalist, Ghosh shapes the ecoregion in new dimensions. He views the Sunderban region as a domain of consciousness. Thus, *The Hungry Tide* becomes a milestone of Ghosh to establish a new ecological ethics and environmental justice.*

Keywords: Biotic, ecoregionalism, ecological insanity, dwindling, cetologist.

Ecoregionalism is a philosophy that originated in the western America during the 1970's in response to the modern environmental crisis. 'Ecoregionalism' refers to the fullness of all earthly life existing in mutuality. Here, Regions are defined not by legislation, but by nature with a commonality of climate, geology, hydrology species and earth forms. From the perspective of ecoregion, it is a geographical area of similar climate where similar ecosystems and groups of species are found on similar sites.

Amitav Ghosh, the great genius in Indian literature, proved his talent of writing in his novels such as, *Sea of Poppies*, *River of Smoke*, *The Circle of Reason*, *The Shadow Lines*, *The Glass Palace*, *In an Antique Land*... etc. His biocentric vision is exemplified in his most famous novel *The Hungry Tide* which was published in 2005. In this novel, Ghosh portrays the biotic life in the Sunderban forest. The word 'Sunderban' means 'the beautiful forest' which derived its name from the common species of mangrove-the Sundari tree. A mangrove forests unique in nature and there are no giant trees, no ferns, no wild flowers and no chattering monkeys or cockatoos. The leaves in mangrove are laugh and leathery. A wide variety of species from the endangered Royal Bengal tiger to microscopic fish live in that Sunderbans.

In this novel *The Hungry Tide*, Ghosh pictures Sunderbans as a densely populated archipelago of islands situated on the border between India and Bengal. The primary locations, in the novel, Lusibari and Garjontala are fictitious of the author. But the secondary locations such as Canning, Gosasa, Satjelia, Morichjhapi and Emilybari are real one.

In *The Hungry Tide* Piyali Roy, the cetologist, comes to the Sunderbans with an aim to study the dwindling breed of Irawaddy dolphin. She recounts the richness of the sunderban fauna. A mother and calf pair of dolphins swim in a 'corkscrew pattern surface frequently and shooting the water with their mouth. The 'spitting behavior' is characteristic of toss the fish into the air before catching that. Later, she discovers the presence of an underwater pool, where the dolphins are seen to herd fish and hunt them, "much like rabbits uprooting a harvest of carrots, the dolphins were picking the fish from the riverbed"(167).

Piya discovers that the dolphins adapt their behavior according to the ebb and flow of the water. As a committed cetologist. Piya wants to protect the dwindling species of river dolphins. But she has to face many hurdles like asking permissions from the higher officers to do any action for saving the dolphins. She has to fight for the sufficient funds from the Government. Piya loves her profession and spends her hours by watering the animals and she thinks, "It would be enough; as an alibi for a life, it would do. She would not need to apologize for how she had spent her time on this earth" (127).

Ghosh compares the past populated species with the present reducing one, through the character Piya. On seeing the Orcaella in the underwater pool, Piya recollects a past incident when two fishermen got a school of fish towards their boat in order to catch the dolphins. While prey the herd of fish, the fishermen caught the dolphins and sunk them in the soft floor of the river Piya wonders, "Did there exist any more remarkable instance of symbiosis between human beings and a population of wild animals?"(169).

In this novel, Amitav Ghosh traps the human inhabitants in the forest area. Kanai Dutta, a Delhi businessman comes to Lusibari to visit his aunt Nilima Bose. His uncle Nirmal Bose has leftsome papers for Kanai at the time of his death. In his papers, Nirmal wrote about his life in morichjhapi, a forestland. In this tide country, he became a close friend of Horen and often visited the house of Horen who lived with his wife Kusum and his son Fokir. Morichjhapi is a place where the Bangladesh refugees settled, but they were evicted the place by saying that it was a reserve forest to save tigers. "Morichjhapi was a protected forest reserve and they had proved unbending in their determination to evict the settlers" (119).

The poor settlers had a great attachment towards every species in the Sunderbans. They lived by interacting with the land, by fishing, by planting the soil and by loving the animals. While evicting the poor refugees, Kusum outburst with pain,

Who are these peoples... who love animals so much that they were willing to kill us for them... the whole world has become a place of animals and our faults, our crime was that we were just human beings. (262).

Finally, the settlers of Morichjhapi were overpowered, huts burnt, women raped and thrown to the water by the forest officers. In contrast, the rich and powerful Scotsman, Sir Daniel Hamilton bought thousand acres of the Sunderbans with an aim to establish a society. The Government encouraged his activities and supported his schemes. This unequal justice promotes the novel to have the central issue-man-animal conflict. "Not a day passed without the news of someone being killed by a tiger, snake or crocodile" (79). In the Island of Lusibari, the silence of the night was broken by the growl of the Tiger. So Nilima states with fear:

I know that in this day and age in the twenty first century, it is difficult for you to imagine yourself being attracted by a tiger. The trouble is that over here it's not in the least bit out of the ordinary. It happens several times each week. (240).

Every day, Man has to struggle for survival from the animals and the animals have to struggle for survival from the human beings. Man killing the animals and the animals killing the men are often happening scenes in the Sunderban. The mind of the people is always haunted with the fear of animals.

In the novel *The Hungry Tide*, Ghosh presents the physical and psychological fear of the people about the forest clearly. Though the characters of the novel, Ghosh makes the readers to feel the fear. In order to stimulate the fear of Kanai, the native fisherman Horen says, "Because it's the fear that protects you, saar, it's what keeps you alive. Without it the danger doubles" (244). In the visual hallucination, Kanai sees the tiger, "The upper parts of its coat were of a colour that shone like gold in the sunlight, but its belly was dark and caked with mud" (329).

According to the belief of the village folk in the Sunderban, to see a tiger is to be as good as dead. All the deaths that happen by tiger attacks occur only in the off stage of the novel expect the death of Kusum's father. While searching for firewood, Kusum's father rowed across the river and he was unable to see the tiger hiding in the trees. On seeing the tiger, Kusum, who stood on the bank, cried and gathered the villagers to catch the attention of her father. But all her efforts failed because of the blowing of wind in the wrong direction. The tiger killed her father in front of her and dragged the corpse into the forest. The family couldn't claim any compensation as it was a reserved area.

J. Fayrer, the English naturalist, who coined the term 'The Royal Bengal Tiger', states that in a six years period between 1860 and 1866, 4,218 people were killed by tigers in the West Bengal. Ghosh in this novel enumerates the reasons for tiger attacks. The foremost reason is the human settlement in the forest area. Secondly, due to the shortage of the fresh water, the tigers prefer human flesh. Though the forest department provides pools of fresh water that make no difference. As a conservationist, Piya voices for the wildlife protection without concerning the human beings. So Kanai raises his voice by saying,

If there were killing on that scale anywhere else on earth it would be called a genocide, and yet here it goes almost unremarked: these killings are never reported, never written about in the papers. And the reason is just that these people are too poor to matter. We all know it, but we choose not to see it. Isn't that a horror too—that we can feel the suffering of an animal, but not of human beings? (301).

But everyone in the Sunderbans fails to accept the truth of their settlement in the dwelling place of animal. Ghosh presents the geological description about the Ganges that flows into the forest. It's a place of the crocodiles which drag their prey including the human beings into the underwater. "A crocodile, it's said, will keep you alive until you drown; it won't kill you on land; it'll drag you into the water while you're still breathing. Nobody finds the remains of people who're killed by crocodiles" (328).

The novel sprays some details about the cyclones that make the people to lose their lives. Human beings and animals are suffered by the natural calamities like the Storms, Tsunami, high temperature, flood... etc. the nature also taking revenge against the habitants for swindling the peace of the forest. When Piya faces the dangerous cyclonic attack, she prays, "Let it be on land, whatever happens, let it be on land, not the water please. Not the water" (372). Ghosh succeeds in showering the idea that the nature is the preserver as well as the destroyer.

In this novel, Ghosh makes awareness to the tide country people through the cetologist Piya with a great pleasure; she has to quit the place for submitting the current condition of the Irrawaddy dolphin to the higher authorities. With a voluminous hope of returning to Lusibari to do project with the funds from conservation and environmental groups, Piya advises the population to project the wild' life. Dolphins become victims in the trade market because, "These dolphins were hunted

with rifles and explosives and their carcasses were hung up in the sun so that their fat would drip into buckets. This oil was then used to run boats and motorcycles” (306). The fast moving motor-boats hit the dolphins that lead to death in dolphin habitats. All kinds of fish dwindle because of the use of nylon nets that drag the eggs too. As the result of these activities, the river is polluted and mass of fish disappear. So the entire ecosystem becomes shapeless.

Nirmal records the ecological changes in the Sunderban-once the sky was crowded by the flock of birds at sunset, and the mud banks were filled with the swarming crabs. But now the entire glory visions start to fade. “That colour began to fade long ago and it is never seen any more. Where had they gone, I wondered, those millions of swarming crabs, those birds” (215).

Acknowledging its biodiversity, the Sunderbans has been identified as a world Heritage site by the International Union for the conservation of nature. Yet, illegal activities like deforestation, poaching the animals, destroying the various species of fish, polluting the water, swindling the land...etc lead the food chain of the ecosystem to breakup step by step. For sustaining their livelihood in the forest area, everyman with his monstrous ego believes that no other species is more superior to him. Finally, nothing will be left to him. Once he starts to kill all the species that paves his way to kill another man. Morality becomes weaker.

Thus, in this novel *The Hungry Tide*, Ghosh directs the human mind towards eco-consciousness. The novel is a milestone which establishes the new ecological ethics and environmental justice.

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Lack of Familial Gusto in Mahesh Dattani's *Where There's A Will*

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Abstract

Mahesh Dattani is one of the distinguished Indian English playwrights whose penetrating insight into Indian urban society is widely extolled. His play Where There's a Will is based on an upper-middle class industrial Gujarati family and its relation to individuals. Hasmukh Mehta is the protagonist of the play who had overriding influence over his family members until his mistress Kiran overrode his unpleasant and annoying attempts to destroy filial harmony. Hasmukh's dominance over his family members compelled him to believe that he is superior to all and he considered his son as dull as ditch water. He also feared that his son would override him. So he created rifts in the family to exercise his patriarchal dominance over others. After the death of Hasmukh, he ruled over his family through his 'will' that denied property rights to his family members. He made Kiran as his trustee who was a victim of circumstances but she rose to the occasions and created successfully a peaceful space in the 'unhomely home' of Hasmukh. Because of the nature of Hasmukh, there was no happiness, emotional attachment, enjoyment and understanding among the family members.

Keywords: Familial gusto, Will, Patriarchal, Marginalise, Postmodern.

Mahesh Dattani is a renowned playwright in Indian English literature. His play, *Where There's a Will* (1986) explores socio-cultural dynamics of postmodern society. The play is an insight depiction of the underlying tensions, interpersonal relations, and power fabrics existing within an urban middle-class Gujarati family. It is a type of unique critique on the changing ethos and relations in urban India. Moreover, the play exhorts a thoughtful response to gender roles and gender-based power equations existing within present society.

Hasmukh Mehta, the protagonist of the play, wants to control the life of everyone who surrounds him. He not only controls the life of his family members while he was alive but also makes an arrangement to control their lives after his death through his 'will'. Ajit, Hasmukh's son, says his father wants members of the family to dance to his tunes. The 'will' acts as a whip and its agent is Hasmukh's mistress

Kiran Jhaveri. Hasmukh's power of money and greed for absolute control over his family members has fractured the interpersonal relationship within the family. Like a typical modern family, there is a lack of emotional attachment, and understanding for one's views and opinions. Here, the politics of patriarchy not only marginalizes the female but also the male. According to the 'will', Ajit has to attend office nine to five daily and has to learn about business tactics from Kiran for which he will be getting an allowance. Similarly, Preeti will be getting an allowance after she becomes a mother and Sonal will also get an allowance. But they all have to act accordingly to get the benefit. On the surface level, it appears that Kiran too was subordinated by Hasmukh but her vibrant speech to Sonal reveals the truth. Kiran pities Hasmukh and says that he depended on her for everything. She asserts that he was not the decision maker. She also says that Hasmukh did not really want a mistress; he wanted a father. He saw in her a woman who would father him. She also says men never really grow. Sonal was docile with Hasmukh whereas Hasmukh was submissive with Kiran. This shows that Hasmukh held Sonal in the margins and Kiran was beyond it.

The setting of the play *Where There's a Will* is the lavish house of Hasmukh. The word 'lavish' denotes sarcastically that the house is full of properties. In the play, there are not only properties, but the characters also are mere properties. Every traditional Indian business man wants his son to take over the business. Hasmukh is the patriarch and a promising business man. He regards everyone in the house as useless. At first, Hasmukh feels his son Ajit to be bankrupt at the age of twenty three. When Ajit wants five lakhs to modernize the company, the MD father regrets his birth and for a moment even wishes him to be dead. Immediately, he realizes his mistake and modifies his prayer as "God make him a vegetable so that he will not interfere in my way" (8). Hasmukh does not give him liberty to even use the phone at home. When the play begins, Ajit is talking over the phone and Hasmukh enters through the main door. He says, "Ajit, I am expecting a call, you can talk to your friend later" (5). Moreover, the dialogue between Hasmukh and Ajit shows the dominance of Hasmukh over his son:

HASMUKH . Wrong! I Hasmukh Metha, have every right. It's my phone you are using in my house, and it's my business secrets you are leaking to government officers, and my typists your friend is flirting with.

AJIT. Don't I have any rights at all?

HASMUKH. You have the right to listen to my advice and obey my orders. (6)

Hasmukh is a dictator who tells his son, "listen to my advice and obey my orders and polish my shoes every morning" (6). He has a general opinion about women that they are false assurers. Dattani gives a very lively statement to prove the concept. Hasmukh says "if you ask them if breakfast, lunch or dinner is ready, they say yes but it is never so" (4). He calls Preeti, his daughter-in-law as brilliant. According to him, she is after his money, that is the reason why she married Ajit. At a glance one feels that, Hasmukh is a man of steel with correctness at every step. His health chart shows that he is terribly weak. He suffers from high cholesterol and blood pressure as well as an enlarged heart. He says he gets indigestion and ulcer. He blames the family members for his illness: "In the olden days, if you said someone had a large heart, you meant he was generous and loving. Today it means he is receiving high aggravation from his twenty-three-year-old son and his scheming daughter-in-law" (4).

Hasmukh also says that, his son Ajit is a big zero and if at all Ajit makes sense, it is because the big zero has a one in front. The number one is unmistakable Hasmukh himself. In this manner another earning member of the family is criticized. For both Ajit and Hasmukh, their family relationship is secondary when compared to money. This is the reason for Ajit to expect his father's property

after his death and for the same reason, the 'will' is a great disappointment. Ajit says on the phone, "Actually I don't give a damn. I mean one day it's all going to be mine. And then I can do all the things I've wanted to do. All the changes, I've been thinking of making" (4-5). But the 'will' of his father disappoints him a lot.

Hasmukh Mehta has no respect and love for his wife Sonal. She is to him good for nothing. In fact, she is a chaste and obedient wife, but what Hasmukh expects from his wife is something disgusting one. He says; "Then I should be very happy man. I've got a loving wife who has been faithful to me like any dog would be" (23). His words throw ample light on the fact that Hasmukh's notion of faithful wife is as good as faithful dog that acts as per provided training without using her own discretion. Actually, Sonal is an innocent and ignorant woman who doesn't know about his sexual lust and his enjoyment with night women. She is a devoted and decent wife, but her husband is perverted and a rude creature. At the end, Sonal and Kiran join hands to eradicate the evil of sexual colonialism. They are gifted with the ability to assess and subsequently shaking off unjust shackle of patriarchy.

Sonal does not have any of the above mentioned aspects of married woman. Hasmukh is highly dissatisfied with the manner in which his life has been spent with no one living up to his expectation, the way he had lived up to his father's expectation. Hasmukh's aim is to seek revenge through his 'will', which will be released only after his death. He suffers from blood pressure, cholesterol, diabetes and salt in the urine. He was prone to so many life risks due to his disorders, but he blames his family members for his physical sufferings. He does not expect death which confronts him very soon.

As a matter of fact, all troubles come out of Hasmukh's false notions of joy and happiness of life. He considers domination as the only and final system which can bring joy and happiness in the family. Ironically he fails to understand that domination kills the joy of human heart and soul. Domination flourishes killing other's self and identity. It is, in fact, biggest hurdle in building up the premise of happiness.

After sometime Hasmukh is dead and he lazes around as a ghost. From this onwards, instead of Hasmukh, his ghost speaks. He sees his ad in obituary as 'Garment Tycoon Dead'. As Hasmukh mentions all are in anguish, but at the same time, they are all waiting for the next thing to happen. Exactly after one week, the concerned officers come to read out the 'will'. The family members are drenched in a shock. Through the following conversation among the family members, Dattani has shown the agony and distrust of their mind:

SONAL. He has ruined us! Minal will be shocked when she hears this.

PREETI. To hell with Minal! As if it makes any difference to her!

SONAL. If I wasn't so exhausted, I would stop you from talking about my sister like that!

AJIT (groaning also). He has ruined us! The old man has taken us for a nice ride. (28)

Preeti accuses Sonal that if she had been nicer, it would not happen like this. She says he wasn't nice to her but she adjusted. Sonal leaves an open statement that she would have left him if she knew he had a mistress. They very soon find out that they were not liable to make use of the property immediately. Preeti wants to contest the 'will'. Sonal says he must be mad to do this to them. Preeti says, they could get the certificate to prove that he was a senile. She goes still further and says that they could prove through Doctor Jhunjhunwalla that he was ill for the past few months. Very soon, Kiran enters the house and gets herself self introduced.

Then Ajit recaps the 'will'. It dissolved when he is forty five years old, the year when his father feels him to have attained complete maturity, he can do what he wants with that money. Ajit tells

Minal that his mother was not at fault. Usually, it is the lady who is blamed for men's fault. This is patriarchy, this is domination and thus it means suppression. He says that his father has formed a Charitable Trust. He has donated all his property, finance and shares to the Trust including the house they live in. They would all get an allowance from that Trust monthly. Sonal reminds the family members that Ajit has to attend office every day at 9am and he can only leave at 6pm. He even has to have his lunch there. The 'will' also stated that no new business project would be sanctioned for Ajit, and Sonal continues to say that, if they do not abide by the 'will', Kiran tries to make them understand that she had no hand in this issue. Sonal becomes weary and Preeti stresses the point of suppression of the whole family. The whole family stood subordinated to the lady Kiran as per the 'will' and it was publicly noticed by everyone.

Kiran declares that there is no proof for their relationship. Preeti pronounces that they must contest the 'will'. She makes it very clear that she is only the trustee and not the owner. It is her job and she gets a salary for it. Kiran says that everything rightfully belongs to three of them provided they follow office as usual. Mrs Mehta shall get a regular allowance to run the house and little more for her personal expenses. Preeti too will get an allowance, when she becomes a mother. When her child is twenty-one, the Trust automatically dissolves. Its holdings will be transferred to Ajit and his heirs. She also tells them that her main duty is to run the Mehta group of companies on behalf of Ajit, and she has the authority to make all the major decisions in the interest of the companies. Her duty also extends to train Ajit and delegate responsibilities to him in phases. Most importantly of all instructions, she must leave her husband and stay here as part of Mehta family. Sonal feels terribly irritated. She feels that Hasmukh had planned the presence of Kiran, just to remind her of her inadequacy. She feels that it was his master plan.

At last, they have no choice but to allow Kiran to stay back at home. They decide to make her stay outside the house. But Sonal decides to make her stay in her own room. She says, "She can share my room! Mrs Jhaveri and I have a lot to discuss" (43). In her short stay, Kiran finds out the crime committed by Preeti. She had interchanged the tablets for BP and vitamin, which Hasmukh used for his health. Kiran enquires about the issue to Preeti and Preeti immediately agrees. As Hasmukh himself mentions, Preeti married Ajit only for his money.

Hasmukh Mehta's parental authority was a tension not only for Sonal and Preeti, but also for Kiran. She confesses that she managed her relationship with an old and erratic man like Hasmukh, only for money. Here Dattani explores the Post-colonial and multi-cultural India. It has been adroitly clear that due to his lack of ethics and sexual transgression, Hasmukh Mehta was flung out of the frying pan into the fire. Hasmukh died many times, his corporeal demise was seen when he was enjoying cigar that the best treatment was given by the playwright to an egoist having self-pride. While Kiran made a full stop to all types of friction in the Mehta family, his ghost could not stand with a re-energized home free from his hellish dominance.

Mahesh Dattani's entire work may be seen as a depiction of conflict between the older and the younger generations. He has accorded greater importance to those issues which largely remain hidden in our society. He has the unique capacity to read the rumblings of contemporary Indian society and smell the unceasing clash between tradition and modernity. Family relations are the keys to the plots of Dattani's plays. He basically deals with issues which are considered to be invisible taboo by the Indian society like gender discrimination, homosexuality, transgender, patriarchy, communalism and so on. He takes his subjects from within the complicated dynamics of modern urban families. Families are composed of unique individuals. That uniqueness stems from the fact that every individual has creativity and free will and he/she is able to make his/her own choices.

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Lack of Familial Love and Affection in Sashi Deshpande's *The Dark Holds No Terrors*

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Abstract

*This paper studies the novel *The Dark Holds No Terrors*, where Sashi Deshpande explains, how a deserted attitude is kept for a girl child by her own parents and how that girl becomes a psychiatric patient and permanent sufferer till coming over by own declaration. Novel presents the suffocating feeling of a girl, who never gets love from her parents and looks marriage as a heaven on the earth, but after marriage she finds dichotomy between her prospect and reality. It is a story of internal and external distressing experiences of a middle-class educated working woman, who is a famous physician and working person. Her dichotomy breaks out with self-realization and conflicts the entire situation. She takes a lengthy expedition painfully with sour experiences to come over this situation.*

Keywords: Suffocate, annihilated, petrified, patriarchy, mirage.

Shashi Deshpande is an Indian novelist who was born in 1938 in Karnataka and educated in Bombay and Bangalore. Deshpande has written four children's books, a number of short stories, and nine novels, besides several perceptive essays, available in a volume entitled *Writing from the Margin and Other Essays*. Her first novel, *The Dark Holds No Terrors*, was published in 1980. In most of her works Sashi Deshpande depicts the piteous state of women.

God has created everything in this world in a beautiful manner. God's every creation in this world has its own significance. He created everything such as plants, animals, birds and many other things in this world. But those creatures were not created according to the resemblance of God. Think how God has love upon the human beings. But God is really upset with present evils in this society. God not only creates a man, he also creates a women companion for the man from his own bone. Every religious scripture praises the wife, the women and they don't consider them as inferior.

In Bible when Salomon writes about a "virtuous wife", he comments like this: "For her worth is far above rubies" (Proverbs 31:10). Quran says like this "Women shall with justice similar to exercised against them (men)" (Quran 2:228). Lord Krishna Says, "Men can achieve purity, prosperity, grace, fame, glory, endurance, patience and intelligence through women". Thus all religions provide a significant

place for women. But in practical life the real state of women is very different and pathetic. Women are considered and treated submissive and inferior in the society. They are denied of their own rights. They are harassed and abused. They are considered only as an object and a toy for pleasure. No one understands her own feeling and emotions. Even in much Family the treatment between boy and girl is different.

In this novel “Dark Holds No Terrors”, Sashi Deshpande depicts how the tender heart of Saru longs for love and care from her parents. Saru is projected as a victim of childhood uncertainty. Parental love is essential for the development of a child, but Saru lacks it. She has no kind word or word of appreciation and affection for her father or mother. The father is a sign of apathy indifference. Saru has no word of honour for her mother. As long as the mother is alive, there is no love and affection between among mother and daughter. She is unable to put-up with the mother’s excessive fondness shown towards her brother. She feels envious of her brother to see him receiving all the parental care and consideration. Her mother is a kind of woman who believes a girl to be a legal responsibility and a boy an asset. Here, to her mother, the boy is more significant than the girl. Her father takes least interest in her studies or development. His dissimilarity can be analyzed as an oblique expression of patriarchy that is emotionally harmful. She is not given any significance. No parental love and care is poured on her.

Saru is the main character of this novel, who married Manohar against her parents’ wish. So she leaves her home has no contact with her parents. When Saru returns to her parents’ home after the dispute with her husband she feels that many things have changed in her home. Her father smiles at her for the first time, which is a different act towards her. Saru mentions that, “He gave her a smile. The first smile she had for him” (18). But her father’s first smile was not a replica of his love and affection; it is only a way of apologizing to Saru for not putting up his dead wife’s photograph. This shows the relationship between Saru and her father. From this we can understand that she doesn’t enjoy the shade of her father’s love. She feels that after the death of her mother, her father has changed completely. Before her mother’s death her father doesn’t bother about the family activity. It is said,

During Saru’s childhood days she doesn’t have much attachment with her father, like Dhruva. Saru longs for her father’s love. “It had been Dhruva sitting on Baba’s lap and talking to him. And I thought ... I must show Baba something, anything to take his attention away from Dhruva sitting on his lap. I must, make him listen to me, no to Dhruva. I must make him ignore Dhruva”. (32)

Saru thinks that her father must ignore her brother. This shows that how much she was denied , avoided and uncared by her parents for the only reason of being a ‘girl child’. This makes the little soft heart of Saru suffocate. When Saru finds Madhav talking with Saru’s father about his college activities she feels for that because her father never asks her in her childhood about her school or college activities. She says, “He never took any interest in my school or college. He left it all to her. And she never really cared. Not after Dhruva’s death. I died long before I left home” (32). Her mother hurts her more when her brother Dhruva died. Her mother says, “Why didn’t you die? Why are you alive and he dead?” (34). This shows how indifferent her parents are with her.

When Saru is arranging the things in the cupboard she finds a bundle of photographs. She searches for her individual photograph but fails to find any of that. But she is able to find a photo of her, but it is not an individual one. It is the photo taken with her brother Dhruva. She feels for that and thinks she is annihilated. It is said, “There was no photograph of herself, she noticed without emotion. As if she had indeed been annihilated” (59).

When Madhav asks Saru to keep her mother's sari with herself she replies abruptly that she doesn't have any good memories of her mother: "I don't have any good memories of my mother" (59). This shows the improper relationship between Saru and her mother. Each and every child is beautiful and special to its mother.

Every mother considers her own daughter or son as princess or prince. But Saru's mother is an exceptional case. She tells to her own daughter that she is very ugly and she won't be good-looking even in her future: "You will never be good looking"(61). This shows the ruthless character of her mother.

She also hurts Saru for her dark complexion. It shows the cruel nature of her mother. She doesn't have soft corner for Saru in her heart. After the death of Dhruva, Saru is taken by Mashvi, a neighbour. Mashvi cares Saru very much; she plaited her hair with lots of love and care. After few days Saru's mother asks Saru to return home, but Saru is not ready to go home. She says, "I don't want to go. Not today" (74). Through this incident we can understand the tender heart of Saru, who is longing for affection from her parents.

Saru's choice of marriage is a comfort against the resentment of her parents. The slackness of mother, indifference of father and the burden of the guilt of the death of brother, forced Saru to depart her parental home and to seek spaces in professional life. The shade of the brutality of her mother, who emits her off from the family and let her stroll in void with her own deserted fate, makes her restless. The fear of being betrayed or being discarded remains rooted in her notice. Saru leaves her parental home influenced by the romantic fancy of Manohar who says, "When we're together, its heaven, wherever we are" (38).

After marriage Saru enjoys better economic and social status and also enjoys a pleasant-sounding relationship as Monohar's wife but after she becomes a lady doctor, equation changes. Both Manohar and Saru travel not only in different directions but even in opposite directions. In everything, be it intellect or occupation or success or ambition she surpasses her husband. Slowly Saru's social and economic status grows far beyond those of her husband. She is a demanding successful doctor in difference to Manu who is an under-salaried lecturer in a third rate college. She establishes herself as a career woman, and her job satisfies her ego, but this brings her no gladness at home.

Manohar's sense of inferiority changes him into a sadist, who gets pleasure by insulting his wife, harassing and, hurting her sexuality. She is two persons in one woman; she is a successful doctor during day time and a terrible petrified trapped animal at night. The sour understanding dawns upon her that the idea of the concept of love in marriage is a mirage, and an delusion. She considers that marriage is nothing and says,

Love... There was no such thing between man and woman.
There was only a need which both fought against, futilely,
the very futility turning into the thing they called 'love'.
It's only a word, she thought. Take away the word, the idea,
and the concept will wither away (72).

The only reason for her love affair is the lack of parental love and affection. Thus Sashi beautifully depicts the various state of Saru who longs for love, care and affection in her work *The Dark Holds No Terror*.

Work Cited

1. Deshpande, Shashi. *The Darks Holds No Terrors*, New Delhi: Penguin Books, India 1990.
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shashi_Deshpande.